

Appendix 3.1: Additional references

Contents

3.2.1	General importance of biodiversity for ecosystem functions and services	1
3.2.2	Positive effect of biodiversity on the magnitude of ecosystem functioning.....	2
3.2.3	Effects of biodiversity on stability and resilience of ecosystem functioning	6
3.2.4	Importance of all hierarchical levels of biodiversity.....	7
3.4.9	Vascular plants	9
3.4.10	Bryophytes	10

3.2.1 General importance of biodiversity for ecosystem functions and services

- Brose U, Hillebrand H. 2016. Biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in dynamic landscapes. *Phil.Trans. R. Soc. B* 371, 20150267. (doi:10.1098/rstb.2015.0267)
- Cardinale B.J., Bennett D.M., Nelson C.E., Gross K. 2009 c. Does productivity drive diversity or vice versa? A test of the multivariate productivity–diversity hypothesis in streams // *Ecology*. V. 90. N. 5. P. 1227–1241.
- Cardinale BJ, Hillebrand H, Harpole WS, Gross K, Ptacnik R. 2009 b. Separating the influence of resource ‘availability’ from resource ‘imbalance on productivity–diversity relationships. *Ecol. Lett.* 12, 475–487. doi 10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01317.x
- Cardinale BJ, Ives AR, Inchausti P. 2004. Effects of species diversity on the primary productivity of ecosystems: extending our spatial and temporal scales of inference. *Oikos* 104: 437–450.
- Grace, J.B. 2006. *Structural Equation Modeling and Natural Systems*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Grace, J. B., D. R. Schoolmaster Jr., G. R. Guntenspergen, A. M. Little, B. R. Mitchell, K. M. Miller, and E. W. Schweiger. 2012. Guidelines for a graph-theoretic implementation of structural equation modeling. *Ecosphere* 3(8):73. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1890/ES12-00048.1>
- Vellend, M., Geber, M.A. 2005. Connections between species diversity and genetic diversity. *Ecol. Lett.*, 8, 767–781.Hillebrand H, Matthiessen B. 2009 Biodiversity in a complex world: consolidation and progress in functional biodiversity research. *Ecol. Lett.*12, 1405–1419. doi:10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01388.x
- Mensens C., De Laender F., Janssen C.R., Sabbe K., De Troch M. 2015. Stressor-induced biodiversity gradients: revisiting biodiversity–ecosystem functioning relationships. *Oikos* 124: 677–684. doi: 10.1111/oik.01904
- Meyer, S.T., Ebeling, A., Eisenhauer, N., Hertzog, L., Hillebrand, H., Milcu, A., Pompe, S., Abbas, M., Bessler, H., Buchmann, N., De Luca, E., Engels, C., Fischer, M., Gleixner, G., Hudewenz, A., Klein, A.-M., de Kroon, H., Leimer, S., Loranger, H., Mommer, L., Oelmann, Y., Ravenek, J.M., Roscher, C., Rottstock, T., Scherber, C., Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Scheu, S., Schmid, B., Schulze, E.-D., Staudler, A., Strecker, T., Temperton, V., Tscharnkte, T., Vogel, A., Voigt, W., Weigelt, A., Wilcke,

W., & Weisser, W.W. (2016). Effects of biodiversity strengthen over time as ecosystem functioning declines at low and increases at high biodiversity. *Ecosphere*, 7, e01619.

Mueller KE, Tilman D, Fornara D, Hobbie SE. 2013. Root depth distribution and the diversity-productivity relationship in a long-term grassland experiment. *Ecology* 94:787–93

Reich PB, Tilman D, Isbell F, Mueller K, Hobbie SE, Flynn DFB, Eisenhauer N. 2012. Impacts of biodiversity loss escalate through time as redundancy fades. *Science* 336, 589–592.

(doi:10.1126/science.1217909)Tylianakis JM, Rand TA, Kahmen A, Klein A-M, Buchmann N, Perner J, Tschamntke T. 2008. Resource Heterogeneity Moderates the Biodiversity-Function Relationship in Real World Ecosystems. *PLoS Biol* 6 (5): e122. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.0060122

3.2.2 Positive effect of biodiversity on the magnitude of ecosystem functioning

Aerts R., Honnay O. 2011. Forest restoration, biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. *BMC Ecology*. 11:29. doi: 10.1186/1472-6785-11-29Allhoff KT, Drossel B. 2016. Biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in evolving food webs. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 371, 20150281. doi:10.1098.rstb.2015.0281

Aguirre JD, Marshall DJ. 2012. Genetic diversity increases population productivity in a sessile marine invertebrate. *Ecology* 93: 1134–1142. doi:10.1890/11-1448.1.

Altukhov Yu.P. 2003. Genetic processes in populations. Moscow, PTC “Academkniga”. 431 p. (In Russian).

Atwater DZ, Callaway RM. 2015. Testing the mechanisms of diversitydependentoveryielding in a grass species. *Ecology*, doi:10.1890/15-0889.1.

Balvanera P, Pfisterer AB, Buchmann N, He J-S, Nakashizuka T, Raffaelli D, Schmid B. 2006 Quantifying the evidence for biodiversity effects on ecosystem functioning and services. *Ecol. Lett.* 9, 1146–1156. doi:10.1111/j.1461-0248.2006.00963.x

Barnes AD, Weigelt P, Jochum M, Ott D, Hodapp D, Haneda NF, Brose U. 2016. Species richness and biomass explain spatial turnover in ecosystem functioning across tropical and temperate ecosystems. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 371:20150279. Doi: 10.1098/rstb.2015.0279

Baruffo M, Schmid B, Bruelheide H, Chi X, Hector A, Ma K., Michalski S., Tang Z., Niklaus P.A. 2013. Biodiversity Promotes Tree Growth during Succession in Subtropical Forest. *PLoS One*. 8(11): e81246. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0081246

Bell, G., Collins, S., 2008. Adaptation, extinction and global change. *Evol. Appl.* 1, 3–16.

Cardinale B., Duffy E., Srivastava D., Loreau M., Thomas M., Emmerson M. 2009 a. Towards a food web perspective on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning // *Biodiversity, Ecosystem Functioning, and Human Wellbeing: An Ecological and Economic Perspective*. Eds.: Naeem S., Bunker D.E., Hector A., Loreau M., Perrings C. Oxford University Press, Oxford, United Kingdom. P. 105-120.

Cardinale BJ, Hillebrand H, Harpole WS, Gross K, Ptacnik R. 2009 b. Separating the influence of resource ‘availability’ from resource ‘imbalance on productivity–diversity relationships. *Ecol. Lett.* 12, 475–487. doi 10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01317.x

Cardinale B.J., Matulich K.L., Hooper D.U., Byrnes J.E., Duffy E., Gamfeldt L., Balvanera P., O’Connor M.I., Gonzalez A. 2011. The functional role of producer diversity in ecosystems. *Am. J. Bot.* 98, 572–592. Cardinale B.J., Srivastava D.S., Duffy J.E., Wright J.P., Downing A.L., Sankaran M.,

- Jouseau C. 2006. Effects of biodiversity on the functioning of trophic groups and ecosystems // *Nature*. V. 443. P. 989–992.
- Cavanaugh, K. C., Gosnell, J. S., Davis, S. L., Ahumada, J., Boundja, P., Clark, D. B., Mugerwa, B., Jansen, P. A., O'Brien, T. G., Rovero, F., Sheil, D., Vasquez, R. and Andelman, S. (2014), Carbon storage in tropical forests correlates with taxonomic diversity and functional dominance on a global scale. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 23: 563–573. doi:10.1111/geb.12143
- Chisholm, R. A., Muller-Landau, H. C., Abdul Rahman, K., Bebbler, D. P., Bin, Y., Bohlman, S. A., Bourg, N. A., Brinks, J., Bunyavejchewin, S., Butt, N., Cao, H., Cao, M., Cárdenas, D., Chang, L.-W., Chiang, J.-M., Chuyong, G., Condit, R., Dattaraja, H. S., Davies, S., Duque, A., Fletcher, C., Gunatilleke, N., Gunatilleke, S., Hao, Z., Harrison, R. D., Howe, R., Hsieh, C.-F., Hubbell, S. P., Itoh, A., Kenfack, D., Kiratiprayoon, S., Larson, A. J., Lian, J., Lin, D., Liu, H., Lutz, J. A., Ma, K., Malhi, Y., McMahon, S., McShea, W., Meegaskumbura, M., Mohd. Razman, S., Morecroft, M. D., Nytch, C. J., Oliveira, A., Parker, G. G., Pulla, S., Punchi-Manage, R., Romero-Saltos, H., Sang, W., Schurman, J., Su, S.-H., Sukumar, R., Sun, I.-F., Suresh, H. S., Tan, S., Thomas, D., Thomas, S., Thompson, J., Valencia, R., Wolf, A., Yap, S., Ye, W., Yuan, Z. and Zimmerman, J. K. (2013), Scale-dependent relationships between tree species richness and ecosystem function in forests. *J Ecol*, 101: 1214–1224. doi:10.1111/1365-2745.12132
- Cook-Patton SC, McArt SH, Parachnowitsch AL, Thaler JS, Agrawal AA. 2011. A direct comparison of the consequences of plant genotypic and species diversity on communities and ecosystem function. *Ecology* 92:915–923
- Covich A.P., Austen M.C., Bärlocher F., Chauvet E., Cardinale B.J, Biles C.L, Inchausti P., Dangles O., Solan M., Gessner M.O, Statzner B., Moss B. 2004. The role of biodiversity in the functioning of freshwater and marine benthic ecosystems // *BioScience*. V. 54. N. 8. P. 767-775.
- Delgado-Baquerizo M, Maestre FT, Reich PB, Jeffries TC, Gaitan JJ, Encinar D, Berdugo M, Campbell CD, Singh BK. 2016. Microbial diversity drives multifunctionality in terrestrial ecosystems. *Nat Commun*. 7:10541. doi: 10.1038/ncomms10541.
- Duffy JE, Carinale BJ, France KE, McIntyre PB, Thebault E, Loreau M. 2007. The functional role of biodiversity in ecosystems: incorporating trophic complexity. *Ecol. Lett.* 10, 522–538. doi:10.1111/j.1461-0248.2007.01037.x
- Duffy JE, Reynolds PL, Boström C, Coyer JA, Cusson M, Donadi S, Douglass JG, Eklöf JS, Engelen AH, Eriksson BK, Fredriksen S, Gamfeldt L, Gustafsson C, Hoarau G, Hori M, Hovel K, Iken K, Lefcheck JS, Moksnes PO, Nakaoka M, O'Connor MI, Olsen JL, Richardson JP, Ruesink JL, Sotka EE, Thormar J, Whalen MA, Stachowicz JJ. 2015. Biodiversity mediates top-down control in eelgrass ecosystems: a global comparative-experimental approach. *Ecol Lett.* 18(7): 696-705. doi: 10.1111/ele.12448.
- Engelhardt, K.A.M., Lloyd, M.W., Neel, M.C. 2014. Effects of genetic diversity on conservation and restoration potential at individual, population, and regional scales. *Biol.Conserv.* 179, 6–16. doi:10.1016/j.biocon. 2014.08.011
- Finn, J. A., Kirwan, L., Connolly, J., Sebastià, M. T., Helgadottir, A., Baadshaug, O. H., Bélanger, G., Black, A., Brophy, C., Collins, R. P., Čop, J., Dalmannsdóttir, S., Delgado, I., Elgersma, A., Fothergill, M., Frankow-Lindberg, B. E., Ghesquiere, A., Golinska, B., Golinski, P., Grieu, P., Gustavsson, A.-M., Höglind, M., Huguenin-Elie, O., Jørgensen, M., Kadziulienė, Z., Kurki, P., Llurba, R., Lunnan, T., Porqueddu, C., Suter, M., Thumm, U. and Lüscher, A. (2013), Ecosystem function enhanced by combining four functional types of plant species in intensively managed grassland mixtures: a 3-year continental-scale field experiment. *J Appl Ecol*, 50: 365–375. doi:10.1111/1365-2664.12041

- Frankham R. 2005. Genetics and extinction. *Biological Conservation* 126: 131–140.
- Griffin JN, Byrnes JEK, Cardinale BJ. 2013. Effects of predator richness on prey suppression: a metaanalysis. *Ecology* 94, 2180–2187. (doi:10.1890/13-0179.1)
- Griffiths S.W., Armstrong J.D. 2001. The benefits of genetic diversity outweigh those of kin association in a territorial animal // *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. V. 268. N. 1473. P. 1293-1296. doi: 10.1098/rspb.2001.1660
- Gross, K., Cardinale, B. J. The functional consequences of random vs. ordered species extinctions. *Ecol. Lett.* 8, 409–418 (2005).
- Hughes, A. R., and J. J. Stachowicz. 2009. Ecological impacts of genotypic diversity in the clonal seagrass, *Zostera marina*. *Ecology* 90:1412–1419.
- Kotowska, A. M., Cahill Jr, J. F. and Keddie, B. A. (2010), Plant genetic diversity yields increased plant productivity and herbivore performance. *Journal of Ecology*, 98: 237–245. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2745.2009.01606.x
- Kuzishchin K.V., Gruzdeva M.A., Savvaitova K.A., Pavlov D.S., Stanford J.A. 2010. Seasonal races of chum salmon *Oncorhynchus keta* and their interrelations in Kamchatka Rivers. *Journal of Ichthyology*. 2010. T. 50. № 2. C. 159-173. Doi: 10.1134/S0032945210020037
- Larsen, T. H., Williams, N. M., Kremen, C. 2005. Extinction order and altered community structure rapidly disrupt ecosystem functioning. *Ecol. Lett.* 8, 538–547.
- Lecerf A., Richardson J.S. 2010. Biodiversity-ecosystem function research: insights gained from streams // *River Research and Applications*. V. 26. P. 45–54.
- Lefcheck, J. S. and Duffy, J. E. 2015. Multitrophic functional diversity predicts ecosystem functioning in experimental assemblages of estuarine consumers. *Ecology*, 96: 2973–2983. doi:10.1890/14-1977.1
- Liang J, Zhou M, Tobin PC, McGuire AD, Reich PB. 2015. Biodiversity influences plant productivity through niche-efficiency. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 112(18):5738-43. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1409853112.
- Massa SI, Paulino CM, Serrão EA, Duarte CM, Arnaud-Haond S. 2013. Entangled effects of allelic and clonal (genotypic) richness in the resistance and resilience of experimental populations of the seagrass *Zostera noltii* to diatom invasion. *BMC Ecology* 13:39_50 DOI 10.1186/1472-6785-13-39.
- Muller-Starck G., Ziehe M., Schubert R. 2005. Genetic Diversity Parameters Associated with Viability Selection, Reproductive Efficiency, and Growth in Forest Tree Species // *Forest Diversity and Function: Temperate and Boreal Systems*. Eds.: Scherer-Lorenzen M., Körner Ch., Schulze E.-D. *Ecological Studies*. V. 176. P. 87 – 108.
- Nadrowski K., Wirth C., Scherer-Lorenzen M. 2010. Is forest diversity driving ecosystem function and service? // *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*. V. 2. P. 75–79.
- O'Connor, N.E., and Donohue, I. 2013. Environmental context determines multi-trophic effects of consumer species loss. *Glob. Chang. Biol.*, 19, 431–440.
- Paquette A., Messier C. 2011. The effect of biodiversity on tree productivity: from temperate to boreal forests. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 2011. 20, 170–180
- Pautasso M., Holdenrieder O., Stenlid J. 2005. Susceptibility to fungal pathogens of forests differing in tree diversity // *Forest Diversity and Function Temperate and Boreal Systems*. Eds.: Scherer-

- Lorenzen M., Korner Ch., Schulze E.-D. *Ecological Studies*.V. 176. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. P. 41-64.
- Pavlov DS, Savvaitova KA, Kuzishchin KV, Bukvareva EN, Vericheva PE, Zvyagintsev VB, Maksimov SV, Augereau Z. 2007. Conservation Strategy of Kamchatka rainbow trout. Moscow, IEEP RAS. (In Russian).
- Pavlov D.S., Savvaitova K.A., Kuzishchin K.V., Gruzdeva M.A., Mal'Tsev A.Yu., Stanford J.A. 2008. Diversity of life strategies and population structure of Kamchatka mykiss *Parasalmo mykiss* in the ecosystems of small salmon rivers of various types. *Journal of Ichthyology*. 2008. T. 48. № 1. C. 37-44. Doi: 10.1134/S0032945208010049
- Poorter, L., van der Sande, M. T., Thompson, J., Arets, E. J. M. M., Alarcón, A., Álvarez-Sánchez, J., Ascarrunz, N., Balvanera, P., Barajas-Guzmán, G., Boit, A., Bongers, F., Carvalho, F. A., Casanoves, F., Cornejo-Tenorio, G., Costa, F. R. C., de Castilho, C. V., Duivenvoorden, J. F., Dutrieux, L. P., Enquist, B. J., Fernández-Méndez, F., Finegan, B., Gormley, L. H. L., Healey, J. R., Hoosbeek, M. R., Ibarra-Manríquez, G., Junqueira, A. B., Levis, C., Licona, J. C., Lisboa, L. S., Magnusson, W. E., Martínez-Ramos, M., Martínez-Yrizar, A., Martorano, L. G., Maskell, L. C., Mazzei, L., Meave, J. A., Mora, F., Muñoz, R., Nytch, C., Pansonato, M. P., Parr, T. W., Paz, H., Pérez-García, E. A., Rentería, L. Y., Rodríguez-Velazquez, J., Rozendaal, D. M. A., Ruschel, A. R., Sakschewski, B., Salgado-Negret, B., Schiatti, J., Simões, M., Sinclair, F. L., Souza, P. F., Souza, F. C., Stropp, J., ter Steege, H., Swenson, N. G., Thonicke, K., Toledo, M., Uriarte, M., van der Hout, P., Walker, P., Zamora, N. and Peña-Claros, M. 2015. Diversity enhances carbon storage in tropical forests. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 24: 1314–1328. doi:10.1111/geb.12364
- Ptácnik R, Solimini AG, Andersen T, Tamminen T, Brettum P, Lepistö L, Willén E, Rekolainen S. 2008 Diversity predicts stability and resource use efficiency in natural phytoplankton communities. *Proc.Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 105, 5134–5138. doi 10.1073/pnas.0708328105
- Reed DH, Frankham R. 2003. Correlation between fitness and genetic diversity. *Conservation Biology* 17:230-237 DOI 10.1046/j.1523-1739.2003.01236.x
- Scherber C, Eisenhauer N, Weisser WW, Schmid B, Voigt W, Fischer, M, Schulze, E D, Roscher, C, Weigelt, A., Allan E., Beßler H., Bonkowski M., Buchmann N., Buscot F., Clement L.W., Ebeling A., Engels C., Halle S., Kertscher I., Klein A.-M., Koller R., König S., Kowalski E., Kummer V., Kuu A., Lange M., Lauterbach D., Middelhoff C., Migunova V.D., Milcu A., Müller R., Partsch S., Petermann J.S., Renker C., Rottstock T., Sabais A., Scheu S., Schumacher J., Temperton V.M., Tschardt T. 2010. Bottom-up effects of plant diversity on multitrophic interactions in a biodiversity experiment. *Nature* 468:553–56
- Schindler D.E., Hilborn R., Chasco B., Boatright C.P. , Quinn T.P. , Rogers L.A., Webster M.S. 2010. Population diversity and the portfolio effect in an exploited species. *Nature* 465: 609–612.
- Schneider, F.D., Brose, U., Rall, B.C., Guill, C. 2016. Animal diversity and ecosystem functioning in dynamic food webs. *Nature Communications*, 7:12718. doi: 10.1038/ncomms12718
- Schmid B., Balvanera P., Cardinale B.J., Godbold J., Pfisterer A.B., Raffaelli D., Solan M., Srivastava D.S. 2009. Consequences of species loss for ecosystem functioning: meta-analyses of data from biodiversity experiments // *Biodiversity, ecosystem functioning, and human wellbeing: an ecological and economic perspective*. Eds.: Naeem S., Bunker D.E., Hector A., Loreau M., Perrings C. Oxford University Press, Oxford, United Kingdom. P. 14-29.
- Srivastava DS, Cardinale BJ, Downing AL, Duffy JE, Jouseau C, Sankaran M, Wright JP. 2009. Diversity has stronger top-down than bottom-up effects on decomposition. *Ecology* 90, 1073–1083.
- Stachowicz J.J., Bruno J.F., Duffy J.E. 2007. Understanding the Effects of Marine Biodiversity on

Communities and Ecosystems // Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst. V. 38. P. 739–66.

- Wang W., Lei X., Ma Z., Kneeshaw D.D., Peng C. 2011. Positive Relationship between Aboveground Carbon Stocks and Structural Diversity in Spruce-Dominated Forest Stands in New Brunswick, Canada. *Forest Science* 57(6) 2011. 506-515
- Willi, Y., Van Buskirk, J., Hoffmann, A.A., 2006. Limits to the adaptive potential of small populations. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* 37, 433–458.
- Yang L., Callaway R. M., Atwater D. Z. 2015. Root contact responses and the positive relationship between intraspecific diversity and ecosystem productivity. *AoB PLANTS* (2015) 7: plv053 doi: 10.1093/aobpla/plv053
- Yasuhara M, Doi H, Wei CL, Danovaro R, Myhre SE. 2016. Biodiversity-ecosystem functioning relationships in long-term time series and palaeoecological records: deep sea as a test bed. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 371 (1694). pii: 20150282. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2015.0282.
- Zhang Y., Chen H.Y.H., Reich P.B. 2012. Forest productivity increases with evenness, species richness and trait variation: a global meta-analysis. *Journal of Ecology* 2012, 100, 742–749. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2745.2011.01944.x

3.2.3 Effects of biodiversity on stability and resilience of ecosystem functioning

- Altukhov Yu.P. 2003. Genetic processes in populations. Moscow, PTC "Academkniga". 431 p. (In Russian).
- de Mazancourt C, Isbell F, Larocque A, Berendse F, De Luca E, Grace JB, Haegeman B, Wayne Polley H, Roscher C, Schmid B, Tilman D, van Ruijven J, Weigelt A, Wilsey BJ, Loreau M. 2013. Predicting ecosystem stability from community composition and biodiversity. *Ecol. Lett.* 16: 617–25. doi: 10.1111/ele.12088.
- Kuzishchin K.V., Gruzdeva M.A., Savvaitova K.A., Pavlov D.S., Stanford J.A. 2010. Seasonal races of chum salmon *Oncorhynchus keta* and their interrelations in Kamchatka Rivers. *Journal of Ichthyology*. 2010. T. 50. № 2. C. 159-173. Doi: 10.1134/S0032945210020037
- Loreau M., de Mazancourt C. 2013. Biodiversity and ecosystem stability: a synthesis of underlying mechanisms. *Ecology Letters*. 16: 106–115
- Menshutkin VV. 2003. Modeling of sockeye population of the Lake Far (Kamchatka) using individual-oriented method // *Biology of sea (Biologiya moray)*. N. 3. S. 217-221. (in Russian)
- Pavlov DS, Savvaitova KA, Kuzishchin KV, Bukvareva EN, Vericheva PE, Zvyagintsev VB, Maksimov SV, Augereau Z. 2007. Conservation Strategy of Kamchatka rainbow trout. Moscow, IEEP RAS. (In Russian).
- Pavlov D.S., Savvaitova K.A., Kuzishchin K.V., Gruzdeva M.A., Mal'Tsev A.Yu., Stanford J.A. 2008. Diversity of life strategies and population structure of Kamchatka mykiss *Parasalmo mykiss* in the ecosystems of small salmon rivers of various types. *Journal of Ichthyology*. 2008. T. 48. № 1. C. 37-44. Doi: 10.1134/S0032945208010049
- Ruijven, J. v., Berendse, F. 2007. Contrasting effects of diversity on the temporal stability of plant populations. *Oikos*, 116: 1323–1330. doi:10.1111/j.0030-1299.2007.16005.x
- Schindler D.E., Hilborn R., Chasco B., Boatright C.P., Quinn T.P., Rogers L.A., Webster M.S. 2010. Population diversity and the portfolio effect in an exploited species. *Nature* 465: 609–612.

Tilman, D., Reich, P. B. & Knops, J. M. H. 2006. Biodiversity and ecosystem stability in a decade-long grassland experiment. *Nature* 441, 629–632.

3.2.4 Importance of all hierarchical levels of biodiversity

Cadotte, M.W. 2015. Phylogenetic diversity and productivity: gauging interpretations from experiments that do not manipulate phylogenetic diversity. *Functional Ecology*, doi: 10.1111/1365-2435.12543.

Cadotte, M.W., Cardinale, B.J., Oakley, T. H. 2008. Evolutionary history and the effect of biodiversity on plant productivity. *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 105, 17012–17017. Díaz S., Lavorel S., de Bello F., Quétier F., Grigulis K., Robson T. M. 2007. Incorporating plant functional diversity effects in ecosystem service assessments. *PNAS*. V. 104. no. 52. 20684–20689, doi: 10.1073/pnas.0704716104

Cardinale B., Duffy E., Srivastava D., Loreau M., Thomas M., Emmerson M. 2009 a. Towards a food web perspective on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning // *Biodiversity, Ecosystem Functioning, and Human Wellbeing: An Ecological and Economic Perspective*. Eds.: Naeem S., Bunker D.E., Hector A., Loreau M., Perrings C. Oxford University Press, Oxford, United Kingdom. P. 105-120.

Clarke A., Gaston K.J. 2006. Climate, energy and diversity // *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. V. 273. P. 2257-2266.

Currie D.J., Mittelbach G.G., Cornell H.V., Field R., Guegan J.-F., Hawkins B.A., Kaufman D.M., Kerr J.T., Oberdorff T., O'Brien E., Turner J.R.G. 2004. Predictions and tests of climate-based hypotheses of broad-scale variation in taxonomic richness // *Ecology Letters*. V. 7. P. 1121–1134.

Cusens J., Wright S.D., McBride P.D., Gillman L.N. 2012. What is the form of the productivity-animal-species-richness relationship? A critical review and meta-analysis. *Ecology*. 93(10):2241-52.

Duffy JE, Carinale BJ, France KE, McIntyre PB, Thebault E, Loreau M. 2007. The functional role of biodiversity in ecosystems: incorporating trophic complexity. *Ecol. Lett.* 10, 522–538. doi:10.1111/j.1461-0248.2007.01037.x

Estes JA, Terborgh J, Brashares JS, Power ME, Berger J, Bond WJ, Carpenter SR, Essington TE, Holt RD, Jackson JB, Marquis RJ, Oksanen L, Oksanen T, Paine RT, Pikitch EK, Ripple WJ, Sandin SA, Scheffer M, Schoener TW, Shurin JB, Sinclair AR, Soulé ME, Virtanen R, Wardle DA. 2011. Trophic downgrading of planet earth. *Science* 333, 301–306. doi: 10.1126/science.1205106.

Faith DP, Magallón S, Hendry AP, Conti E, Yahara T, Donoghue MJ. 2010. Ecosystem services: An evolutionary perspective on the links between biodiversity and human well-being. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*. 2:66–74. DOI 10.1016/j.cosust.2010.04.002

Field R., O'Brien E., Whittaker R.J. 2005. Global models for predicting woody plant richness from climate: development and evaluation // *Ecology*. V. 86. N. 9. P. 2263-2277.

Flynn, D.F.B., Mirotnick, N., Jain, M., Palmer, M.I. & Naeem, S. 2011. Functional and phylogenetic diversity as predictors of biodiversity-ecosystem-function relationships. *Ecology* 92, 1573–1581.

Fraser LH, Pither J, Jentsch A, Sternberg M, Zobel M, Askarizadeh D, Bartha S, Beierkuhnlein C, Bennett JA, Bittel A, Boldgiv B, Boldrini II, Bork E, Brown L, Cabido M, Cahill J, Carlyle CN, Campetella G, Chelli S, Cohen O, Csergo AM, Díaz S, Enrico L, Ensing D, Fidelis A, Fridley JD, Foster B, Garris H, Goheen JR, Henry HA, Hohn M, Jouri MH, Klironomos J, Koorem K, Lawrence-

- Lodge R, Long R, Manning P, Mitchell R, Moora M, Müller SC, Nabinger C, Naseri K, Overbeck GE, Palmer TM, Parsons S, Pesek M, Pillar VD, Pringle RM, Roccaforte K, Schmidt A, Shang Z, Stahlmann R, Stotz GC, Sugiyama S, Szentes S, Thompson D, Tungalag R, Undrakhbold S, van Rooyen M, Wellstein C, Wilson JB, Zupo T. 2015. Worldwide evidence of a unimodal relationship between productivity and plant species richness *Science* 349 (6245), 302-305. doi: 10.1126/science.aab3916.
- Fussmann GF, Loreau M, Abrams PA. 2007. Eco-evolutionary dynamics of communities and ecosystems. *Funct. Ecol.* 21:465–77
- Gaston K.J. 2000. Global patterns in biodiversity // *Nature*. V. 405. P. 220-227.
- Gillman L.N., Wright S.D. 2006. The influence of productivity on the species richness of plants: a critical assessment // *Ecology*. V. 87. N. 5. P. 1234–1243.
- Gillman L.N., Wright S.D., Cusens J., McBride P.D., Malhi Y., Whittaker R.J. 2014. Latitude, productivity and species richness // *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 24, 107–117
- Gross K.L., Willig M.R., Gough L., Inouye R., Cox S.B. 2000. Species diversity and productivity at different spatial scales in herbaceous plant communities // *Oikos*. V. 89. P. 417-427.
- Hairston NH, Ellner SP, Geber MA, Yoshida T, Fox JA. 2005. Rapid evolution and the convergence of ecological and evolutionary time. *Ecol. Lett.* 8:1114–27
- Hawkins B.A., Field R., Cornell H.V., Currie D.J., Guégan J.-F., Kaufman D.M., Kerr J.T., Mittelbach G.G., Oberdorff T., O'Brien E.M., Porter E.E., Turner J.R.G. 2003. Energy, water and broad-scale geographic patterns of species richness // *Ecology*. V. 84. N. 12. P. 3105–3117.
- Johnson MTJ, Stinchcombe JR. 2007. An emerging synthesis between community ecology and evolutionary biology. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 22:250–57
- Lavelle S., Storkey J., Bardgett R. D., de Bello F., Berg M. P., Le Roux X., Moretti M., Mulder C., Pakeman R. J., Díaz S. and Harrington R. (2013), A novel framework for linking functional diversity of plants with other trophic levels for the quantification of ecosystem services. *J Veg Sci*, 24: 942–948. doi:10.1111/jvs.12083
- Lefcheck, J. S. and Duffy, J. E. 2015. Multitrophic functional diversity predicts ecosystem functioning in experimental assemblages of estuarine consumers. *Ecology*, 96: 2973–2983. doi:10.1890/14-1977.1
- McBride PD, Cusens J, Gillman LN. 2014. Revisiting spatial scale in the productivity–species richness relationship: fundamental issues and global change implications. *AoB PLANTS* 6: plu057; doi:10.1093/aobpla/plu057
- Mittelbach G.G., Steiner C.F., Scheiner S.M., Gross K.L., Reynolds H.L., Waide R.B., Willig M.R., Dodson S.I., Gough L. 2001. What is the observed relationship between species richness and productivity? // *Ecology*. V. 82. N. 9. P. 2381–2396.
- Petchey O.L., O’Gorman E.J., Flynn D.F.B. 2009. A functional guide to functional diversity measures // *Biodiversity, ecosystem functioning and human well-being: an ecological and economic perspective*. Eds.: Naeem S., Bunker D.E., Hector A., Loreau M., Perrings C. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK. P. 49 -59.
- Tittensor D.P., Mora C., Jetz W., Lotze H.K., Ricard D., Berghe E.V., Worm B. 2010. Global patterns and predictors of marine biodiversity across taxa // *Nature*. V. 466. P. 1098 – 1101.
- Venail P., Gross K., Oakley T. H., Narwani A., Allan E., Flombaum P., Isbell F., Joshi J., Reich P. B.,

Tilman, D., van Ruijven, J., Cardinale, B. J. 2015. Species richness, but not phylogenetic diversity, influences community biomass production and temporal stability in a re-examination of 16 grassland biodiversity studies. *Functional Ecology*, 29: 615–626. doi: 10.1111/1365-2435.12432

Whittaker R.J., Nogues-Bravo D., Araujo M.B. 2007. Geographical gradients of species richness: a test of the water-energy conjecture of Hawkins et al. (2003) using European data for five taxa // *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. V. 16. P. 76 – 89.

3.4.9 Vascular plants

Dengler, J., Janišová, M., Török, P., & Wellstein, C. (2014). Biodiversity of Palaeartic grasslands: A synthesis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 182, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.12.015>

García-Valdés, R., Svenning, J.-C., Zavala, M. a., Purves, D. W., & Araújo, M. B. (2015). Evaluating the combined effects of climate and land-use change on tree species distributions. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52, 902–912. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12453>

Hölzel, N., Haub, C., Ingelfinger, M. P., Otte, A., & Pilipenko, V. N. (2002). The return of the steppe large-scale restoration of degraded land in southern Russia during the post-Soviet era. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 10(2), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1078/1617-1381-00009>

Kamp, J., Koshkin, M. A., Bragina, T. M., Katzner, T. E., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Schreiber, D., ... Urazaliev, R. (2016). Persistent and novel threats to the biodiversity of Kazakhstan's steppes and semi-deserts. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1083-0>

Kamp, J., Urazaliev, R., Donald, P. F., & Hölzel, N. (2011). Post-Soviet agricultural change predicts future declines after recent recovery in Eurasian steppe bird populations. *Biological Conservation*, 144(11), 2607–2614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2011.07.010>

Kuzemko, A. A., Steinbauer, M. J., Becker, T., Didukh, Y. P., Dolnik, C., Jeschke, M., ... Dengler, J. (2016). Patterns and drivers of phytodiversity in steppe grasslands of Central Podolia (Ukraine). *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(12), 2233–2250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1060-7>

Mathar, W., Kleinebecker, T., & Hölzel, N. (2015). Environmental variation as a key process of co-existence in flood-meadows. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 26(3), 480–491. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvs.12254>

Mathar, W. P., Kämpf, I., Kleinebecker, T., Kuzmin, I., Tolstikov, A., Tupitsin, S., & Hölzel, N. (2015). Floristic diversity of meadow steppes in the Western Siberian Plain: effects of abiotic site conditions, management and landscape structure. *Biodiversity and Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-1023-4>

Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Russian Federation. (2015). 5th National Report Conservation of Biodiversity in the Russian Federation.

Nowak, A., Nowak, S., & Nobis, M. (2011). Distribution patterns, ecological characteristic and conservation status of endemic plants of Tadzhikistan - A global hotspot of diversity. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 19(5), 296–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2011.05.003>

Schustov, M. (2015). ЛИШАЙНИКИ В КРАСНЫХ КНИГАХ УЛЬЯНОВСКОЙ И САМАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТЕЙ (Red List of lichens in the Uliyanovsk and the Samara region).

Sekercioglu, C. H., Anderson, S., Akcay, E., Bilgin, R., Can, O. E., Semiz, G., ... Nüzhet Dalfes, H. (2011).

- Turkey's globally important biodiversity in crisis. *Biological Conservation*, 144(12), 2752–2769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2011.06.025>
- Silva, J., Toland, J., Jones, W., Elridge, J., Thorpe, E., Campbell, M., & O'Hara, E. (2008). LIFE and endangered plants. *Conserving Europe's threatened flora*. European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/99297>
- Socher, S. A., Prati, D., Boch, S., Müller, J., Klaus, V. H., Hölzel, N., & Fischer, M. (2012). Direct and productivity-mediated indirect effects of fertilization, mowing and grazing on grassland species richness. *Journal of Ecology*, 100(6), 1391–1399. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2012.02020.x>
- Vrahnakis, M., Janišová, M., Rūsiņa, S., Török, P., Venn, S., & Dengler, J. (2013). The European Dry Grassland Group (EDGG): stewarding Europe's most diverse habitat type. In *Steppenlebensräume Europas–Gefährdung, Erhaltungsmaßnahmen und Schutz* (pp. 417–434).
- Wesche, K., Ambarl, D., Kamp, J., Torok, P., Treiber, J., & Dengler, J. (2016). The Palaearctic steppe biome: a new synthesis. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(12), 2197–2231. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1214-7>
- Wesche, K., Krause, B., Culmsee, H., & Leuschner, C. (2012). Fifty years of change in Central European grassland vegetation: Large losses in species richness and animal-pollinated plants. *Biological Conservation*, 150(1), 76–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.02.015>

3.4.10 Bryophytes

- Abdul Malak, D., Livingstone S.R., Pollard D., Polidoro B.A., Cuttelod A., Bariche M., Bilecenoglu M., Carpenter K.E., Collette B.B., Francour P., Goren M., Kara M.H., Massuti E., Papaconstantinou c., T. L. (2011). *Overview of the Conservation Status of the Marine Fishes of the Mediterranean Sea*.
- Abell, R., Thieme, M. L., Revenga, C., Bryer, M., Kottelat, M., Bogutskaya, N., ... Petry, P. (2008). Freshwater Ecoregions of the World: A New Map of Biogeographic Units for Freshwater Biodiversity Conservation. *BioScience*, 58(5), 403. <https://doi.org/10.1641/B580507>
- Abellán Sánchez-Fernández, D., P. (2015). A gap analysis comparing the effectiveness of Natura 2000 and national protected area networks in representing European amphibians and reptiles. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 24, 1377–1390.
- Adrianov, A. V., & Tarasov, V. G. (2007). Современные проблемы экологической безопасности морских акваторий Дальнего Востока РФ [Modern problems of ecological safety of the marine areas of the Russian Far East]. In *Динамика морских экосистем и современные проблемы сохранения биологического потенциала морей России [Dynamics of marine ecosystems and modern problems of preservation of biological potential of Russian seas]* (pp. 177–194). Vladivostok: Dalnauka.
- Adrianov, A. V. (2011). Экологическая безопасность дальневосточных морей России [Ecological safety of the Russian Far East seas]. *Вестник Российской Академии Наук [Herald of the Russian Academy of Sciences]*, 81(2), 111–119.
- Airoldi, L., Beck, M. . (2007). Loss status and trends for coastal marine habitats of Europe. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: An Annual Review*, 45, 345–405.
- Aizpuru I. et al. (2000). Lista roja de Flora vascular Española. *Conservacion Vegetal*, 11–38.
- Aladin, N., Chida, T., Cretaux, J.-F., Ermakhanov, Z., Jollibekov, B., Karimov, B., ... Toman, M. (2017).

Current status of Lake Aral – challenges and future opportunities. In *Proceedings of the 16th World Lake Conference “Lake ecosystem health and its resilience: Diversity and risks of Extinction”, November 7-11th, 2016, Bali – Indonesia.*

- Aladin N. V. [Аладин Н.В.], & Plotnikov I.S. [Плотников И.С.]. (2008). Современная фауна остаточных водоемов, образовавшихся на месте бывшего Аральского моря [Modern fauna of residual water bodies formed on the place of the former Aral Sea]. *Труды Зоологического Института РАН [Proceedings of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences]*, 312(1/2), 145–154.
- Alahuhta, J., Heino, J., & Luoto, M. (2011). Climate change and the future distributions of aquatic macrophytes across boreal catchments. *Journal of Biogeography*, 38, 383–393.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2010.02412.x>
- Alatalo, J. M., Jägerbrand, A. K., & Čuchta, P. (2015). Collembola at three alpine subarctic sites resistant to twenty years of experimental warming. *Scientific Reports*, 5, 18161.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/srep18161>
- Alatalo, J. M., Jägerbrand, A. K., & Molau, U. (2015). Testing reliability of short-term responses to predict longer-term responses of bryophytes and lichens to environmental change. *Ecological Indicators*, 58, 77–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.05.050>
- Albert, C. H., Thuiller, W., Lavorel, S., Davies, I. D., & Garbolino, E. (2008). Land-use change and subalpine tree dynamics: Colonization of *Larix decidua* in French subalpine grasslands. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 45(2), 659–669. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2007.01416.x>
- Alcantara, C., Kuemmerle, T., Prishchepov, A. V., & Radeloff, V. C. (2012). Mapping abandoned agriculture with multi-temporal MODIS satellite data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 124, 334–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.05.019>
- Aleksandrova, V. D. [Александрова В. Д.]. (1983). *Растительность полярных пустынь СССР [The vegetation of the Polar Deserts of the USSR]*. Leningrad: Наука [Science].
- Aleynikov, A. A., Aleynikova, A. M., Vocharnikov, M. V., Glazov, P. M., Golovlev, P. P., Golovleva, V. O., ... Хохлов С.Ф. (2014). *Остров Вайгач: природа, климат и человек [Vaigach Island: nature, climate and people]*. (Липка О.Н. [Липка О.Н.], Ed.). Moscow: WWF Russia. Retrieved from <http://www.wwf.ru/resources/publ/book/964>
- Alkemade, R., Ahrens, R., Bakkenes, M., Bakkes, J., van den Berg, M., ten Brink, B., ... Wilting, H. (2010). *Rethinking Global Biodiversity Strategies: Exploring structural changes in production and consumption to reduce biodiversity loss*. The Hague/Bilthoven: Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL).
- Allan, E., Bossdorf, O., Dormann, C. F., Prati, D., Gossner, M. M., Tschardtke, T., ... Fischer, M. (2014). Interannual variation in land-use intensity enhances grassland multidiversity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(1), 308–313.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1312213111>
- Allison, E. H., & Bassett, H. R. (2015). Climate change in the oceans: Human impacts and responses. *Science*, 350(6262), 778–782. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac8721>
- Alomar, C., Deudero, S., Andaloro, F., Castriota, L., Consoli, P., Falautano, M., & Sinopoli, M. (2016). *Caulerpa cylindracea* Sonder invasion modifies trophic niche in infralittoral rocky benthic community. *Marine Environmental Research*, 120, 86–92.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2016.07.010>
- Ameer Abdulla, Marina Gomei, Elodie Maison, and C. P. (2008). *Status of Marine Protected Areas in*

the Mediterranean Sea - A collaborative study by IUCN, WWF and MedPan. IUCN, Malaga and WWF.

- Amstrup, S. C., Marcot, B. G., & Douglas, D. C. (2013). A Bayesian Network Modeling Approach to Forecasting the 21st Century Worldwide Status of Polar Bears (pp. 213–268). American Geophysical Union. <https://doi.org/10.1029/180GM14>
- Ana Nieto, Stuart P.M. Roberts, James Kemp, Pierre Rasmont, M. K., Mariana García Criado, Jacobus C. Biesmeijer, Petr Bogusch, Holger H. Dathe, P. D. la R., Thibaut De Meulemeester, Manuel Dehon, Alexandre Dewulf, F. J. O.-S., Patrick Lhomme, Alain Pauly, Simon G. Potts, Christophe Praz, M. Q., Vladimir G. Radchenko, Erwin Scheuchl, Jan Smit, Jakub Straka, Michael Terzo, B. T., & Miche, Jemma Window, D. M. (2014). *European Red List of Bees*. (Publication Office of the European Union, Ed.). Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2779/77003>
- Ananjeva, N., & Agasyan, A. (2009). *Phrynocephalus horvathi*. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 2009*, e.T164759A5923724. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2009.RLTS.T164759A5923724.en>
- Andersen, J. H., Dahl, K., Goke, C., Hartvig, M., Murray, C., Rindorf, A., ... Korpinen, S. (2014). Integrated assessment of marine biodiversity status using a prototype indicator-based assessment tool. *Frontiers in Marine Science, 1*(55), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00055>
- Andersen, J. H., Halpern, B. S., Korpinen, S., Murray, C., & Reker, J. (2015). Baltic Sea biodiversity status vs. cumulative human pressures. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science, 161*(October 2016), 88–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2015.05.002>
- Anderson Turiyev, B., Bafti, S.S., S. (2009). *Phrynocephalus persicus*. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 2009*, e.T164647A5915480. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2009.RLTS.T164647A5915480.en>
- Andersson, L. I., & Hytteborn, H. (1991). Bryophytes and decaying wood - a comparison between managed and natural forest. *Holarctic Ecology, 14*(1987), 121–130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.1991.tb00642.x>
- Andreev, M. P. (2010). *A checklist of the lichen flora of Russia*. (M. P. Andreev, Ed.). NAUKA.
- Andreev, M. P., & Himelbrant, D. E. (2014). *The lichen flora of Russia: biology, ecology, diversity, distribution and methods on studying lichens*. (M. P. Andreev & D. E. Himelbrant, Eds.). Moscow; Sankt-Petersburg.
- Anker, Y., Rosenthal, E., Shulman, H., & Flexer, A. (2009). Runoff geochemical evolution of the hypersaline Lower Jordan Valley basin. *Israel Journal of Earth Sciences, 58*(1), 41–61. <https://doi.org/10.1560/IJES.58.1.41>
- Antonchikov, A. N. (2005). A review of the conservation status of steppe birds of the northern part of the Eastern Palearctic. In S. M. & Jc. Bota, G., M. B. Morales (Ed.), *Ecology and Conservation of Steppe-land birds* (p. 343). Barcelona: Lynx.
- Antonov, N. P., Klovatch, N. V., Orlov, A. M., Datsky, A. V., Lepskaya, V. A., Kuznetsov, V. V., ... N.A. Evseeva1, D. O. S. (2013). Рыболовство в Дальневосточном рыбохозяйственном бассейне в 2013 г. [Fishing in the Russian Far East fishery basin in 2013]. *Труды ВНИРО [Proceedings of VNIRO], 160*, 133–211.
- Appeltans, W., Ahyong, S. T., Anderson, G., Angel, M. V., Artois, T., Bailly, N., ... Costello, M. J. (2012). The magnitude of global marine species diversity. *Current Biology, 22*(23), 2189–2202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2012.09.036>

- Aptroot, A., & van Herk, C. M. (2007). Further evidence of the effects of global warming on lichens, particularly those with Trentepohlia phycobionts. *Environmental Pollution*, 146(2), 293–298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2006.03.018>
- Aptroot, A., van Herk, C. M., van Dobben, H. F., van den Boom, P. P. G., Brand, a M., & Spier, L. (1998). Rode lijst van Nederlandse korstmossen (Red List of the lichens of the Netherlands). *Buxbaumiella*, 46, 1–101.
- Aragon, G., Martínez, I., Izquierdo, P., Belinchón, R., & Escudero, A. (2010). Effects of forest management on epiphytic lichen diversity in Mediterranean forests. *Applied Vegetation Science*, 13(2), 183–194. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-109X.2009.01060.x>
- Araújo, M. B., Thuiller, W., & Pearson, R. G. (2006). Climate warming and the decline of amphibians and reptiles in Europe. *Journal of Biogeography*, 33(10), 1712–1728. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2006.01482.x>
- Araújo, R. M., Assis, J., Aguillar, R., Airoidi, L., Bárbara, I., Bartsch, I., ... Sousa-Pinto, I. (2016). Status, trends and drivers of kelp forests in Europe: an expert assessment. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(7), 1319–1348. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1141-7>
- Arizaga, J., & Laso, M. (2015). A quantification of illegal hunting of birds in Gipuzkoa (north of Spain). *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 61(5), 795–799. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-015-0940-6>
- Armitage, H. F., Britton, A. J., van der Wal, R., & Woodin, S. J. (2014). The relative importance of nitrogen deposition as a driver of Racomitrium heath species composition and richness across Europe. *Biological Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.01.039>
- Arnolds, E. (1991). Decline of ectomycorrhizal fungi in Europe. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 35(2–3), 209–244. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8809\(91\)90052-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8809(91)90052-Y)
- Arnolds, E. (2001). The future of fungi in Europe: threats, conservation and management. In D. Moore, M. N. Nauta, S. E. Evans, & M. Rotheroe (Eds.), *Fungal conservation, issues and solutions*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. (pp. 64–80). Cambridge (UK): Cambridge University Press.
- Arntzen, J.W., Denoël, M., Miaud, C., Franco Andreone, Vogrin, M., Edgar, P., Crnobrnja Isailovic, J., Ajtic, R., Corti, C. (2009). Proteus anguinus, The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2009: e.T18377A8173419.
- Arrieta, J. M., Arnaud-Haond, S., & Duarte, C. M. (2010). What lies underneath: conserving the oceans' genetic resources. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 107(43), 18318–24. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0911897107>
- Artyukhin, Y. B., Burkanov, V. N., [Артюхин Ю.Б., & Бурканов В.Н.]. (1999). *Морские птицы и млекопитающие Дальнего Востока России: полевой определитель [Marine birds and mammals of the Russian Far East: a field guide]*. Moscow: ACT [AST].
- Assis, J., Araújo, M. B., & Serrão, E. A. (2017). Projected climate changes threaten ancient refugia of kelp forests in the North Atlantic. *Global Change Biology*, in press.
- Assis, J., Coelho, N. C., Lamy, T., Valero, M., Alberto, F., & Serrão, E. A. (2016). Deep reefs are climatic refugia for genetic diversity of marine forests. *Journal of Biogeography*, 43(4), 833–844. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12677>
- Assis, J., Lucas, A. V., Bárbara, I., & Serrão, E. A. (2015). Future climate change is predicted to shift long-term persistence zones in the cold-temperate kelp Laminaria hyperborea. *Marine*

- Environmental Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2015.11.005>
- Aude, E., & Ejrnæs, R. (2005). Bryophyte colonisation in experimental microcosms: The role of nutrients, defoliation and vascular vegetation. *Oikos*, *109*(2), 323–330. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0030-1299.2005.13268.x>
- Augustine, D. J., & McNaughton, S. J. (1998). Ungulate Effects on the Functional Species Composition of Plant Communities: Herbivore Selectivity and Plant Tolerance. *Source: The Journal of Wildlife Management*, *62*(4), 1165–1183. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3801981>
- Aukema, B., Rieger, C., & Rabitsch, W. (2013). *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region, Volume 6: Supplement*. Amsterdam: The Netherlands Entomology Society.
- Aunins, A., & Martin, G. (2014). Biodiversity assessment of MARMONI project areas.
- Babai, D., & Molnár, Z. (2014). Small-scale traditional management of highly species-rich grasslands in the Carpathians. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, *182*, 123–130. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.08.018>
- Badino, G. (2004). Cave temperatures and global climatic change. *International Journal of Speleology*, *33*, 103–113. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1827-806X.33.1.10>
- Bagella, S., Gascón, S., Filigheddu, R., Cogoni, A., & Boix, D. (2016). Mediterranean Temporary Ponds: new challenges from a neglected habitat. *Hydrobiologia*, *782*(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-016-2962-9>
- Bagin, A. M., Melnikov, B. P., & Tambiev, S. B. (2011). *Diagnostic analysis of the environment of the Arctic zone of the Russian Federation (Extended summary)*. (Morgunov B.A., Ed.). Moscow: Scientific World. Retrieved from <http://npa-arctic.ru>
- Bai, Y. G., Broersma, K., Thompson, D., & Ross, T. J. (2004). Landscape-level dynamics of grassland-forest transitions in British Columbia. *Journal of Range Management*, *57*(1), 66–75.
- Bailey, D. ., Collins, M. ., Gordon, J. D. ., Zuur, A. ., & Priede, I. . (2009). Long-term changes in deep-water fish populations in the northeast Atlantic: a deeper reaching effect of fisheries? *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*. Retrieved from <http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/early/2009/03/06/rspb.2009.0098>
- Balata, D., Piazzini, L., & Bulleri, F. (2015). Sediment deposition dampens positive effects of substratum complexity on the diversity of macroalgal assemblages. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, *467*, 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2015.03.005>
- Baldrighi, E., Giovannelli, D., D’Errico, G., Lavaleye, M., & Manini, E. (2017). Exploring the Relationship between Macrofaunal Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning in the Deep Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, *4*, 198. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00198>
- Balian, E. V., Segers, H., Lévêque, C., & Martens, K. (2008). The Freshwater Animal Diversity Assessment: An overview of the results. *Hydrobiologia*, *595*(1), 627–637. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-007-9246-3>
- BalticSTERN. (2013). *State of the Baltic Sea: background paper*.
- Balushkina E.V. [Балушкина Е.В.], Golubkov S.M. [Голубков С.М.], Golubkov M.S. [Голубков М.С.], Litvinchuk L.F. [Литвинчук Л.Ф.], & Shadrin N.V. [Шадрин Н.В.]. (2008). Влияние абиотических и биотических факторов на структурно-функциональную организацию экосистем соленых озер Крыма [Effect of abiotic and biotic factors on the structural and functional organization of the saline lake ecosystems in Crimea]. *Журнал Общей Биологии [Zhurnal Obshchei Biologii]*,

70(6), 504–514.

- Barannik, V., Borysova, O., & Stolberg, F. (2004). The Caspian Sea Region: Environmental Change. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*, 33(1), 45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447-33.1.45>
- Barbet-Massin, M., & Jetz, W. (2014). A 40-year, continent-wide, multispecies assessment of relevant climate predictors for species distribution modelling. *Diversity and Distributions*, 20(11), 1285–1295. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12229>
- Barbet-Massin, M., Thuiller, W., & Jiguet, F. (2012). The fate of European breeding birds under climate, land-use and dispersal scenarios. *Global Change Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02552.x>
- Barceló, C., Ciannelli, L., Olsen, E. M., Johannessen, T., & Knutsen, H. (2016). Eight decades of sampling reveal a contemporary novel fish assemblage in coastal nursery habitats. *Global Change Biology*, 22(3), 1155–1167. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13047>
- Bardat, J., & Aubert, M. (2007). Impact of forest management on the diversity of corticolous bryophyte assemblages in temperate forests. *Biological Conservation*, 139(1), 47–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.06.004>
- Barenboim, G. M., Danilov-Danilyan, V. I., Gelfan, A. N., & Motovilov, Y. G. (2013). On the problems of water quality in Russia and some approaches to their solution, 361. Retrieved from https://istina.msu.ru/media/publications/article/817/fb7/24998371/RedBookr361_end.pdf
- Bastrup-Birk, A., Reker, J., & Zal, N. (2016). *European forest ecosystems: — State and trends. EEA Report n° 5/2016* (Vol. 5). <https://doi.org/10.2800/964893>
- Bates, J., & Farmer, A. (1992). *Bryophytes and lichens in a changing environment*. (A. M. Bates, J. W.; Farmer, Ed.). Clarendon Press.
- Beaugrand, Gregory; Luczak, Christophe; Edwards, M. (2009). Rapid biogeographical plankton shifts in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Global Change Biology*, 15(7), 1790–1803. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01848.x>
- Beaugrand, G. (2004). The North Sea regime shift: Evidence, causes, mechanisms and consequences. *Progress in Oceanography*, 60(2–4), 245–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2004.02.018>
- Beaugrand, G., Edwards, M., Raybaud, V., Goberville, E., & Kirby, R. R. (2015). Future vulnerability of marine biodiversity compared with contemporary and past changes. *Nature Clim. Change*, 5(7), 695–701. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2650><http://www.nature.com/nclimate/journal/v5/n7/abs/nclimate2650.html#supplementary-information>
- Beaugrand, G., Luczak, C., & Edwards, M. (2009). Rapid biogeographical plankton shifts in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Global Change Biology*, 15(7), 1790–1803. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01848.x>
- Beaugrand, G., McQuatters-Gollop, A., Edwards, M., & Goberville, E. (2013). Long-term responses of North Atlantic calcifying plankton to climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(3), 263–267. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1753>
- Beaugrand, G., Reid, P. C., Ibañez, F., Lindley, J. A., & Edwards, M. (2002). Reorganization of North Atlantic Marine Copepod Biodiversity and Climate. *Science*, 296(2002), 1692–1694. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1071329>

- Beebee, T. J. C., & Griffiths, R. A. (2005). The amphibian decline crisis: A watershed for conservation biology? <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.04.009>
- Belan, T. A. (2003). Benthos abundance pattern and species composition in conditions of pollution in Amursky Bay (the Peter the Great Bay, the Sea of Japan). *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 46(9), 1111–1119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X\(03\)00242-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X(03)00242-X)
- Belimov, G. T., & Sedalishchev, V. T. (1980). The Marsh Frog, *Rana ridibunda*. Water Bodies of the City of Yakutsk. *Vestnik Zoologii*, 3, 74–75 (in Russian).
- Benejam, L., Mello, F. T., Meerhoff, M., Loureiro, M., Jeppesen, E., & Brucet, S. (2016). Assessing effects of change in land use on size-related variables of fish in subtropical streams. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 73, 547–556.
- Benito Garzon, M., Sanchez de Dios, R., Sainz Ollero, H., Benito M, G., Sanchez R, D. E. D., & Sainz H, O. (2008). Effects of climate change on the distribution of Iberian tree species. *Applied Vegetation Science*, 11(2), 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.3170/2008-7-18348>
- Benton, T. G., Bryant, D. M., Cole, L., & Crick, H. Q. P. (2002). Linking agricultural practice to insect and bird populations: A historical study over three decades. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 39(4), 673–687. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2664.2002.00745.x>
- Berg, L. S. (1949). *Freshwater fishes of the USSR and adjacent countries, part. 2*. Moskva–Leningrad: Izdatel'stvo Akademii Nauk SSSR.
- Bergamini, A., & Pauli, D. (2001). Effects of increased nutrient supply on bryophytes in montane calcareous fens. *Journal of Bryology*, 23(4), 331–339. <https://doi.org/10.1179/jbr.2001.23.4.331>
- Bergamini, A., Peintinger, M., Fakheran, S., Moradi, H., Schmid, B., & Joshi, J. (2009). Loss of habitat specialists despite conservation management in fen remnants 1995-2006. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, 11(1), 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2008.10.001>
- Bergamini, A., Peintinger, M., Schmid, B., & Urmi, E. (2001). Effects of management and altitude on bryophyte species diversity and composition in montane calcareous fens. *Flora*, 196(3), 180–193. <https://doi.org/0367-2530/01/196/03-180>
- Bergamini, A., Ungricht, S., & Hofmann, H. (2009). An elevational shift of cryophilous bryophytes in the last century - An effect of climate warming? *Diversity and Distributions*, 15(5), 871–879. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2009.00595.x>
- Bertocci, I., Araújo, R., Oliveira, P., & Sousa-Pinto, I. (2015). Potential effects of kelp species on local fisheries. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52, 1216–1226. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12483>
- Bespalova, L. A., & [Беспалова Л. А.]. (2016). *Экологическая диагностика и оценка устойчивости ландшафтной структуры Азовского моря [Environmental diagnosis and assessment of the sustainability of the landscape structure of the Azov Sea]*. Rostov-on-Don: Rostov University.
- Bianchi, C. N., Morri, C., Chiantore, M., Montefalcone, M., Parravicini, V., & Rovere, A. (2012). Mediterranean sea biodiversity between the legacy from the past and a future of change. In Noga Stambler (Ed.), *Life in the Mediterranean Sea: A look at habitat changes* (p. 739). New York: Nova Science Publishers. Retrieved from https://www.novapublishers.com/catalog/product_info.php?products_id=21851
- Biermann, R., & Daniels, F. (1997). Changes in a lichen-rich dry sand grassland vegetation with special reference to lichen synusiae and *Campylopus introflexus*. *Phytocoenologia*, 27(2), 257–273. <https://doi.org/10.1127/phyto/27/1997/257>

- Biesmeijer, J. C., Roberts, S. P. M., Reemer, M., Ohlemüller, R., Edwards, M., Peeters, T., ... Kunin, W. E. (2006). Parallel declines in pollinators and insect-pollinated plants in Britain and the Netherlands. *Science*, *313*(5785), 351–354. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1127863>
- Bilandžija, H., Čuković, T., & Puljas, S. (2014). *Protokol praćenja stanja vrsta Congeria kusceri Bole , 1962 i Congeria jalzici Morton & Bilandžija , 2013 u Republici Hrvatskoj*. Hrvatsko biospeleološko društvo.
- Billetter, R., Liira, J., Bailey, D., Bugter, R., Arens, P., Augenstein, I., ... Edwards, P. J. (2008). Indicators for biodiversity in agricultural landscapes: A pan-European study. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, *45*(1), 141–150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2007.01393.x>
- Bilz, M., Kell, S. P., Maxted, N., & Lansdown, R. V. (2011a). *European Red List of Vascular Plants*. Publications Office of European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/8515>
- Bilz, M., Kell, S. P., Maxted, N., & Lansdown, R. V. (2011b). *European Red List of Vascular Plants*. Publications Office of European Union. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/8515>
- Birchenough, S. N. R., Reiss, H., Degraer, S., Mieszkowska, N., Borja, Á., Buhl-Mortensen, L., ... Wätjen, K. (2015). Climate change and marine benthos: a review of existing research and future directions in the North Atlantic. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, *6*(2), 203–223. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.330>
- BirdLife International. (2008). Palearctic-African migratory birds have suffered substantial declines. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from <http://datazone.birdlife.org/sowb/casestudy/palearctic-african-migratory-birds-have-suffered-substantial-declines>
- BirdLife International. (2015a). *European Red List of Birds*. (Luxemburg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, Ed.). European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2779/975810>
- BirdLife International. (2015b). *European Red List of Birds*. Luxemburg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities. Retrieved from http://datazone.birdlife.org/userfiles/file/Species/erlob/EuropeanRedListOfBirds_June2015.pdf
- BirdLife International. (2016). IUCN Red List for birds. <https://doi.org/http://www.birdlife.org>
- BirdLife International. (2017). *European birds of conservation concern: populations, trends and national responsibilities*. Cambridge, UK.
- Blois, J. L., Zarnetske, P. L., Fitzpatrick, M. C., & Finnegan, S. (2013). Climate Change and the Past, Present, and Future of Biotic Interactions. *Science*, *341*(6145), 499–504. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1237184>
- Blondel, J., Aronson, J., Bodiou, J. Y., & Boeuf, G. (2010). *The Mediterranean region: biological diversity in space and time*. Oxford University Press.
- Bobbink, R., Hicks, K., Galloway, J., Spranger, T., Alkemade, R., Ashmore, M., ... De Vries, W. (2010). Global assessment of nitrogen deposition effects on terrestrial plant diversity: A synthesis. *Ecological Applications*, *20*(1), 30–59. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1140.1>
- Boch, S., Prati, D., Hessenmöller, D., Schulze, E. D., & Fischer, M. (2013). Richness of Lichen Species, Especially of Threatened Ones, Is Promoted by Management Methods Furthering Stand Continuity. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(1), e55461. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0055461>
- Boch, S., Prati, D., Schöning, I., & Fischer, M. (2016). Lichen species richness is highest in non-intensively used grasslands promoting suitable microhabitats and low vascular plant

- competition. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(2), 225–238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-1037-y>
- Bogatov, V. V., & Fedorovskiy, A. S. (2016). Freshwater ecosystems of the southern region of the Russian Far East are undergoing extreme environmental change. *Knowledge and Management of Aquatic Ecosystems*, 417(34). <https://doi.org/10.1051/kmae/2016021>
- Böhm, M., Collen, B., Baillie, J., & Bowles, P. (2013). The conservation status of the world's reptiles. *Biological*. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0006320712003357>
- Bohn, U., Gollub, G., Hettwer, C., Neuhäuslová, Z., Raus, T., Schlüter, H., & Weber, H. (2000). *Karte der natürlichen Vegetation Europas, Maßstab 1: 2 500 000. [Map of the Natural Vegetation of Europe. Scale 1: 2 500 000]. Bundesamt für Naturschutz, Bonn, Germany: Bundesamt für Naturschutz (BfN) / Federal Agency for Nature Conservation.*
- Boix, D., Kneitel, J., Robson, B. J., Duchet, C., Zúñiga, L., Day, J., ... Blaustein, L. (2016). *Invertebrates of Freshwater Temporary Ponds in Mediterranean Climates*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24978-0>
- Boll, T., Levi, E. E., Bezirci, G., Özuluğ, M., Tavşanoğlu, Ü. N., Çakiroğlu, A. İ., ... Beklioğlu, M. (2016). Fish assemblage and diversity in lakes of western and central Turkey: role of geo-climatic and other environmental variables. *Hydrobiologia*, 771(1), 31–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-015-2608-3>
- Bologa, A. S., & Sava, D. (2012). Present state and evolution trends of biodiversity in the Black Sea: decline and restoration. *J. Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 18(2), 144–154. Retrieved from <http://www.blackmedjournal.org/pdf/vol18no2pdf5.pdf>
- Bonnin, I., Bonneuil, C., Goffaux, R., Montalent, P., & Goldringer, I. (2014). Explaining the decrease in the genetic diversity of wheat in France over the 20th century. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 195, 183–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.06.003>
- Boomer, I., Aladin, N., Plotnikov, I., & Whatley, R. (2000). The palaeolimnology of the Aral Sea: a review. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 19(13), 1259–1278. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(00\)00002-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(00)00002-0)
- Bornand, C., Gyax, A., Juillerat, P., Jutzi, M., Möhl, A., Rometsch, S., ... Eggenberg, S. (2016). *Rote Liste Gefäßpflanzen. Gefährdete Arten der Schweiz* (Vol. 1621). Bundesamt für Umwelt, Bern und Info Flora, Genf.
- Boros, E., Ecsedi, Z., & Oláh, J. (2017). *Ecology And Management Of Soda Pans In The Carpathian Basin*.
- Boudouresque, C. F., Bernard, G., Pergent, G., Shili, A., & Verlaque, M. (2009). Regression of Mediterranean seagrasses caused by natural processes and anthropogenic disturbances and stress: A critical review. *Botanica Marina*, 52(5), 395–418. <https://doi.org/10.1515/BOT.2009.057>
- Brasier, C. M., & Buck, K. W. (2001). Rapid evolutionary changes in a globally invading fungal pathogen (Dutch elm disease). *Biological Invasions*, 3(3), 223–233. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015248819864>
- Breckle, S.-W., Wucherer, W., Dimeyeva, L., & Ogar, N. (2012). The Aralkum, a Man-Made Desert on the Desiccated Floor of the Aral Sea (Central Asia): General Introduction and Aims of the Book. In *The Aralkum, a Man-Made Desert on the Desiccated Floor of the Aral Sea (Central Asia)* (Springer, pp. 1–9). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-21117-1_1

- Breeze, T. D., Vaissière, B. E., Bommarco, R., Petanidou, T., Seraphides, N., Kozák, L., ... Potts, S. G. (2014). Agricultural policies exacerbate honeybee pollination service supply-demand mismatches across Europe. *PLoS ONE*, *9*(1), e82996. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0082996>
- Brinkert, A., Hölzel, N., Sidorova, T. V., & Kamp, J. (2015). Spontaneous steppe restoration on abandoned cropland in Kazakhstan: grazing affects successional pathways. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-1020-7>
- Britton, A. J., & Fisher, J. M. (2010). Terricolous alpine lichens are sensitive to both load and concentration of applied nitrogen and have potential as bioindicators of nitrogen deposition. *Environmental Pollution*, *158*(5), 1296–1302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2010.01.015>
- Brochet, A.-L., Van den Bosschen, W., Jbour, S., Ndong'ang'a, P. K., Jones, V. R., Abdou, W. A. L. I., ... Butchart, S. H. M. (2016). Preliminary assessment of the scope and scale of illegal killing and taking of birds in the Mediterranean. *Bird Conservation International*, *26*(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0959270915000416>
- Brodie, J., Williamson, C. J., Smale, D. A., Kamenos, N. A., Mieszkowska, N., Santos, R., ... Hall-Spencer, J. M. (2014). The future of the northeast Atlantic benthic flora in a high CO₂ world. *Ecology and Evolution*, *4*(13), 2787–2798. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.1105>
- Broggi M.F. and al. (1984). *Rote Liste der gefährdeten und seltenen Gefäßspflanzarten des Fürstentums Liechtenstein*. Liechtenstein: Naturkundliche Forschung im Fürstentum.
- Brönmark, C., & Hansson, L.-A. (2002). Environmental issues in lakes and ponds: current state and perspectives. *Environmental Conservation*, *29*(3), 290–307. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892902000218>
- Brooks, T. M., Akçakaya, H. R., Burgess, N. D., Butchart, S. H. M., Hilton-Taylor, C., Hoffmann, M., ... Young, B. E. (2016a). Analysing biodiversity and conservation knowledge products to support regional environmental assessments. *Scientific Data*, *3*, 160007. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.7> <http://www.nature.com/articles/sdata20167#supplementary-information>
- Brooks, T. M., Akçakaya, H. R., Burgess, N. D., Butchart, S. H. M., Hilton-Taylor, C., Hoffmann, M., ... Young, B. E. (2016b). Analysing biodiversity and conservation knowledge products to support regional environmental assessments. *Scientific Data*, *3*, 160007. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.7>
- Brooks, T. M., Akçakaya, H. R., Burgess, N. D., Butchart, S. H. M., Hilton-Taylor, C., Hoffmann, M., ... Young, B. E. (2016c). Analysing biodiversity and conservation knowledge products to support regional environmental assessments. *Scientific Data*, *3*, 160007. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.7>
- Brown, L. E., Hannah, D. M., & Milner, A. M. (2007). Vulnerability of alpine stream biodiversity to shrinking glaciers and snowpacks. *Global Change Biology*, *13*(5), 958–966. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2007.01341.x>
- Brucet, S., Boix, D., Gascón, S., Sala, J., Quintana, X. D., Badosa, A., ... Jeppesen, E. (2009). Species richness of crustacean zooplankton and trophic structure of brackish lagoons in contrasting climate zones: North temperate Denmark and Mediterranean Catalonia (Spain). *Ecography*, *32*(4), 692–702. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2009.05823.x>
- Brucet, S., Boix, D., Nathansen, L. W., Quintana, X. D., Jensen, E., Balayla, D., ... Jeppesen, E. (2012). Effects of temperature, salinity and fish in structuring the macroinvertebrate community in

- shallow lakes: implications for effects of climate change. *PLoS ONE*, (7(2)).
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0030877>
- Brucet, S., Boix, D., Quintana, X. D., Jensen, E., Nathansen, L. W., Trochine, C., ... Jeppesen, E. (2010). Factors influencing zooplankton size structure at contrasting temperatures in coastal shallow lakes: Implications for effects of climate change. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 55(4), 1697–1711. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2010.55.4.1697>
- Brucet, S., Pédrón, S., Mehner, T., Lauridsen, T. L., Argillier, C., Winfield, I. J., ... Jeppesen, E. (2013). Fish diversity in European lakes: Geographical factors dominate over anthropogenic pressures. *Freshwater Biology*, 58(9), 1779–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fwb.12167>
- Bruchmann, I. (2011). *Plant endemism in Europe: spatial distribution and habitat affinities of endemic vascular plants*.
- Brühl, C. A., Schmidt, T., Pieper, S., & Alscher, A. (2013). Terrestrial pesticide exposure of amphibians: An underestimated cause of global decline? *Scientific Reports*, 3(1), 1135. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep01135>
- Brunet, J., Hedwall, P. O., Holmström, E., & Wahlgren, E. (2016). Disturbance of the herbaceous layer after invasion of an eutrophic temperate forest by wild boar. *Nordic Journal of Botany*, 34(1), 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/njb.01010>
- BSC. (2008). *State of the Environment of the Black Sea (2001 - 2006/7)*. (Temel Oguz, Ed.). Istanbul, Turkey: Commission on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (BSC). Retrieved from http://www.blacksea-commission.org/_publ-SOE2009.asp
- Bugmann, H., Gurung, A. B., Ewert, F., Haeberli, W., Guisan, A., Fagre, D., ... GLOCHAMORE participants. (2007). Modeling the Biophysical Impacts of Global Change in Mountain Biosphere Reserves. *Mountain Research and Development*, 27(1), 66–77. [https://doi.org/10.1659/0276-4741\(2007\)27\[66:MTBIOG\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1659/0276-4741(2007)27[66:MTBIOG]2.0.CO;2)
- Buisson, L., Thuiller, W., Lek, S., Lim, P., & Grenouillet, G. (2008). Climate change hastens the turnover of stream fish assemblages. *Global Change Biology*, 14(10), 2232–2248. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2008.01657.x>
- Bulleri, F., & Piazzini, L. (2014). Variations in importance and intensity of competition underpin context dependency in the effects of an invasive seaweed on resident assemblages. *Marine Biology*, 162(2), 485–489. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-014-2563-y>
- Bullock J. (2011). Broad Habitats: Semi-natural Grasslands. In *UK National Ecosystem Assessment: Technical Report*.
- Burdin, A. M., Filatova, O. A., Khoit, E., [Бурдин А. М., Филатова О. А., & Хойт Э.]. (2009). *Морские млекопитающие России [Marine mammals of Russia]*. Киров: Волго-Вятское книжное издательство [Volga-Vyatka book publishing house].
- Burgmer, T., Hillebrand, H., & Pfenninger, M. (2007). Effects of climate-driven temperature changes on the diversity of freshwater macroinvertebrates. *Oecologia*, 151(1), 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-006-0542-9>
- Butzin, M., & Pörtner, H. O. (2016). Thermal growth potential of Atlantic cod by the end of the 21st century. *Global Change Biology*, 22(12), 4162–4168. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13375>
- Cacho, O. J., Spring, D., Pheloung, P., & Hester, S. (2006). Evaluating the feasibility of eradicating an invasion. *Biological Invasions*, 8, 903–917. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-005-4733-9>

- CAFF. (2013). *Arctic Biodiversity Assessment. Status and trends in Arctic biodiversity*. Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF), Arctic Council.
- Cañadas, E. M., Fenu, G., Peñas, J., Lorite, J., Mattana, E., & Bacchetta, G. (2014). Hotspots within hotspots: Endemic plant richness, environmental drivers, and implications for conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 170, 282–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.12.007>
- Cañedo-Argüelles, M., Hawkins, C. P., Kefford, B. J., Schäfer, R. B., Dyack, B. J., Brucet, S., ... Timpano, A. J. (2016). Saving freshwater from salts. *Science*, 351, 8–10.
- Capinha, C., Larson, E. R., Tricarico, E., Olden, J. D., & Gherardi, F. (2013). Effects of climate change, invasive species, and disease on the distribution of native European crayfishes. *Conservation Biology*, 27(4), 731–740. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12043>
- Cardador, L., De Cáceres, M., Bota, G., Giral, D., Casas, F., Arroyo, B., ... Brotons, L. (2014). A resource-based modelling framework to assess habitat suitability for steppe birds in semiarid Mediterranean agricultural systems. *PLoS ONE*, 9(3), e92790. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0092790>
- Cardinale, B. J., Duffy, J. E., Gonzalez, A., Hooper, D. U., Perrings, C., Venail, P., ... Naeem, S. (2012). Biodiversity loss and its impact on humanity. *Nature*, 489(7415), 326–326. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11373>
- Cardinale, M., & Scarcella, G. (2017). Mediterranean Sea: A Failure of the European Fisheries Management System. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4(March). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00072>
- Cardinale, M., & Svedäng, H. (2011). The beauty of simplicity in science: Baltic cod stock improves rapidly in a “cod hostile” ecosystem state. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 425(Ices 2010), 297–301. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps09098>
- Carpenter, S. R., Mooney, H. A., Agard, J., Capistrano, D., DeFries, R. S., Díaz, S., ... Whyte, A. (2009). Science for managing ecosystem services: Beyond the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(5), 1305–1312. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0808772106>
- Carrizo, S. F., Lengyel, S., Kapusi, F., Szabolcs, M., Kasperidus, H. D., Scholz, M., ... Darwall, W. (2017). Critical catchments for freshwater biodiversity conservation in Europe: identification, prioritisation and gap analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, (November), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12842>
- Carstensen, J., Andersen, J. H., Gustafsson, B. G., & Conley, D. J. (2014). Deoxygenation of the Baltic Sea during the last century. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(15), 5628–33. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1323156111>
- Carvalho, L. G., Kunin, W. E., Keil, P., Aguirre-Gutiérrez, J., Ellis, W. N., Fox, R., ... Biesmeijer, J. C. (2013). Species richness declines and biotic homogenisation have slowed down for NW-European pollinators and plants. *Ecology Letters*, 16(7), 870–878. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12121>
- Carvalho, P., Figueira, R., & Jones, M. P. (2008). List of lichens and lichenicolous fungi (fungi). In P. A. V. et al. Borges (Ed.), *A List of the Terrestrial Fungi, Flora and Fauna of Madeira and Salvagens Archipelagos* (pp. 105–122).
- Casale, P., & Margaritoulis, D. (eds.). (2010). *Sea turtles in the Mediterranean: distribution, threats and conservation priorities*. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.

- Casas, F., Mougeot, F., Viñuela, J., & Bretagnolle, V. (2009). Effects of hunting on the behaviour and spatial distribution of farmland birds: Importance of hunting-free refuges in agricultural areas. *Animal Conservation*, 12(4), 346–354. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-1795.2009.00259.x>
- Casazza, G., Giordani, P., Benesperi, R., Foggi, B., Viciani, D., Filigheddu, R., ... Mariotti, M. G. (2014). Climate change hastens the urgency of conservation for range-restricted plant species in the central-northern Mediterranean region. *Biological Conservation*, 179, 129–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.09.015>
- Castro, M. C., Fileman, T. W., & Hall-Spencer, J. M. (2017). Invasive species in the Northeastern and Southwestern Atlantic Ocean: A review. *Mar Pollut Bull.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2016.12.048>
- Cavanagh, R. D., & Gibson, C. (2007). *Overview of the Conservation Status of Cartilaginous Fishes (Chondrichthyans) in the Mediterranean Sea*. (IUCN -The World Conservation Union., IUCN Centre for Mediterranean Cooperation., IUCN Species Survival Commission., & IUCN Shark Specialist Group., Eds.), IUCN. Gland, Switzerland and Malaga, Spain: World Conservation Union (IUCN). <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2007.MRA.3.en>
- Celesti-Grapow, L., Bassi, L., Brundu, G., Camarda, I., Carli, E., D’Auria, G., ... Blasi, C. (2016). Plant invasions on small Mediterranean islands: An overview. *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with All Aspects of Plant Biology*, 150(5), 1119–1133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2016.1218974>
- CEP. (2007). *Caspian Environment Programme Transboundary Diagnostic Analysis Revisit*. Retrieved from <http://www.ais.unwater.org/ais/aismcm/getprojectdoc.php?docid=1058>
- Céréghino, R., Biggs, J., Oertli, B., & Declerck, S. (2008). The ecology of European ponds: Defining the characteristics of a neglected freshwater habitat. *Hydrobiologia*, 597(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-007-9225-8>
- Cerqueira, Y., Navarro, L. M., Maes, J., Marta-Pedroso, C., Honrado, J. P., & Pereira, H. M. (2015). Ecosystem services: the opportunities of rewilding in Europe. In *Rewilding European Landscapes* (pp. 47–64). Springer International Publishing.
- Cervenková, Z., & Münzbergová, Z. (2009). Susceptibility of the landscape of the Giant Mountains, Czech Republic, to invasion by *Rumex alpinus*. In European Conference on Biological Invasions (Ed.), *Biological Invasions: Towards a Synthesis* (Vol. 8, pp. 75–85). Prague. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/11104/0177613>
- Chandra, A., & Idrisova, A. (2011). Convention on Biological Diversity: A review of national challenges and opportunities for implementation. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 20(14), 3295–3316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-0141-x>
- Chapron, G., Kaczensky, P., Linnell, J. D. C., Arx, M. von, Huber, D., Andrén, H., ... Boitani, L. (2014). Recovery of large carnivores in Europe’s modern human-dominated landscapes. *Science*, 346(6216), 1517–1519. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1257553>
- Chebib, A., Badeau, V., Boe, J., Chuine, I., Delire, C., Dufrêne, E., ... Leadley, P. (2012). Climate change impacts on tree ranges: model intercomparison facilitates understanding and quantification of uncertainty. *Ecology Letters*, 15(6), 533–544. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2012.01764.x>
- Cheffings, C., & Farrell, L. (2005). *The Vascular Plant Red Data List for Great Britain*.
- Chemonics International. (2001a). Biodiversity assessment for Central Asia: Regional overview, (June).

- Chemonics International. (2001b). Biodiversity Assessment for Kazakhstan.
- Chemonics International. (2001c). Biodiversity Assessment for Kyrgyzstan.
- Chemonics International. (2001d). Biodiversity Assessment for Tajikistan.
- Chemonics International. (2001e). Biodiversity Assessment for Turkmenistan.
- Chemonics International. (2001f). Biodiversity Assessment for Uzbekistan.
- Cheung, W. W. L., Jones, M. C., Reygondeau, G., Stock, C. A., Lam, V. W. Y., & Frölicher, T. L. (2016). Structural uncertainty in projecting global fisheries catches under climate change. *Ecological Modelling*, 325, 57–66. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2015.12.018>
- Cheung, W. W. L., Lam, V. W. Y., Sarmiento, J. L., Kearney, K., Watson, R., & Pauly, D. (2009). Projecting global marine biodiversity impacts under climate change scenarios. *Fish and Fisheries*, 10(3), 235–251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2008.00315.x>
- Cieslinski, S., Czyżewska, K., & Fabiszewski, J. (2003). Czerwona lista porostów wymarłych i zagrożonych w Polsce [Red List of extinct and threatened lichens in Poland]. *Monographiae Botanicae*, 91.
- Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Program, C. of A. F. and F., & Program for the Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna. (2017). *State of the arctic marine biodiversity report*. Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna International Secretariat. Retrieved from <https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/handle/11374/1945>
- Čížková, H., Květ, J., Comín, F. A., Laiho, R., Pokorný, J., & Pithart, D. (2013). Actual state of European wetlands and their possible future in the context of global climate change. *Aquatic Sciences*, 75(1), 3–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-011-0233-4>
- Clark, M. R., Althaus, F., Schlacher, T. A., Williams, A., Bowden, D. A., & Rowden, A. A. (n.d.). The impacts of deep-sea fisheries on benthic communities: a review, 73(suppl 1), i51–i69. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsv123>
- Claudet, J., Osenberg, C. W., Benedetti-Cecchi, L., Domenici, P., García-Charton, J. A., Pérez-Ruzafa, Á., ... Planes, S. (2008). Marine reserves: Size and age do matter. *Ecology Letters*, 11(5), 481–489. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01166.x>
- Coll, M., Carreras, M., Ciércoles, C., Cornax, M. J., Gorelli, G., Morote, E., & Sáez, R. (2014). Assessing fishing and marine biodiversity changes using fishers' perceptions: The Spanish Mediterranean and Gulf of Cadiz case study. *PLoS ONE*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0085670>
- Coll, M., Piroddi, C., Steenbeek, J., Kaschner, K., Ben Rais Lasram, F., Aguzzi, J., ... Voultsiadou, E. (2010). The biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: estimates, patterns, and threats. *PloS One*, 5(8), e11842. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011842>
- Coll, M., Shannon, L. J., Yemane, D., Link, J. S., Ojaveer, H., Neira, S., ... Shin, Y.-J. (2010). Ranking the ecological relative status of exploited marine ecosystems. *Ices Journal of Marine Science*, 67(4), 769–786. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsp261>
- Colloca, F., Cardinale, M., Maynou, F., Giannoulaki, M., Scarcella, G., Jenko, K., ... Fiorentino, F. (2013). Rebuilding Mediterranean fisheries: A new paradigm for ecological sustainability. *Fish and Fisheries*, 14(1), 89–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2011.00453.x>
- Comin, F., & Alonso, M. (1988). Spanish salt lakes: Their chemistry and biota. *Hydrobiologia*, (158(1)), 237–245.
- Conley, D. J., Carstensen, J., Aigars, J., Axe, P., Bonsdorff, E., Eremina, T., ... Zillén, L. (2011). Hypoxia is

- increasing in the coastal zone of the baltic sea. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 45(16), 6777–6783. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es201212r>
- Conti F. and al. (1992). *Libro rosso delle Plante d'Italia*. Roma: WWF Italia.
- Corbett, K., Societas Europaea Herpetologica. Conservation Committee., & IUCN/SSC European Reptile and Amphibian Specialist Group. (1989). *The Conservation of European reptiles and amphibians*. C. Helm.
- Cordellier, M., Pfenninger, A., Streit, B., & Pfenninger, M. (2012). Assessing the effects of climate change on the distribution of pulmonate freshwater snail biodiversity. *Marine Biology*, 159, 2519–2531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-012-1894-9>
- Cornelissen, J. H. C., Callaghan, T. V., Alatalo, J. M., Michelsen, A., Graglia, E., Hartley, A. E., ... Aerts, R. (2001). Global change and arctic ecosystems: Is lichen decline a function of increases in vascular plant biomass? *Journal of Ecology*, 89(6), 984–994. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2745.2001.00625.x>
- Cornelissen, J. H. C., Lang, S. I., Soudzilovskaia, N. A., & During, H. J. (2007). Comparative cryptogam ecology: A review of bryophyte and lichen traits that drive biogeochemistry. *Annals of Botany*, 99(5), 987–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcm030>
- Costello, M. J., & Ballantine, B. (2015). Biodiversity conservation should focus on no-take Marine Reserves: 94% of Marine Protected Areas allow fishing. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 30(9), 507–509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2015.06.011>
- Costello, M. J., Coll, M., Danovaro, R., Halpin, P., Ojaveer, H., & Miloslavich, P. (2010). A census of marine biodiversity knowledge, resources, and future challenges. *PLoS ONE*, 5(8). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012110>
- Cox, N.A., & Temple, H.J., (2009). *European Red List of Reptiles*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
- Crosa, G., Froebrich, J., Nikolayenko, V., Stefani, F., Galli, P., & Calamari, D. (2006). Spatial and seasonal variations in the water quality of the Amu Darya River (Central Asia). *Water Research*, 40(11), 2237–2245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2006.04.004>
- Culver, D. C., Deharveng, L., Bedos, A., Lewis, J. J., Madden, M., Reddell, J. R., ... White, D. (2006). The mid-latitude biodiversity ridge in terrestrial cave fauna. *Ecography*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2005.0906-7590.04435.x>
- Culver, D. C., & Pipan, T. (2013). Subterranean Ecosystems. *Encyclopedia of Biodiversity*, 7(January 2013), 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-384719-5.00224-0>
- Culver, D. C., & Pipan, T. (2014). *Shallow Subterranean Habitats. Ecology, Evolution, and Conservation*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Culver, D. C., & Sket, B. (2000). Hotspots of subterranean biodiversity in caves and wells. *Journal of Cave and Karst Studies*, 62(1), 11–17.
- Curtis, C. J., Emmett, B. A., Grant, H., Kernan, M., Reynolds, B., & Shilland, E. (2005). Nitrogen saturation in UK moorlands: The critical role of bryophytes and lichens in determining retention of atmospheric N deposition. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 42(3), 507–517. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2005.01029.x>
- Curtis T.G.F. and al. (1988). *The Irish Red Data Book: 1) Vascular plants*. Dublin: Wildlife Service Ireland Stationary Office, Dublin, Ireland.

- Cuttelod, A., Seddon, M., & Neubert, E. (2011a). *European Red List of Non-marine Molluscs*. <https://doi.org/10.2779/84538>
- Cuttelod, A., Seddon, M., & Neubert, E. (2011b). *European Red List of Non-marine Molluscs*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/84538>
- Daan, N., Gislason, H., Pope, J. G., & Rice, J. C. (2005). Changes in the North Sea fish community: Evidence of indirect effects of fishing? *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 62(2), 177–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icesjms.2004.08.020>
- Dahlberg, A., Genney, D. R., & Heilmann-Clausen, J. (2010). Developing a comprehensive strategy for fungal conservation in Europe: current status and future needs. *Fungal Ecology*, 3(2), 50–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2009.10.004>
- Dahlberg, A., & Mueller, G. M. (2011). Applying IUCN red-listing criteria for assessing and reporting on the conservation status of fungal species. *Fungal Ecology*, 4(2), 147–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2010.11.001>
- Dahlgren, S., & Kautsky, L. (2004). Can different vegetative states in shallow coastal bays of the Baltic Sea be linked to internal nutrient levels and external nutrient load? *Hydrobiologia*, 514, 249–258. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:hydr.0000018223.26997.b0>
- Dalpadado, P., Arrigo, K. R., Hjøllø, S. S., Rey, F., Ingvaldsen, R. B., Sperfeld, E., ... Ottersen, G. (2014). Productivity in the Barents Sea - Response to Recent Climate Variability. *PLoS ONE*, 9(5), e95273. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0095273>
- Danielopol, D., Griebler, C., Gunatilaka, A., & Notenboom, J. (2003). Present state and future prospects for groundwater ecosystems. *Environmental Conservation*, 30(2), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892903000>
- Danovaro, R., Company, J. B., Corinaldesi, C., D’Onghia, G., Galil, B., Gambi, C., ... Tselepides, A. (2010). Deep-sea biodiversity in the Mediterranean Sea: The known, the unknown, and the unknowable. *PLoS ONE*, 5(8), e11832. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011832>
- Danovaro, R., Gambi, C., Dell’Anno, A., Corinaldesi, C., Frascchetti, S., Vanreusel, A., ... Gooday, A. J. (2008). Exponential Decline of Deep-Sea Ecosystem Functioning Linked to Benthic Biodiversity Loss. *Current Biology*, 18(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2007.11.056>
- Daufresne, M., Lengfellner, K., & Sommer, U. (2009). Global warming benefits the small. *PNAS*, 106, 12788–12793.
- Davidson, A. D., Detling, J. K., & Brown, J. H. (2012). Ecological roles and conservation challenges of social, burrowing, herbivorous mammals in the world’s grasslands. *Front Ecol Environ*, 10, 477–486. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110054>
- Davydov, E. A., Insarov, G. E., & Sundetpaev, A. K. (2013). Lichen Monitoring In Katon-Karagai National Park, Eastern Kazakhstan, in Context of Climate Change. *Problems of Ecological Monitoring and Ecosystem Modelling*, 25, 428–441.
- De Frenne, P., Rodríguez-Sánchez, F., Coomes, D. A., Baeten, L., Verstraeten, G., Vellend, M., ... Verheyen, K. (2013). Microclimate moderates plant responses to macroclimate warming. *Pnas*, 110(46), 18561–5. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1311190110>
- Deckers, B., Kerselaers, E., Gulinck, H., Muys, B., & Hermy, M. (2005). Long-term spatio-temporal dynamics of a hedgerow network landscape in Flanders, Belgium. *Environmental Conservation*, 32(1), 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0376892905001840>

- Deharveng, L., Stoch, F., Gibert, J., Bedos, A., Galassi, D., Zagamajster, M., ... Marmonier, P. (2009). Groundwater biodiversity in Europe. *Freshwater Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2008.01972.x>
- Dehling, D. M., Hof, C., Brändle, M., & Brandl, R. (2010). Habitat availability does not explain the species richness patterns of European lentic and lotic freshwater animals. *Journal of Biogeography*, 37(10), 1919–1926. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2010.02347.x>
- Delgado, V., & Ederra, A. (2013). Long-term changes (1982–2010) in the bryodiversity of Spanish beech forests assessed by means of Ellenberg indicator values of temperature, nitrogen, light and pH. *Biological Conservation*, 157, 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.06.022>
- Dengler, J., Janišová, M., Török, P., & Wellstein, C. (2014a). Biodiversity of Palaeartic grasslands: A synthesis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 182(182), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.12.015>
- Dengler, J., Janišová, M., Török, P., & Wellstein, C. (2014b). Biodiversity of Palaeartic grasslands: A synthesis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 182, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.12.015>
- Deudero, S., Box, A., Alós, J., Arroyo, N. L., & Marbà, N. (2011). Functional changes due to invasive species: Food web shifts at shallow *Posidonia oceanica* seagrass beds colonized by the alien macroalga *Caulerpa racemosa*. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 93(2), 106–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.03.017>
- Diagelets, E. Y., Knizhnikov, A. Y., Mnatsekanov, R. A., Pegova, O. V., [Дягилец Е.Ю., Книжников А.Ю., ... Пегова О.В.]. (2014). *Люди, нефть, птицы. Рекомендации для практических мероприятий [People, oil, birds. Recommendations for practical activities]*. Moscow: WWF Russia.
- Díaz, S., Lavorel, S., McIntyre, S., Falczuk, V., Casanoves, F., Milchunas, D. G., ... Campbell, B. D. (2007). Plant trait responses to grazing - A global synthesis. *Global Change Biology*, 13(2), 313–341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01288.x>
- Dirnböck, T., Dullinger, S., Grabherr, G., & Dirnb, T. (2003). A regional impact assessment of climate and land-use change on alpine vegetation. *Journal of Biogeography*, 101(3), 1–417. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2699.2003.00839.x>
- Dirnböck, T., Essl, F., & Rabitsch, W. (2011). Disproportional risk for habitat loss of high-altitude endemic species under climate change. *Global Change Biology*, 17(2), 990–996. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02266.x>
- Dobrovolskii A.D. [Добровольский А.Д.], & Zalogin B.S. [Залогин Б.С.]. (1982). *Моря СССР [The Seas of the USSR]*. Moscow: МГУ [Moscow State University].
- Doğan, P. (n.d.). *Global Climate Change and Its Effects in Turkey*.
- Dolev Pervolutzki, A., A. (2004). *Endangered species in Israel. Red list of threatened animals. Vertebrates*. Jerusalem: The Nature Reserves and Park Authority and the Society for Conservation of Nature.
- Dominoni, D. M., & Partecke, J. (2015). Does light pollution alter daylength ? A test using light loggers on free-ranging European blackbirds (*Turdus merula*). *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences*, 370(MAY), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2014.0118>
- Domisch, S., Araújo, M. B., Bonada, N., Pauls, S. U., Jähnig, S. C., & Haase, P. (2013). Modelling

- distribution in European stream macroinvertebrates under future climates. *Global Change Biology*, 19(3), 752–762. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12107>
- Domisch, S., Jähnig, S. C. , & Haase, P. (2011). Climate-change winners and losers: stream macroinvertebrates of a submontane region in Central Europe. *Freshwater Biology*, 56(10), 2009–2020. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2011.02631.x>
- Donald, P. F., Green, R. E., & Heath, M. F. (2001). Agricultural intensification and the collapse of Europe's farmland bird populations. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 268(1462), 25–29. Retrieved from <http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/268/1462/25.abstract>
- Donald, P. F., Sanderson, F. J., Burfield, I. J., & van Bommel, F. P. J. (2006). Further evidence of continent-wide impacts of agricultural intensification on European farmland birds, 1990–2000. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 116(3–4), 189–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2006.02.007>
- Doxa, A., Paracchini, M. L., Pointereau, P., Devictor, V., & Jiguet, F. (2012). Preventing biotic homogenization of farmland bird communities: The role of High Nature Value farmland. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 148(May 2017), 83–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.11.020>
- Drobyshev, I., Niklasson, M., & Linderholm, H. W. (2012). Forest fire activity in Sweden: Climatic controls and geographical patterns in 20th century. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 154–155, 174–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2011.11.002>
- Dudgeon, D., Arthington, A. H., Gessner, M. O., Kawabata, Z.-I., Knowler, D. J., Lévêque, C., ... Sullivan, C. A. (2006). Freshwater biodiversity: importance, threats, status and conservation challenges. *Biological Reviews of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 81(2), 163–82. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1464793105006950>
- Duffus, A. L. J., & Cunningham, A. A. (2010). Major disease threats to European amphibians. *Herpetological Journal*, 20, 117–1. Retrieved from [http://faculty.gordonstate.edu/aduffus/duffus and cunningham 2010.pdf](http://faculty.gordonstate.edu/aduffus/duffus%20and%20cunningham%202010.pdf)
- Dullinger, S., Gattringer, A., Thuiller, W., Moser, D., Zimmermann, N. E., Guisan, A., ... Hülber, K. (2012). Extinction debt of high-mountain plants under twenty-first-century climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 2(8), 619–622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1514>
- Dulvy, N. K., Rogers, S. I., Jennings, S., Stelzenmüller, V., Dye, S. R., & Skjoldal, H. R. (2008). Climate change and deepening of the North Sea fish assemblage: A biotic indicator of warming seas. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 45(4), 1029–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2008.01488.x>
- Dumont, H., Mamaev, V. O., & Zaitsev, Y. P. (1999). *Black Sea Red Data Book*. New York NY, USA.
- Dumont, H. J. (1998). The Caspian Lake: History, biota, structure, and function. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 43(1), 44–52. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.1998.43.1.0044>
- Dumont, H., Mamaev, V. O., & Zaitsev, Y. P. (1999). *Black Sea Red Data Book*. New York: UNOPS.
- Duprè, C., Stevens, C. J., Ranke, T., Bleeker, A., Peppler-Lisbach, C., Gowing, D. J. G., ... Diekmann, M. (2010). Changes in species richness and composition in European acidic grasslands over the past 70 years: The contribution of cumulative atmospheric nitrogen deposition. *Global Change Biology*, 16(1), 344–357. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01982.x>
- Durance, I., & Ormerod, S. J. (2009). Trends in water quality and discharge confound long-term

- warming effects on river macroinvertebrates. *Freshwater Biology*, 54(2), 388–405.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2008.02112.x>
- Dymytrova, L., Nadyeina, O., Hobi, M. L., & Scheidegger, C. (2014). Topographic and forest-stand variables determining epiphytic lichen diversity in the primeval beech forest in the Ukrainian Carpathians. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 23(6), 1367–1394. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-014-0670-1>
- EC. (2014). EC, 2014, Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species — European Environment Agency. Retrieved September 20, 2017, from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/ec-2014-regulation-eu-no>
- Edda Johannesen, Herdis Langøy Mørk, Knut Korsbrekke, R. W., & Elena Eriksen, Maria Fossheim, Thomas de Lange Wenneck, Andrey Dolgov, Tatiana Prokhorova, D. P. (2017). *Arctic fishes in the Barents Sea 2004–2015: Changes in abundance and distribution*.
- Edgar, G. J., Stuart-Smith, R. D., Willis, T. J., Kininmonth, S., Baker, S. C., Banks, S., ... Thomson, R. J. (2014). Global conservation outcomes depend on marine protected areas with five key features. *Nature*, 506(7487), 216–220. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13022>
- Edwards, M., & Richardson, A. J. (2004). Impact of climate change on marine pelagic phenology and trophic mismatch. *Nature*, 430(7002), 881–884. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature02808>
- Edwards, R., Soos, J., & Ritcey, R. (1960). Quantitative observations on epidendric lichens used as food by caribou. *Ecology*, 41(3), 425–431. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1933317>
- EEA. (2002). *Europe's biodiversity - biogeographical regions and seas*. EEA Report No 1/2002. Retrieved from http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/report_2002_0524_154909
- EEA. (2010). *Assessing biodiversity in Europe — the 2010 report*. Europe. <https://doi.org/10.2800/42824>
- EEA. (2012). *European waters — current status and future challenges: Synthesis*, EEA Report No 9/2012.
- EEA. (2015). *The State of Nature in the European Union*. [https://doi.org/COM\(2015\)219 final](https://doi.org/COM(2015)219final)
- Eeva, T., Belskii, E., Gilyazov, A. S., & Kozlov, M. V. (2012). Pollution impacts on bird population density and species diversity at four non-ferrous smelter sites. *Biological Conservation*, 150(1), 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.03.004>
- Eeva, T., Belskii, E., & Kuranov, B. (2006). Environmental pollution affects genetic diversity in wild bird populations. *Mutation Research*, 608, 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrgentox.2006.04.021>
- Elkin, C., Gutiérrez, A. G., Leuzinger, S., Manusch, C., Temperli, C., Rasche, L., & Bugmann, H. (2013). A 2 °C warmer world is not safe for ecosystem services in the European Alps. *Global Change Biology*, 19(6), 1827–1840. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12156>
- Ellingsen, I. H., Dalpadado, P., Slagstad, D., & Loeng, H. (2008). Impact of climatic change on the biological production in the Barents Sea. *Climatic Change*, 87(1–2), 155–175. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-007-9369-6>
- Ellis, A., Jackson, M. C., Jennings, I., England, J., & Phillips, R. (2012). Present distribution and future spread of louisiana red swamp crayfish *Procambarus clarkii* (Crustacea, Decapoda, Astacida, Cambaridae) in Britain: Implications for conservation of native species and habitats. *Knowledge and Management of Aquatic Ecosystems*, 406, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1051/kmae/2012022>

- Ellis, C. J. (2012). Lichen epiphyte diversity: A species, community and trait-based review. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, 14(2), 131–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2011.10.001>
- Ellis, C. J. (2015). Ancient woodland indicators signal the climate change risk for dispersal-limited species. *Ecological Indicators*, 53, 106–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.01.028>
- Ellis, C. J., Coppins, B. J., & Hollingsworth, P. M. (2012). Lichens under threat from ash dieback. *Nature*, 491(29), 672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.10.042>
- Ellis, C. J., Eaton, S., Theodoropoulos, M., Coppins, B. J., Seaward, M. R. D., & Simkin, J. (2014). Response of epiphytic lichens to 21st century climate change and tree disease scenarios. *Biological Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.09.046>
- Elmendorf, S. C., Henry, G. H. R., Hollister, R. D., Björk, R. G., Bjorkman, A. D., Callaghan, T. V., ... Wookey, P. A. (2012). Global assessment of experimental climate warming on tundra vegetation: Heterogeneity over space and time. *Ecology Letters*, 15(2), 164–175. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01716.x>
- Emanuelsson, U. (2010). The rural landscapes of Europe. How man has shaped European nature. *Soc. Ekol. Zagreb*, 19(1), 93–96.
- Emmrich, M., Pédrón, S., Brucet, S., Winfield, I. J., Jeppesen, E., Volta, P., ... Mehner, T. (2014). Geographical patterns in the body-size structure of European lake fish assemblages along abiotic and biotic gradients. *Journal of Biogeography*, 41(12), 2221–2233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12366>
- Engler, R., Randin, C. F., Thuiller, W., Dullinger, S., Zimmermann, N. E., Araújo, M. B., ... Guisan, A. (2011a). 21st century climate change threatens mountain flora unequally across Europe. *Global Change Biology*, 17(7), 2330–2341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02393.x>
- Engler, R., Randin, C. F., Thuiller, W., Dullinger, S., Zimmermann, N. E., Araújo, M. B., ... Guisan, A. (2011b). 21st century climate change threatens mountain flora unequally across Europe. *Global Change Biology*, 17(7), 2330–2341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02393.x>
- Eremeev, V. N., Gaevskaya, A. V., Shulman, G. E., Zagorodnyaya, J. A., [Еремеев В.Н., Гаевская А.В., ... Загородняя Ю.А.] (Eds.). (2011). *Промысловые биоресурсы Черного и Азовского морей [Biological resources of the Black Sea and Sea of Azov]*. Sevastopol: ЭКОСИ-Гидрофизика [EKOSI-Gidrofizika].
- Erkakan, F., & Ozdemir, F. (2012). The first new cave fish species, *Cobitis damlae* (Teleostei: Cobitidae) from Turkey, 40(3), 219–225.
- Ermakhanov, Z. K., Plotnikov, I. S., Aladin, N. V., & Micklin, P. (2012). Changes in the Aral Sea ichthyofauna and fishery during the period of ecological crisis. *Lakes and Reservoirs: Research and Management*, 17(1), 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-1770.2012.00492.x>
- Essl, F., & Lambdon, P. W. (2009). Alien Bryophytes and Lichens of Europe. In *Handbook of Alien Species in Europe* (pp. 29–41). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8280-1_3
- Essl, F., Moser, D., Dullinger, S., Mang, T., & Hulme, P. E. (2010). Selection for commercial forestry determines global patterns of alien conifer invasions. *Diversity and Distributions*, 16(6), 911–921. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00705.x>
- Essl, F., Steinbauer, K., Dullinger, S., Mang, T., & Moser, D. (2013). Telling a different story: A global assessment of bryophyte invasions. *Biological Invasions*, 15(9), 1933–1946.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-013-0422-2>

Estrada, A., Morales-Castilla, I., Caplat, P., & Early, R. (2016). Usefulness of Species Traits in Predicting Range Shifts. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 31(3), 190–203.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2015.12.014>

EU. (2009). European Redlist - Environment - European Commission. Retrieved September 20, 2017, from

<http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/conservation/species/redlist/amphibians/status.htm>

Euro+Med. (2017). Euro+Med PlantBase - the information resource for Euro-Mediterranean plant diversity. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from <http://www.emplantbase.org/home.html>

European Commission. (2007). Commission Regulation (EC) No 708/2007 concerning use of alien and locally absent species in aquaculture. *Official Journal of the European Union* (28.6.2007), L 168/1.

European Environment Agency. (2015a). *Annexes A–F to: State of nature in the EU - Results from reporting under the nature directives 2007-2012*. EEA Technical Report (Vol. 2).

<https://doi.org/10.2800/603862>

European Environment Agency. (2015b). *Spatial analysis of marine protected area networks in Europe's seas*. European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2015c). *The European Environment - State and Outlook 2015*. Copenhagen, Denmark: European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2016). *European forest ecosystems - state and trends*.

<https://doi.org/doi:10.2800/964893>

European Environment Agency (EEA). (2014). *State of nature in the EU*.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13398-014-0173-7.2>

European Environmental Agency, E. (2015a). *SOER. The European environment — state and outlook 2015. A comprehensive assessment of the European environment's state, trends and prospects, in a global context*. Copenhagen.

European Environmental Agency, E. (2015b). *State of Europe's seas*.

European Reptile & Amphibian Specialist Group. (1996). *Trionyx triunguis* (Mediterranean subpopulation). *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 1996*, e.T22200A9364253.

<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.1996.RLTS.T22200A9364253.en>

Ewald, J., Hennekens, S. M., Conrad, S., Wohlgemuth, T., Jansen, F., Jenssen, M., ... Godefroid, S. (2013). Spatial and temporal patterns of Ellenberg values for nutrients in forests of Germany and adjacent regions - a survey based on phytosociological databases. *Tuexenia*.

Faber-Langendoen, D., & Josse, C. (2010). *World Grasslands and Biodiversity Patterns A Report to IUCN Ecosystem Management Programme*. @NatureService. Arlington, VA.

Falasco, E., Ector, L., Isaia, M., Wetzell, C. E., Hoffmann, L., & Bona, F. (2014). Diatom flora in subterranean ecosystems: A review. *International Journal of Speleology*, 43(3), 231–251.

<https://doi.org/10.5038/1827-806X.43.3.1>

FAO. (2007). *The first report on the state of world's - Animal Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. Agriculture*. Rome. Retrieved from

<http://www.fao.org/docrep/010/a1250e/a1250e00.htm>

- FAO. (2010). *The Second Report on The State of The World's Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture*. Rome.
- FAO. (2011). *Review of the state of world marine fishery resources. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper* (Vol. 569).
- FAO. (2015). *The Second Report on the State of the World's Animal Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture*, edited by B.D. Scherf & D. Pilling.
- Fedorciak, M., Rudenko, S., Iaroshynska, O., & Zhukovets, E. (2012). Spiders (Aranaea) of Chernivtsi City(Ukraine). *Arachnologische Mitteilungen*, 37–50.
- Feistel, R., Nausch, G., & Wasmund, N. (2008). *State and evolution of the Baltic Sea, 1952-2005: a detailed 50-year survey of meteorology and climate, physics, chemistry, biology, and marine environment*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Feliciísimo, Á. M., Muñoz, J., Villalba, C. J., & Mateo, R. G. (2011). *Impactos, vulnerabilidad y adaptación al Cambio Climático de la biodiversidad española. 2. Flora y vegetación*. Madrid.
- Felline, S., Mollo, E., Ferramosca, A., Zara, V., Regoli, F., Gorbi, S., & Terlizzi, A. (2014). Can a marine pest reduce the nutritional value of Mediterranean fish flesh? *Marine Biology*, 161(6), 1275–1283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-014-2417-7>
- Felton, A., Lindbladh, M., Brunet, J., & Fritz, Ö. (2010). Replacing coniferous monocultures with mixed-species production stands: An assessment of the potential benefits for forest biodiversity in northern Europe. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 260(6), 939–947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2010.06.011>
- Fernandes, P. G., Ralph, G. M., Nieto, A., García Criado, M., Vasilakopoulos, P., Maravelias, C. D., ... Carpenter, K. E. (2017a). Coherent assessments of Europe's marine fishes show regional divergence and megafauna loss. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1(May), 170. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0170>
- Fernandes, P. G., Ralph, G. M., Nieto, A., García Criado, M., Vasilakopoulos, P., Maravelias, C. D., ... Carpenter, K. E. (2017b). Coherent assessments of Europe's marine fishes show regional divergence and megafauna loss. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0170>
- Feurerer, T. (2013). Checklists of Lichens - A Global Information System for the Biodiversity of Lichens. Retrieved December 8, 2016, from http://www.lichens.uni-hamburg.de/lichens/portalpages/portalpage_checklists_switch.htm
- Field, C. D., Dise, N. B., Payne, R. J., Britton, A. J., Emmett, B. A., Helliwell, R. C., ... Caporn, S. J. M. (2014). The Role of Nitrogen Deposition in Widespread Plant Community Change Across Semi-natural Habitats. *Ecosystems*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-014-9765-5>
- Fijen, T. P. M., Kamp, J., Lameris, T. K., Pulikova, G., Urazaliev, R., Kleijn, D., & Donald, P. F. (2015). Functions of extensive animal dung pavements around the nests of the Black Lark (*Melanocorypha yeltoniensis*). *Auk*, (September), 878–892. <https://doi.org/10.1642/AUK-15-38.1>
- Filipov, D. M., & [Филиппов Д.М.]. (1968). *Циркуляция и структура вод Черного моря [Circulation and structure of waters of the Black Sea]*. Moscow: Наука [Science].
- Finstad, A. G., & Hein, C. L. (2012). Migrate or stay: terrestrial primary productivity and climate drive anadromy in Arctic char. *Global Change Biology*, 18(8), 2487–2497. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2012.02717.x>

- Fletcher, D. H., Gillingham, P. K., Britton, J. R., Blanchet, S., Gozlan, R. E., Stohlgren, T. J., ... Maclsaac, H. J. (2016). Predicting global invasion risks: a management tool to prevent future introductions. *Scientific Reports*, 6(December 2015), 26316. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep26316>
- Fochetti, R., & Tierno De Figueroa, J. M. (2008). Global diversity of stoneflies (Plecoptera; Insecta) in freshwater. *Hydrobiologia*, 595(1), 365–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-007-9031-3>
- Fominykh, A. S., & Lyapkov, S. M. (2011). The formation of new characteristics in life cycle of the marsh frog (*Rana ridibunda*) in thermal pond condition. *Zhurnal Obshchei Biologii*, 72(6), 403–421. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079086412030036>
- Ford, D., & Williams, P. (2007). *Karst Hydrogeology and Geomorphology*. *Karst Hydrogeology and Geomorphology*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118684986>
- Forest Europe. (2015). *State of Europe's Forests 2015*. Madrid.
- Fossheim, M., Primicerio, R., Johannesen, E., Ingvaldsen, R. B., Aschan, M. M., & Dolgov, A. V. (2015a). Recent warming leads to a rapid borealization of fish communities in the Arctic. *Nature Clim. Change*, 5(7), 673–677. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2647><http://www.nature.com/nclimate/journal/v5/n7/abs/nclimate2647.html#supplementary-information>
- Fossheim, M., Primicerio, R., Johannesen, E., Ingvaldsen, R. B., Aschan, M. M., & Dolgov, A. V. (2015b). Recent warming leads to a rapid borealization of fish communities in the Arctic. <https://doi.org/10.1038/NCLIMATE2647>
- Fraiture, A., & Otto, P. (2015). Distribution, ecology and status of 51 macromycetes in Europe: Results of the ECCF Mapping Programme. *Scripta Botanica Belgica*, 53, 1–246.
- Frederiksen, M. (2010). Appendix 1: seabirds in the North East Atlantic. A review of status, trends and anthropogenic impact. *TemaNord*, 587, 47–122.
- Frederiksen, M., Anker-Nilssen, T., Beaugrand, G., & Wanless, S. (2013). Climate, copepods and seabirds in the boreal Northeast Atlantic - current state and future outlook. *Global Change Biology*, 19(2), 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12072>
- Frederiksen, M., Harris, M. P., Daunt, F., Rothery, P., & Wanless, S. (2004). Scale-dependent climate signals drive breeding phenology of three seabird species. *Global Change Biology*, 10(7), 1214–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1529-8817.2003.00794.x>
- Frederiksen, M., Krause-Jensen, D., Holmer, M., & Laursen, J. S. (2004). Long-term changes in area distribution of eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) in Danish coastal waters. *Aquatic Botany*, 78(2), 167–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquabot.2003.10.002>
- Freyhof, J. (2011). *European red list of freshwater fishes*. Retrieved from <http://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&btnG=Search&q=intitle:European+Red+List+of+Freshwater+Fishes#0%5Cnhttp://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&btnG=Search&q=intitle:European+red+list+of+freshwater+fishes%230>
- Freyhof, J., & Brooks, E. (2011). *European Red List of Freshwater Fishes*. (I. U. for C. of N. and N. R. IUCN, Ed.). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/85903>
- Friend, A. D., Lucht, W., Rademacher, T. T., Keribin, R., Betts, R., Cadule, P., ... Woodward, F. I. (2014). Carbon residence time dominates uncertainty in terrestrial vegetation responses to future climate and atmospheric CO₂. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(9), 3280–5. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1222477110>

- Friocourt, Y. F., Skogen, M., Stolte, W., & Albretsen, J. (2012). Marine downscaling of a future climate scenario in the North Sea and possible effects on dinoflagellate harmful algal blooms. *Food Additives and Contaminants - Part A Chemistry, Analysis, Control, Exposure and Risk Assessment*, 29(10), 1630–1646. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2012.714079>
- Fuchs, R., Herold, M., Verburg, P. H., Clevers, J. G. P. W., & Eberle, J. (2015). Gross changes in reconstructions of historic land cover/use for Europe between 1900 and 2010. *Global Change Biology*, 21(1), 299–313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12714>
- Fujikura, K., Lindsay, D., Kitazato, H., Nishida, S., & Shirayama, Y. (2010). Marine Biodiversity in Japanese Waters. *PLoS ONE*, 5(8), e11836. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011836>
- Fung, T., Farnsworth, K., Shephard, S., Reid, D., & Rossberg, A. (2013). Why the size structure of marine communities can require decades to recover from fishing. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 484, 155–171. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10305>
- Gage, J. D., & Tyler, P. A. (1991). *Deep-sea biology: a natural history of organisms at the deep-sea floor*. Cambridge University Press.
- Galil, B., Marchini, A., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., & Ojaveer, H. (2017). The enlargement of the Suez Canal—Erythraean introductions and management challenges. *Management of Biological Invasions*, 8(2), 141–152. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2017.8.2.02>
- Galil, B. S. (2007). Loss or gain? Invasive aliens and biodiversity in the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 55(7–9), 314–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2006.11.008>
- Galil, B. S., Boero, F., Campbell, M. L., Carlton, J. T., Cook, E., Frascchetti, S., ... Ruiz, G. M. (2015). “Double trouble”: the expansion of the Suez Canal and marine bioinvasions in the Mediterranean Sea. *Biological Invasions*, 17(4), 973–976. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-014-0778-y>
- Galil, B. S., Marchini, A., & Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A. (2015). East is east and West is west? Management of marine bioinvasions in the Mediterranean Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2015.12.021>
- Galil, B. S., Marchini, A., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Minchin, D., Narščius, A., Ojaveer, H., & Olenin, S. (2014). International arrivals: widespread bioinvasions in European Seas. *Ethology Ecology & Evolution*, 26(2–3), 152–171. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03949370.2014.897651>
- Gamero, A. (2016). Tracking progress towards EU biodiversity strategy targets: EU policy effects in preserving its common farmland birds. *Conservation Letters*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12292>.This
- García-Charton, J. A., Pérez-Ruzafa, A., Marcos, C., Claudet, J., Badalamenti, F., Benedetti-Cecchi, L., ... Planes, S. (2008). Effectiveness of European Atlanto-Mediterranean MPAs: Do they accomplish the expected effects on populations, communities and ecosystems? *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 16(4), 193–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2008.09.007>
- García-Valdés, R., Svenning, J.-C., Zavala, M. a., Purves, D. W., & Araújo, M. B. (2015). Evaluating the combined effects of climate and land-use change on tree species distributions. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52, 902–912. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12453>
- García Molinos, J., Halpern, B. S., Schoeman, D. S., Brown, C. J., Kiessling, W., Moore, P. J., ... Burrows, M. T. (2016). Climate velocity and the future global redistribution of marine biodiversity. *Nature Climate Change*, 6(1), 83–88. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2769>
- Gauthier, G., Bêty, J., Cadieux, M.-C., Legagneux, P., Doiron, M., Chevallier, C., ... Berteaux, D. (2013).

- Long-term monitoring at multiple trophic levels suggests heterogeneity in responses to climate change in the Canadian Arctic tundra. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences*, 368(1624), 20120482. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2012.0482>
- Gehrig-Fasel, J., Guisan, A., & Zimmermann, N. E. (2007). Tree line shifts in the Swiss Alps: Climate change or land abandonment? *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 18(4), 571–582.
- Gennaro, P., Piazzini, L., Persia, E., & Porrello, S. (2015). Nutrient exploitation and competition strategies of the invasive seaweed *Caulerpa cylindracea*. *European Journal of Phycology*, 50(4), 384–394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09670262.2015.1055591>
- Georgiadi, A. G., Koronkevich, N. I., Milyukova, I. P., & Barabanova, E. A. (2014). The ensemble scenarios projecting runoff changes in large Russian river basins in the 21st century, 364. <https://doi.org/10.5194/piahs-364-210-2014>
- Georgievsky, M. (2016). Water resources of the Russian rivers and their changes, 374755194(10), 75–77. <https://doi.org/10.5194/piahs-374-75-2016>
- Geptner, V. G., Chapskiy, K. K., Arseniev, V. A., Sokolov, V. E., [Гептнер В.Г., Чапский К.К., ... Соколов В.Е.]. (1976). *Млекопитающие Советского Союза. Том 2/3. Ластоногие и зубатые киты [Mammals Of The Soviet Union. Volume 2/3. Pinnipeds and toothed whales]*.
- Gerson, U., & Seaward, M. R. D. (1977). Lichen-invertebrate associations. In M. R. D. Seaward (Ed.), *Lichen ecology* (pp. 69–119). London: Academic Press.
- Ghorbani, A., Gravendeel, B., Naghibi, F., & de Boer, H. (2014). Wild orchid tuber collection in Iran: a wake-up call for conservation. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 23(11), 2749–2760. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-014-0746-y>
- Giakoumi, S. (2014). Distribution patterns of the invasive herbivore *Siganus luridus* (Rüppell, 1829) and its relation to native benthic communities in the central Aegean Sea, Northeastern Mediterranean. *Marine Ecology*, 35(1), 96–105. <https://doi.org/10.1111/maec.12059>
- Giakoumi, S., Scianna, C., Plass-Johnson, J., Micheli, F., Grorud-Colvert, K., Thiriet, P., ... Guidetti, P. (2017). Ecological effects of full and partial protection in the crowded Mediterranean Sea: a regional meta-analysis. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 8940. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-08850-w>
- Gibert, J., & Culver, D. C. (2005). Diversity patterns in Europe. In D. C. Culver & W. B. White (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of caves* (pp. 196–201). Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier Press.
- Gibert, J., & Deharveng, L. (2002). Subterranean Ecosystems: A Truncated Functional Biodiversity. *BioScience*, 52(6), 473–481. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2002\)052\[0473:SEATFB\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2002)052[0473:SEATFB]2.0.CO;2)
- Gil-Tena, A., Saura, S., & Brotons, L. (2007). Effects of forest composition and structure on bird species richness in a Mediterranean context: Implications for forest ecosystem management. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 242(2–3), 470–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2007.01.080>
- Gilbert, O. L. (1989). *The Ecology of Urban Habitats*. (O. Gilbert, Ed.). London: Chapman and Hall.
- Gilbert, O. L. (1992). Lichen reinvasion with declining air pollution. In J. Bates & A. Farmer (Eds.), *Bryophytes and lichens in a changing environment* (pp. 159–177). Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Gladyshev, M. I., Sushchik, N. N., Anishchenko, O. V., Makhutova, O. N., Kolmakov, V. I., Kalachova, G. S., ... Dubovskaya, O. P. (2011). Efficiency of transfer of essential polyunsaturated fatty acids

- versus organic carbon from producers to consumers in a eutrophic reservoir. *Oecologia*, 165, 521–531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-010-1843-6>
- Glantz, M. H., & Zonn, I. S. (1997). *Scientific, environmental, and political issues in the circum-Caspian region*. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Glazovsky N.F. [Глазовский Н.Ф.]. (1990). *Аральский кризис: Причины возникновения и пути выхода [The Aral crisis: causes and ways out]*. Moscow: Наука [Science].
- Glover, A. G., Gooday, A. J., Bailey, D. M., Billett, D. S. M., Chevaldonné, P., Colaço, A., ... Vanreusel, A. (2010). Temporal Change in Deep-Sea Benthic Ecosystems. A Review of the Evidence From Recent Time-Series Studies. *Advances in Marine Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-381015-1.00001-0>
- Godbold, J. A., Bailey, D. M., Collins, M. A., Gordon, J. D. M., Spallek, W. A., & Priede, I. G. (2013). Putative fishery-induced changes in biomass and population size structures of demersal deep-sea fishes in ICES Sub-area VII, Northeast Atlantic Ocean. *Biogeosciences*, 10(1), 529–539. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-10-529-2013>
- Gomoiu, M.-T., Begun, T., Caraus, I., Muresan, M., Oaie, G., Opreanu, P., ... Vasiliu, D. (2012). Studying the Romanian Shelf benthic community in EU FP7 HYPOX Project: ecosystem recovery trends vs. fish kill events. In *EGU General Assembly 2012, held 22-27 April, 2012 in Vienna, Austria* (p. 9474).
- Goodman, S., & Dmitrieva, L. (2016). *Pusa caspica*. Retrieved from <http://www.iucnredlist.org/details/41669/0>
- Gossner, M. M., Lewinsohn, T. M., Kahl, T., Grassein, F., Boch, S., Prati, D., ... Allan, E. (2016). Land-use intensification causes multitrophic homogenization of grassland communities. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20575>
- Gotelli, N. J., & Stanton-Geddes, J. (2015). Climate change, genetic markers and species distribution modelling. *Journal of Biogeography*, 42(9), 1577–1585. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12562>
- Goulson, D., Lye, G., & Darvill, B. (2008). Decline and Conservation of Bumble Bees. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 53, 191–208. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.53.103106.093454>
- Gozlan, R. E. (2008a). Introduction of non-native freshwater fish: is it all bad? *Fish and Fisheries*, 9, 106–115.
- Gozlan, R. E. (2008b). Introduction of non-native freshwater fish: is it all bad?
- Gozlan, R. E. (2015). Role and Impact of Non-native species on Inland fisheries: The Janus Syndrome. In J. F. Craig (Ed.), *Freshwater Fisheries Ecology* (p. 920pp). London: Wiley-Blackwell publisher.
- Gozlan, R. E. (2016). Interference of Non-native Species with Fisheries and Aquaculture. In P. E. Vilà, E., Hulme (Ed.), *Invading Nature - Springer Series in Invasion Ecology 12* (pp. 119–137). Cham: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45121-3>
- Gozlan, R. E., St-Hilaire, S., Feist, S. W., Martin, P., & Kent, M. L. (2005). Biodiversity: Disease threat to European fish. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/4351046a>
- Greenstreet, S. P. R., Rossberg, A. G., Fox, C. J., Le Quesne, W. J. F., Blasdale, T., Boulcott, P., ... Moffat, C. F. (2012). Demersal fish biodiversity: species-level indicators and trends-based targets for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. *Ices Journal of Marine Science*, 69(10), 1789–1801. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fss148>
- Gregory, R. D., Vorisek, P., Van Strien, A., Gmelig Meyling, A. W., Jiguet, F., Fornasari, L., ... Burfield, I.

- J. (2007). Population trends of widespread woodland birds in Europe. *Ibis*, 149(SUPPL. 2), 78–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2007.00698.x>
- Grémillet, D., & Boulinier, T. (2009). Spatial ecology and conservation of seabirds facing global climate change: a review. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 391, 121–138. <https://doi.org/10.2307/24873660>
- Griffiths, H. I., Krystufek, B., & Reed, J. M. (2004). *Balkan biodiversity: pattern and process in the European hotspot*. (Kluwer Academic, Ed.). London: Dordrecht.
- Gubbay, S., Sanders, N., Haynes, T., Janssen, J. A. M., Rodwell, J. R., Nieto, A., ... Calix, M. (2016). *European Red List of Habitats. Part 1. Marine habitats*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Guerold, F., Boudot, J. P., Gilles, J., Vein, D., Merlet, D., & Rouiller, J. (2000). Macroinvertebrate community loss as a result of headwater stream acidification in the Vosges Mountains (N-E France). *Biodiversity & Conservation*, 9, 767–783.
- Guidetti, P. (2006a). Marine reserves reestablish lost predatory interactions and cause community changes in rocky reefs. *Ecological Applications*, 16, 963–976.
- Guidetti, P. (2006b). Potential of marine reserves to cause community-wide changes beyond their boundaries. *Conservation Biology*, 21, 540–545.
- Guidetti, P., Baiata, P., Ballesteros, E., Di Franco, A., Hereu, B., Macpherson, E., ... Sala, E. (2014). Large-scale assessment of mediterranean marine protected areas effects on fish assemblages. *PLoS ONE*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0091841>
- Guisan, A., & Theurillat, J.-P. J.-P. (2001). Assessing alpine plant vulnerability to climate change: a modeling perspective. *Integrated Assessment*, 1(1), 307–320. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018912114948>
- Gurevich E. (2009). Influence of air temperature on the river runoff in winter (the Aldan river catchment case study). *Russian Meteorology and Hydrology*, 34(9), 628–633.
- Habel, J. C., Dengler, J., Janisova, M., Török, P., Wellstein, C., & Wiezik, M. (2013). European grassland ecosystems : threatened hotspots of biodiversity. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 22, 2131–2138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-013-0537-x>
- Halada, L., Evans, D., Romão, C., & Petersen, J. E. (2011). Which habitats of European importance depend on agricultural practices? *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 20(11), 2365–2378. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-9989-z>
- Hall-Spencer, J. M., Pike, J., & Munn, C. B. (2007). Diseases affect cold-water corals too: *Eunicella verrucosa* (Cnidaria: Gorgonacea) necrosis in SW England. *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms*, 76(2), 87–97. <https://doi.org/10.3354/dao076087>
- Hall-Spencer, J., Allain, V., & Fosså, J. H. (2002). Trawling damage to Northeast Atlantic ancient coral reefs. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 269(1490). Retrieved from <http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/269/1490/507>
- Hällfors, H., Backer, H., Leppänen, J. M., Hällfors, S., Hällfors, G., & Kuosa, H. (2013). The northern Baltic Sea phytoplankton communities in 1903-1911 and 1993-2005: A comparison of historical and modern species data. *Hydrobiologia*, 707(1), 109–133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-012-1414-4>
- Hallingbäck, T., & Hodgetts, N. (2001). *Status survey and conservation action plan for Bryophytes:*

- mosses, liverworts and hornworts*. (IUCN/SSC Bryophyte Specialist Group, Ed.). IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK. Retrieved from <https://portals.iucn.org/library/efiles/documents/2000-074.pdf>
- Hallmann, C. a., Foppen, R. P. B., Turnhout, C. a M. Van, Kroon, H. De, Jongejans, E., van Turnhout, C. a. M., ... Jongejans, E. (2014). Declines in insectivorous birds are associated with high neonicotinoid concentrations. *Nature*, *511*(7509), 341–343. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13531>
- Hallmann, C. A., Sorg, M., Jongejans, E., Siepel, H., Hofland, N., Schwan, H., ... De Kroon, H. (2017). More than 75 percent decline over 27 years in total flying insect biomass in protected areas. *PLoS ONE*, *12*(10). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0185809>
- Halpern, B. S., Frazier, M., Potapenko, J., Casey, K. S., Koenig, K., Longo, C., ... Walbridge, S. (2015). Spatial and temporal changes in cumulative human impacts on the world's ocean. *Nature Communications*, *6*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8615>
- Hamel, S., Killengreen, S. T., Henden, J.-A., Yoccoz, N., & Ims, R. A. (2013). Disentangling the importance of interspecific competition, food availability, and habitat in species occupancy: recolonization of the endangered Fennoscandian arctic fox. *Biological Conservation*, *160*, 114–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.01.011>
- Hamer, A. J., & Mcdonnell, M. J. (2008). Amphibian ecology and conservation in the urbanising world: A review. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.07.020>
- Hammond, P. S., Bearzi, G., Bjørge, A., Forney, K. A., Karczmarski, L., Kasuya, T., ... Wilson, B. (2008). *Phocoena phocoena* (Baltic Sea subpopulation).
- Harding, K. C., & Härkönen, T. J. (1999). Development in the Baltic Grey Seal (*Halichoerus grypus*) and Ringed Seal (*Phoca hispida*) Populations during the 20th Century. *Ambio*, *28*(7), 619–627.
- Härkönen, T. (2015). *Pusa hispida* ssp. *botnica*,. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*, *8235*(e.T41673A66991604). <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2015-4.RLTS.T41673A66991604.en>
- Harkonen, T., Harding, K. C., Wilson, S., Baimukanov, M., Dmitrieva, L., Svensson, C. J., & Goodman, S. J. (2012). Collapse of a Marine Mammal Species Driven by Human Impacts. *PLoS ONE*, *7*(9), e43130. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0043130>
- Hartel, T., Schweiger, O., Öllerer, K., Cogălniceanu, D., & Arntzen, J. W. (2010). Amphibian distribution in a traditionally managed rural landscape of Eastern Europe: Probing the effect of landscape composition. *Biological Conservation*, *143*(5), 1118–1124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.02.006>
- Hassall, C., Thompson, D. J., & Harvey, I. F. (2010). The impact of climate-induced distributional changes on the validity of biological water quality metrics. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, *160*, 451–456.
- Hassel, K., & Soderstrom, L. (2005). The expansion of the alien mosses *Orthodontium lineare* and *Campylopus introflexus* in Britain and continental Europe. *Journal of the Hattori Botanical Laboratory*, (97), 183–193.
- Hauck, M. (2009a). Global warming and alternative causes of decline in arctic-alpine and boreal-montane lichens in north-western Central Europe. *Global Change Biology*, *15*(11), 2653–2661. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01968.x>
- Hauck, M. (2009b). Global warming and alternative causes of decline in arctic-alpine and boreal-

- montane lichens in North-Western Central Europe. *Global Change Biology*, 15(11), 2653–2661. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.01968.x>
- Hauck, M. (2010). Ammonium and nitrate tolerance in lichens. *Environmental Pollution*, 158(5), 1127–1133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2009.12.036>
- Hauck, M., Bruyn, U. de, & Leuschner, C. (2013a). Dramatic diversity losses in epiphytic lichens in temperate broad-leaved forests during the last 150 years. *Biological Conservation*, 157, 136–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.06.015>
- Hauck, M., Bruyn, U. de, & Leuschner, C. (2013b). Dramatic diversity losses in epiphytic lichens in temperate broad-leaved forests during the last 150 years. *Biological Conservation*, 157, 136–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.06.015>
- Hauck, M., Zimmermann, J., Jacob, M., Dulamsuren, C., Bade, C., Ahrends, B., & Leuschner, C. (2012). Rapid recovery of stem increment in Norway spruce at reduced SO₂ levels in the Harz Mountains, Germany. *Environmental Pollution*, 164, 132–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2012.01.026>
- Hawksworth, D. L., Kirk, P. M., Sutton, B. C., & Pegler, D. N. (1996). Ainsworth & Bisby's dictionary of the fungi. *Revista Do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo*, 38(4), 272–272. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0036-46651996000400018>
- Hedberg, P., Kotowski, W., Saetre, P., Mälson, K., Rydin, H., & Sundberg, S. (2012). Vegetation recovery after multiple-site experimental fen restorations. *Biological Conservation*, 147(1), 60–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.01.039>
- Hédli, R., Petřík, P., & Boublík, K. (2011). Long-term patterns in soil acidification due to pollution in forests of the Eastern Sudetes Mountains. *Environmental Pollution*, 159(10), 2586–2593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2011.06.014>
- Hedwall, P. O., & Brunet, J. (2016). Trait variations of ground flora species disentangle the effects of global change and altered land-use in Swedish forests during 20 years. *Global Change Biology*, 22(12), 4038–4047. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13329>
- Heilmann-Clausen, J., Aude, E., van Dort, K., Christensen, M., Piltaver, A., Veerkamp, M., ... Òdor, P. (2014). Communities of wood-inhabiting bryophytes and fungi on dead beech logs in Europe - reflecting substrate quality or shaped by climate and forest conditions? *Journal of Biogeography*, 41(12), 2269–2282. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12388>
- Heilmann-Clausen, J., Barron, E. S., Boddy, L., Dahlberg, A., Griffith, G. W., Nordén, J., ... Halme, P. (2015). A fungal perspective on conservation biology. *Conservation Biology*, 29(1), 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12388>
- Heino, J. (2002). Concordance of species richness patterns among multiple freshwater taxa: a regional perspective. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 11, 137–147.
- Heino, J., Virkkala, R., & Toivonen, H. (2009). Climate change and freshwater biodiversity: Detected patterns, future trends and adaptations in northern regions. *Biological Reviews*, 84(1), 39–54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2008.00060.x>
- Heino, J., Virtanen, R., Vuori, K. M., Saastamoinen, J., Ohtonen, A., & Muotka, T. (2005). Spring bryophytes in forested landscapes: Land use effects on bryophyte species richness, community structure and persistence. *Biological Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.03.004>
- Hejcman, M., Hejcmanová, P., Pavlů, V., & Beneš, J. (2013). Origin and history of grasslands in central

- europe - A review. *Grass and Forage Science*, 68(3), 345–363.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12066>
- Hejcman, M., Száková, J., Schellberg, J., Šrek, P., Tlustoš, P., & Balík, J. (2010). The Rengen Grassland experiment: Bryophytes biomass and element concentrations after 65 years of fertilizer application. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 166(1–4), 653–662.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-009-1030-6>
- HELCOM. (2009). *Biodiversity in the Baltic Sea*.
- HELCOM. (2010). Ecosystem Health of the Baltic sea 2003-2007: HELCOM Initial Holistic Assessment. Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings No. 122. *Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings*, 122, 63.
- HELCOM. (2013). HELCOM Red List of Baltic Sea species in danger of becoming extinct. *Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings*, 140(140), 110.
- HELCOM. (2016). Towards an Assessment of Ecological Coherence of the Marine Protected Areas Network in the Baltic Sea Region, (i), 141. Retrieved from
<http://www.nature.com/doi/10.1038/nature13022>
- HELCOM. (2017a). Abundance of coastal key fish species. Retrieved July 6, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/abundance-of-key-coastal-fish-species>
- HELCOM. (2017b). Abundance of waterbirds in the breeding season. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/abundance-of-waterbirds-in-the-breeding-season/>
- HELCOM. (2017c). Abundance of waterbirds in the wintering season. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/abundance-of-waterbirds-in-the-wintering-season/>
- HELCOM. (2017d). Distribution of Baltic seals. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/distribution-of-baltic-seals/>
- HELCOM. (2017e). Distribution of Baltic seals. HELCOM core indicator report. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/distribution-of-baltic-seals/>
- HELCOM. (2017f). First version of the “ State of the Baltic Sea ” report – June 2017 – to be updated in 2018. Available at: <Http://stateofthebalticsea.helcom.fi>.
- HELCOM. (2017g). State of the soft-bottom macrofauna community. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/state-of-the-soft-bottom-macrofauna-community/>
- HELCOM. (2017h). Trends in arrival of new non-indigenous species. Retrieved July 26, 2017, from
<http://www.helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/trends-in-arrival-of-new-non-indigenous-species/>
- Henwood, W. D. (2010). Toward a strategy for the conservation and protection of the world’s temperate grasslands. *Great Plains Research*, 20(1), 121–134. Retrieved from
<http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/greatplainsresearch>
- Hering, D., Schmidt-Kloiber, A., Murphy, J., Lücke, S., Zamora-Muñoz, C., López-Rodríguez, M. J., ... Graf, W. (2009). Potential impact of climate change on aquatic insects: A sensitivity analysis for European caddisflies (Trichoptera) based on distribution patterns and ecological preferences. *Aquatic Sciences*, 71(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-009-9159-5>
- Hermý, M., Honnay, O., Firbank, L., Grashof-Bokdam, C., & Lawesson, J. E. (1999). An ecological

- comparison between ancient and other forest plant species of Europe, and the implications for forest conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 91(1), 9–22. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(99\)00045-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(99)00045-2)
- Herrera, P. M., García “Petu,” J. A., & Balmori, A. (2015). Valladolid. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 207–253). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>
- Hickling, R., Roy, D. B., Hill, J. K., Fox, R., & Thomas, C. D. (2006). The distributions of a wide range of taxonomic groups are expanding polewards. *Global Change Biology*, 12(3), 450–455.
- Hiddink, J. G., Burrows, M. T., & García Molinos, J. (2015). Temperature tracking by North Sea benthic invertebrates in response to climate change. *Global Change Biology*, 21(1), 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12726>
- Hiddink, J. G., & ter Hofstede, R. (2008). Climate induced increases in species richness of marine fishes. *Global Change Biology*, 14(3), 453–460. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2007.01518.x>
- Hobohm, C., & Bruchmann, I. (2009). Endemische Gefäßpflanzen und ihre Habitate in Europa– Plädoyer für den Schutz der Grasland-Ökosysteme. *Berichte Der Reinhold-Tüxen-Gesellschaft*, 21, 142–161.
- Hochkirch, A., Nieto, A., Braud, Y., Buzzetti, F. M., Chobanov, D., Willemse, L., & Zuna-kratky, T. (2016). *European Red List of Grasshoppers, Crickets and Bush-crickets*. <https://doi.org/10.2779/60944>
- Hodd, R. L., Bourke, D., & Skeffington, M. S. (2014). Projected range contractions of European protected oceanic montane plant communities: Focus on climate change impacts is essential for their future conservation. *PLoS ONE*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0095147>
- Hodgetts, N. (2015). *Checklist and country status of European bryophytes – towards a new Red List for Europe*. *Irish Wildlife Manuals*. National Parks and Wildlife Service. Ireland. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/2262/73373>
- Hodgetts, N. G. (1992). Measures to protect bryophytes in Great Britain. *Biological Conservation*, 59(2–3), 259–264. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(92\)90594-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(92)90594-D)
- Hof, A. R. (2015). Alien species in a warming climate: a case study of the nutcracker and stone pines. *Biological Invasions*, 17(5), 1533–1543. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-014-0813-z>
- Hofmeister, J., Hošek, J., Brabec, M., Dvořák, D., Beran, M., Deckerová, H., ... Svoboda, T. (2015). Value of old forest attributes related to cryptogam species richness in temperate forests: A quantitative assessment. *Ecological Indicators*, 57, 497–504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.05.015>
- Holsinger, J. R. (1988). Trogllobites: the evolution of cave-dwelling organisms. *American Scientist*, 76(146–153).
- Hölzel, N., Haub, C., Ingelfinger, M. P., Otte, A., & Pilipenko, V. N. (2002a). The return of the steppe large-scale restoration of degraded land in southern Russia during the post-Soviet era. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 10(2), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1078/1617-1381-00009>
- Hölzel, N., Haub, C., Ingelfinger, M. P., Otte, A., & Pilipenko, V. N. (2002b). The return of the steppe large-scale restoration of degraded land in southern Russia during the post-Soviet era. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 10(2), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1078/1617-1381-00009>

- Human Development Report 2015 Work for Human Development. (n.d.). Retrieved from www.undp.org
- Hunkeler, P. (2007). Standing Committee 27th meeting Report for On-the-spot appraisal Construction of the Hydro-electric Power Station Lesce on the Dobra River (Croatia). In *Report of the on-the-spot appraisal (5-6 June 2007)*. Strasbourg, France.
- Hunt, G. L., Drinkwater, K. F., Arrigo, K., Berge, J., Daly, K. L., Danielson, S., ... Wolf-Gladrow, D. (2016). Advection in polar and sub-polar environments: Impacts on high latitude marine ecosystems. *Progress in Oceanography*, 149, 40–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2016.10.004>
- Hunt, G. L., Katō, H., & McKinnell, S. M. (2000). *Predation by marine birds and mammals in the subarctic North Pacific Ocean. PICES Scientific Report No. 14*. PICES.
- Hutchinson, W. F., van Oosterhout, C., Rogers, S. I., & Carvalho, G. R. (2003). Temporal analysis of archived samples indicates marked genetic changes in declining North Sea cod (*Gadus morhua*). *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, 270(1529), 2125–2132. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2493>
- Icelandic Natural History Institute. (1996). *Valisti 1 Plöntur Red Data List (1) Plants*. Reyjavik.
- Ignatov, M., Afonina, O., Ignatova, E., & others. (2006). Check-list of mosses of East Europe and North Asia. *Arctoa*, 15, 1–130.
- Inger, R., Gregory, R., Duffy, J. P., Stott, I., Voříšek, P., & Gaston, K. J. (2015). Common European birds are declining rapidly while less abundant species' numbers are rising. *Ecology Letters*, 18(1), 28–36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12387>
- Innocenti, G., Stasolla, G., Goren, M., Stern, N., Levitt-Barmats, Y., Diamant, A., & Galil, B. S. (2017). Going down together: invasive host, *Charybdis longicollis* (Decapoda: Brachyura: Portunidae) and invasive parasite, *Heterosaccus dollfusi* (Cirripedia: Rhizocephala: Sacculinidae) on the upper slope off the Mediterranean coast of Israel. *Marine Biology Research*, 13(2), 229–236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2016.1240873>
- Inсарov, G., & Insarova, I. (2013). Lichens and Plants in Urban Environment. In D. Malkinson, D. Czamanski, & I. Benenson (Eds.), *Modeling of Land-Use and Ecological Dynamics* (pp. 167–193). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.
- Inсарov, G., Moutchnik, E., & Insarova, I. (2010). Epiphytic Lichens under Air Pollution Stress in Moscow: Methodology for Long-Term Monitoring. *Problems of Ecological Monitoring and Ecosystem Modelling*, 23, 277–296.
- Inсарov, G., & Schroeter, B. (2002). Lichen Monitoring and Climate Change. In P. L. Nimis, C. Scheidegger, & P. A. Wolseley (Eds.), *Monitoring with Lichens - Monitoring Lichens* (pp. 183–201). The Hague, The Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- IPBES. (2016a). *Assessment Report on Pollinators, Pollination and Food Production*. (S. G. Potts, V. L. Imperatriz-Fonseca, & H. T. Ngo, Eds.). Bonn, Germany: Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services.
- IPBES. (2016b). *IPBES Assessment Report on Pollinators, Pollination and Food Production: Summary for Policymakers*. (S. G. Potts, V. L. Imperatriz-Fonseca, H. T. Ngo, J. C. Biesmeijer, T. D. Breeze, L. V. Dicks, ... B. F. Viana, Eds.). Bonn, Germany: Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Retrieved from http://www.ipbes.net/sites/default/files/downloads/pdf/spm_deliverable_3a_pollination_2017_0222.pdf

- IPCC. (2014a). *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. (C. B. Field, V. R. Barros, D. J. Dokken, K. J. Mach, M. D. Mastrandrea, T. E. Bilir, ... L. L. White, Eds.). Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press.
- IPCC. (2014b). *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part B: Regional Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Barros, V.R., C.B. Field, D.J. Dokken, M.D. Mastrandrea]*. Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press.
- IUCN. (2016). IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. *Version 2016-1*, www.iucnredlist.org. Retrieved from www.iucnredlist.org
- IUCN. (2017a). How many species are threatened? Retrieved from <http://www.iucnredlist.org/about/summary-statistics>
- IUCN. (2017b). IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from <http://www.iucnredlist.org/>
- IUCN. (2017c). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2017.1.
- IUCN (n.d.). (n.d.). Red List of Threatened Species. Version 3.1. Retrieved September 1, 2015, from <http://www.iucnredlist.org/technical-documents/classification-schemes/habitats-classification-scheme-ver3>
- Ivanov, O. A., & Sukhanov, V. . V. (2015). Species Structure of Pelagic Ichthyocenes in Russian Waters of Far Eastern Seas and the Pacific Ocean in 1980–2009. *Journal of Ichthyology*, 55(4), 497–526.
- Jähnig, S.C., Kuemmerlen, M., Kiesel, J., Domisch, S., Cai, Q., Schmalz, B., Fohrer, N. (2012). Modelling of riverine ecosystems by integrated models: conceptual approach, a case study and research agenda. *Journal of Biogeography*, 39, 2253–2263.
- Janssen, J. A. M., Rodwell, J. S., García Criado, M., Gubbay, S., Haynes, T., Nieto, A., ... Valachovič, M. (2016). *European red list of habitats. Part 2. Terrestrial and freshwater habitats*. European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2779/091372>
- Jelić, D., Kuljerić, M., Koren T., T. D., Šalomon, D., Lončar, M., Podnar Lešić, M. ., ... Jelić, K. (2006). *Crvena knjiga vodozemaca i gmazova Hrvatske. ... kulture, Državni zavod ...*. Retrieved from <http://bib.irb.hr/prikazi-rad?lang=en&rad=282336>
- Jenkins, C., Pimm, S. L., & Joppa, L. N. (2013). Global bird diversity. Retrieved January 28, 2017, from BiodiversityMapping.org
- Jeppesen, E., Brucet, S., Naselli-Flores, L., Papastergiadou, E., Stefanidis, K., Nöges, T., ... Bekliöglu, M. (2015). Ecological impacts of global warming and water abstraction on lakes and reservoirs due to changes in water level and related changes in salinity. *Hydrobiologia*, 750(1), 201–227.
- Jeppesen, E., Brucet, S., Naselli-Flores, L., Papastergiadou, E., Stefanidis, K., Nöges, T., ... Bekliöglu, M. (2015). Ecological impacts of global warming and water abstraction on lakes and reservoirs due to changes in water level and related changes in salinity. *Hydrobiologia*, 750(1), 201–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-014-2169-x>
- Jeppesen, E., Kronvang, B., Meerhoff, M., Søndergaard, M., Hansen, K. M., Andersen, H. E., ... Olesen, J. E. (2009). Climate change effects on runoff, catchment phosphorus loading and lake ecological state, and potential adaptations. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 38, 1930–1941.

- Jeppesen, E., Meerhoff, M., Davidson, T. A., Trolle, D., Søndergaard, M., Lauridsen, T. L., ... Nielsen, A. (2014). Climate change impacts on lakes: An integrated ecological perspective based on a multi-faceted approach, with special focus on shallow lakes. *Journal of Limnology*, 73(1 SUPPL), 88–111. <https://doi.org/10.4081/jlimnol.2014.844>
- Jeppesen, E., Meerhoff, M., Holmgren, K., González-Bergonzoni, I., Teixeira-de Mello, F., Declerck, S. A. J., ... Lazzaro, X. (2010). Impacts of climate warming on lake fish community structure and potential effects on ecosystem function. *Hydrobiologia*, 646(1), 73–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-010-0171-5>
- Jeppesen, E., Mehner, T., Winfield, I. J., Kangur, K., Sarvala, J., Gerdeaux, D., ... Meerhoff, M. (2012). Impacts of climate warming on the long-term dynamics of key fish species in 24 European lakes. *Hydrobiologia*, 694(1), 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-012-1182-1>
- Jeppesen, E., Søndergaard, M., Jensen, J. P., Havens, K. E., Anneville, O., Carvalho, L., ... Winder, M. (2005). Lake responses to reduced nutrient loading - an analysis of contemporary long-term data from 35 case studies. *Freshwater Biology*, 50(10), 1747–1771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2005.01415.x>
- Jeppesen, E., Søndergaard, M., & Liu, Z. (2017). Lake Restoration and Management in a Climate Change Perspective : An Introduction, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w9020122>
- Jeppesen, E., Winfield, I. J., Trochine, C., Brucet, S., Argillier, C., Arranz, I., ... Hesthagen, T. (2017). Non-native Fish Occurrence and Biomass in 1943 Western Palearctic Lakes and Reservoirs and their Abiotic and Biotic ... Non-native Fish Occurrence and Biomass in 1943 Western Palearctic Lakes and Reservoirs and their Abiotic and Biotic Correlates, (May). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-017-0156-6>
- Jepson, P. D., Deaville, R., Barber, J. L., Aguilar, À., Borrell, A., Murphy, S., ... Law, R. J. (2016). PCB pollution continues to impact populations of orcas and other dolphins in European waters. *Scientific Reports*, 6(January), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep18573>
- Ji, R., Jin, M., & Varpe, Ø. (2013). Sea ice phenology and timing of primary production pulses in the Arctic Ocean. *Global Change Biology*, 19(3), 734–741. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12074>
- Johansson, P. (2008). Consequences of disturbance on epiphytic lichens in boreal and near boreal forests. *Biological Conservation*, 141(8), 1933–1944. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.05.013>
- Johnson, M. S., Putwain, P. D., & Holliday, R. J. (1978). Wildlife conservation value of derelict metalliferous mine workings in Wales. *Biological Conservation*, 14(2), 131–148.
- Jones, M. C., & Cheung, W. W. L. (2015). Multi-model ensemble projections of climate change effects on global marine biodiversity. *Ices Journal of Marine Science*, 72(3), 741–752. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsu172>
- Jones, M. C., Dye, S. R., Pinnegar, J. K., Warren, R., & Cheung, W. W. L. (2013). Applying distribution model projections for an uncertain future: The case of the Pacific oyster in UK waters. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 23(5), 710–722. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2364>
- Jönsson, M. T., & Thor, G. (2012). Estimating Coextinction Risks from Epidemic Tree Death: Affiliate Lichen Communities among Diseased Host Tree Populations of *Fraxinus excelsior*. *PLoS ONE*, 7(9), e45701. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0045701>
- Joppa, L. N., O'Connor, B., Visconti, P., Smith, C., Geldmann, J., Hoffmann, M., ... Burgess, D. N. (2016). Filling in biodiversity threat gaps. *Science*, 352(6284), 416–418.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf3565>

- Jørgensen, P. S., Böhning-Gaese, K., Thorup, K., Tøttrup, A. P., Chylarecki, P., Jiguet, F., ... Rahbek, C. (2016). Continent-scale global change attribution in European birds - combining annual and decadal time scales. *Global Change Biology*, 22(2), 530–543. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13097>
- Jovanović Glavaš, O., Jalžić, B., & Bilandžija, H. (2017). Population density, habitat dynamic and aerial survival of relict cave bivalves from genus *Congeria* in the Dinaric karst. *International Journal of Speleology*, 46(1), 13–22.
- Juberthie, C. (2000). Conservation of subterranean habitats and species. In Wilkens, H., D. C. Culver, & W. Humphreys (Eds.), *Ecosystems of the World: subterranean ecosystems* (pp. 691–700). Amsterdam: Elsevier Science Publishers.
- Kabisch, N., & Haase, D. (2013). Green spaces of European cities revisited for 1990-2006. *Landscape and Urban Planning*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.10.017>
- Kaiser, J., Clarke, K. R., Hinz, H., Austen, M. C. V., Somerfield, P. J., & Karakassis, I. (2006). Global analysis of response and recovery of benthic biota to fishing. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 311, 1–14.
- Kalkman, V. J., Boudot, J.-P., Bernard, R., Conze, K.-J., De Knijf, G., Dyatlova, E., ... Sahlén, G. (2010). *European Red List of Dragonflies*. <https://doi.org/10.2779/84650>
- Kamenos, N. A. (2010). North Atlantic summers have warmed more than winters since 1353, and the response of marine zooplankton. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 107(52), 22442–22447. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1006141107>
- Kamilov, G. K. (1973). *ishes and biological basis of fishery use of in Uzbekistan reservoirs*. Fan.Tashkent.
- Kamp, J., Koshkin, M. A., Bragina, T. M., Katzner, T. E., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Schreiber, D., ... Urazaliev, R. (2016a). Persistent and novel threats to the biodiversity of Kazakhstan's steppes and semi-deserts. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1083-0>
- Kamp, J., Koshkin, M. A., Bragina, T. M., Katzner, T. E., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Schreiber, D., ... Urazaliev, R. (2016b). Persistent and novel threats to the biodiversity of Kazakhstan's steppes and semi-deserts. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1083-0>
- Kamp, J., Urazaliev, R., Donald, P. F., & Hölzel, N. (2011). Post-Soviet agricultural change predicts future declines after recent recovery in Eurasian steppe bird populations. *Biological Conservation*, 144(11), 2607–2614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2011.07.010>
- Kämpf, I., Mathar, W., Kuzmin, I., Hölzel, N., & Kiehl, K. (2016). Post-Soviet recovery of grassland vegetation on abandoned fields in the forest steppe zone of Western Siberia. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1078-x>
- Karelian research centre of the Russian Academy of Sciences. (2008). Fundamental and applied problems of botany at the beginning of the 21st century: *Materials of all-Russian conference Part 2: Algology. Mycology. Lichenology. Bryology*.
- Karimov, B. (2011). An overview on desert aquaculture in Central Asia (Aral Sea Drainage Basin). In *Aquaculture in desert and arid lands* (pp. 61–84). Rome: FAO.
- Karimov, B. K., Kamilov, B. G., & Matthies, M. (2014). Unconventional water resources of agricultural origin and their re-utilization potential for development of desert land aquaculture in the Aral Sea basin. In *The Global Water System in the Anthropocene: Challenges for Science and*

Governance (pp. 183–200). Springer International Publishing Switzerland.

- Karimov, B. K., Kamilov, B. G., Upare, M., Van Anrooy, R., Bueno, P., & Shohimardonov, D. R. (2009). Inland capture fisheries and aquaculture in the republic of Uzbekistan: current status and planning. *Fish Aquac Circular Rome*, (1030(1)), 1–124.
- Karimov B.K., B.G. Kamilov, M. M. (2014). Unconventional water resources of agricultural origin and their re-utilization potential for development of desert land aquaculture in the Aral Sea basin. In M. Bhaduri, Bogardi, Leentvaar (Ed.), *Challenges for Science and Governance* (pp. 183–200). Springer International Publishing Switzerland.
- Kašák, J., Mazalová, M., Šipoš, J., & Kuras, T. (2015). Dwarf pine: invasive plant threatens biodiversity of alpine beetles. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 24(10), 2399–2415.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-0929-1>
- Kasymov A.G. [Касымов А.Г.]. (1987). *Каспийское море [The Caspian Sea]*. Leningrad: Гидрометеоиздат [Gidrometeoizdat].
- Kauserud, H., Heegaard, E., Büntgen, U., Halvorsen, R., Egli, S., Senn-Irlet, B., ... Stenseth, N. C. (2012). Warming-induced shift in European mushroom fruiting phenology. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(36), 14488–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1200789109>
- Kazanci, N., Girgin, S., & Dügel, M. (2004). On the limnology of Salda Lake, a large and deep soda lake in southwestern Turkey: future management proposals. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, (14(2)), 151–162.
- Kazantcheev E.N. [Казанчев Е.Н.]. (1981). *Рыбы Каспийского моря [Fishes of the Caspian Sea]*. Moscow: Легкая и пищевая промышленность [Legkaya i pischevaya promyshlennost].
- Kearns, C. A., Inouye, D. W., & Waser, N. M. (1998). Endangered Mutualisms: The Conservation of Plant-Pollinator Interactions. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 29(1), 83–112.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.29.1.83>
- Kędra, M., Moritz, C., Choy, E. S., David, C., Degen, R., Duerksen, S., ... Węśławski, J. M. (2015). Status and trends in the structure of Arctic benthic food webs. *Polar Research*, 34(2015).
<https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v34.23775>
- Kędra, M., Moritz, C., Choy, E. S., David, C., Degen, R., Duerksen, S., ... Węśławski, J. M. (2015). Status and trends in the structure of Arctic benthic food webs. *Polar Research*, 34(1), 23775.
<https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v34.23775>
- Keeley, J. E., Bond, W. J., Bradstock, R. A., Pausas, J. G., & Rundel, P. W. (2012). *Fire in Mediterranean Ecosystems: Ecology, Evolution and Management*. Cambridge University Press.
- Keith, S. A., Newton, A. C., Morecroft, M. D., Bealey, C. E., & Bullock, J. M. (2009). Taxonomic homogenization of woodland plant communities over 70 years. *Proceedings. Biological Sciences / The Royal Society*, 276(1672), 3539–44. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2009.0938>
- Kelcey, J. (2015). *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna*. (J. Kelcey, Ed.) (1st ed.). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>
- Kelcey, J., & Rheinwald, G. (2005). Conclusions. In J. Kelcey & G. Rheinwald (Eds.), *Birds in European Cities* (1st ed., pp. 417–422). St. Katharinen: Ginster verlag.
- Kell, S. P., Maxted, N., & Bilz, M. (2012). European crop wild relative threat assessment: knowledge

- gained and lessons learnt. In P. de C. M. Maxted N, Dulloo ME, Ford-Lloyd BV, Frese L, Iriondo JM (Ed.), *Agrobiodiversity Conservation: Securing the Diversity of Crop Wild Relatives and Landraces* (p. 218–242). Wallingford: CAB International.
- Kenis, M., & Branco, M. (2010). Impact of alien terrestrial arthropods in Europe. Chapter 5. *BioRisk*, 4(1), 51–71. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biorisk.4.42>
- Kestrup, Å. M., Smith, D. L., & Therriault, T. W. (Eds.). (2015). *Report of Working Group 21 on Non-indigenous Aquatic Species. PICES Sci. Rep. No. 48*. PICES.
- Ketelaars, H. A. M., Lambregts-van De Clundert, F. E., Carpentier, C. J., Wagenvoort, A. J., & Hoogenboezem, W. (1999). Ecological effects of the mass occurrence of the Ponto-Caspian invader, *Hemimysis anomala* G.O. Sars, 1907 (Crustacea: Mysidacea), in a freshwater storage reservoir in the Netherlands, with notes on its autecology and new records. *Hydrobiologia*, 394, 233–248. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1003619631920>
- Ketner-Oostra, R., & Sýkora, K. V. (2004). Decline of lichen-diversity in calcium-poor coastal dune vegetation since the 1970s, related to grass and moss encroachment. *Phytocoenologia*, 34(4), 521–549. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0340-269X/2004/0034-0521>
- Kharuk, V. I., Ranson, K. J., Im, S. T., & Naurzbaev, M. M. (2006). Forest-tundra larch forests and climatic trends. *Russian Journal of Ecology*, 37(5), 291–298. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1067413606050018>
- Khrustalev, Y. P., Ivlieva, O. V., Bepalova, A. A., Pirumova, E. I., [Хрусталеv Ю.П., Ивлиева О.В., ... Пирумова Е.И.]. (2001). Ландшафты Азовского моря и их преобразование под влиянием хозяйственной деятельности [Landscapes of the Azov sea and their transformation under the impact of economic activity]. In *Экологические проблемы природопользования [Ecological problems of nature management]* (pp. 110–123). Taganrog: ФГУ «Азовморвод» [FGU “Azovmorvod”].
- Kideys, A. E. (2002). Fall and Rise of the Black Sea Ecosystem. *Science*, 297(5586), 1482–1484. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1073002>
- Kipriyanova, L. M., Yermolaeva, N. I., Bezmaternykh, D. M., Dvurechenskaya, S. Y., & Mitrofanova, E. Y. (2007). Changes in the biota of Chany Lake along a salinity gradient. *Hydrobiologia*, (576(1)), 83–93.
- Kirby, R. R., & Beaugrand, G. (2009). Trophic amplification of climate warming. *Proceedings. Biological Sciences / The Royal Society*, 276(1676), 4095–103. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2009.1320>
- Kirschbaum, U., Windisch, U., Vorbeck, A., & Hanewald, K. (2006). Mapping lichen diversity in Wetzlar and Giessen as an indicator of air quality: Comparison between the surveys of 1970, 1985, 1995 and 2005. *Gefahrstoffe Reinhaltung Der Luft*, 66(6), 272–280.
- Kleijn, D., Rundlöf, M., Scheper, J., Smith, H. G., & Tscharntke, T. (2011). Does conservation on farmland contribute to halting the biodiversity decline? *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 26(9), 474–481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2011.05.009>
- Kleinbauer, I., Dullinger, S., Peterseil, J., & Essl, F. (2010). Climate change might drive the invasive tree *Robinia pseudacacia* into nature reserves and endangered habitats. *Biological Conservation*, 143(2), 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2009.10.024>
- Klonner, G., Dullinger, I., Wessely, J., Bossdorf, O., Carboni, M., Dawson, W., ... Dullinger, S. (2017). Will climate change increase hybridization risk between potential plant invaders and their congeners in Europe? *Diversity and Distributions*, 23(8), 934–943.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12578>

- Kobelt, M., & Nentwig, W. (2008). Alien spider introductions to Europe supported by global trade. *Diversity and Distributions*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2007.00426.x>
- Koch, M., Bowes, G., Ross, C., & Zhang, X.-H. (2013). Climate change and ocean acidification effects on seagrasses and marine macroalgae. *Global Change Biology*, 19(1), 103–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2012.02791.x>
- Koh, L. P. (2004). Species Coextinctions and the Biodiversity Crisis. *Science*, 305(5690), 1632–1634. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1101101>
- Kolman, R., Kapusta, A., & Duda, A. (2011). Re-establishing the Atlantic Sturgeon (*Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus* Mitchill) in Poland. In P. Williot, E. Rochard, J. Gessner, & F. Kirschbaum (Eds.), *Biology and Conservation of the European Sturgeon Acipenser sturio* L. 1758 (pp. 573–581). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-20611-5>
- König, Cl., & Weick, F. (2008). *Owls of the world*. London: Christopher Helm.
- Kontorovich, A. E., Eder, L. V., Filimonova, I. V., Nemov, V. U., & Provornaya, I. V. (2013). Нефтяная промышленность Дальнего Востока: современное состояние и перспективы развития [Oil industry of the Russian Far East: modern state and development perspectives]. *Бурение И Нефть [Drilling and Oil]*, (7–8), 3–9.
- Konvička, M., Fric, Z., & Beneš, J. (2006). Butterfly extinctions in European states: Do socioeconomic conditions matter more than physical geography? *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 15(1), 82–92. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2006.00188.x>
- Kopecký, M., Hédli, R., & Szabó, P. (2013). Non-random extinctions dominate plant community changes in abandoned coppices. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 50(1), 79–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12010>
- Körner, C. (2012). *Alpine treelines: functional ecology of the global high elevation tree limits*. Basel: Springer.
- Korotchenko, I., & Peregrym, M. (2012). Ukrainian Steppes in the Past, at Present and in the Future. In *Eurasian Steppes. Ecological Problems and Livelihoods in a Changing World* (pp. 173–196). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-3886-7_5
- Korpinen, S., & Jormalainen, V. (2008). Grazing and nutrients reduce recruitment success of *Fucus vesiculosus* L. (Fucales: Phaeophyceae). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 78(2), 437–444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2008.01.005>
- Kortsch, S., Primicerio, R., Fossheim, M., Dolgov, A. V., & Aschan, M. (2015). Climate change alters the structure of arctic marine food webs due to poleward shifts of boreal generalists. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 282(1814). Retrieved from <http://rspb.royalsocietypublishing.org/content/282/1814/20151546>
- Koslow, J. A., Auster, P., Bergstad, O. A., Roberts, J. M., Rogers, A., Vecchione, M., ... Bernal, P. (2016). Chapter 51. Biological Communities on Seamounts and Other Submarine Features Potentially Threatened by Disturbance. *The First Global Integrated Marine Assessment: World Ocean Assessment I*, 1–26. Retrieved from http://www.un.org/Depts/los/global_reporting/WOA_RPROC/Chapter_51.pdf http://www.un.org/Depts/los/global_reporting/WOA_RegProcess.htm
- Košuthová, A., Svitková, I., Pišút, I., Senko, D., & Valachovič, M. (2013). The impact of forest management on changes in composition of terricolous lichens in dry acidophilous Scots pine

- forests. *The Lichenologist*, 45(3), 413–425. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002428291300011X>
- Kotlyakov V.M. [Котляков В.М.]. (2004). Азовское море [The Azov Sea]. In *Национальный атлас России [The National Atlas of Russia]* (pp. 254–257). Moscow: Федеральное агентство геодезии и картографии (РОСКАРТОГРАФИЯ) [The Federal Agency of Geodesy and Cartography (ROSKARTOGRAFIYA)].
- Kotova, I., Kayukova, E., & Kotov, S. (2016). Peloids of Crimean salt lakes and the Dead Sea: controls on composition and formation. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, (75(16)), 1207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-016-5999-1>
- Kotta, J., Almroth-rosell, E., Andersson, H. C., Eilola, K., Hinrichsen, H. H., Jänes, H., ... Dewitz, B. Von. (2016). BONUS BIO-C3 Biodiversity changes : causes, consequences and management implications, (Art 185). <https://doi.org/10.3289/BIO-C3>
- Kotze, J., Venn, S., Niemelä, J., & Spence, J. (2014). Effects of Urbanization on the Ecology and Evolution of Arthropods. *Urban Ecology Patterns, Processes, and Applications*, 6(38), 45–66. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof>
- Kovács-Hostyánszki, A., Li, J. L., Pettis, J., Settele, J., Aneni, T., Espíndola, A., ... Vandame, R. (2016). Chapter 2: Drivers of change of pollinators, pollination networks and pollination. In S. G. Potts, V. L. Imperatriz-Fonseca, & H. T. Ngo (Eds.), *IPBES Assessment Report on Pollinators, Pollination and Food Production*. Bonn, Germany: Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services.
- Kovalenko, A. E., Bondartseva, M. A., Karatygin, I. V., Melnik, V. A., Novozhilov, Y. K., Popov, E. S., & Pystina, K. A. (2005). State of the study and estimation of the species diversity of fungi and myxomycetes of Russia // Fungi in natural and anthropogenic ecosystems. In *Proceedings of international conference dedicated to the 100 anniversary of the beginning of the work of prof. A.A.S. Bondartsev in the Komarov Botanical Institute RAS* (pp. 267–270). Saint-Petersburg.
- Krader, L. (1955). Ecology of central Asian pastoralism. *Southwestern Journal of Anthropology*, 11(4), 301–326. Retrieved from <http://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/soutjanth.11.4.3628907?journalCode=soutjanth&>
- Kraus, D., & Krumm, F. (2013). *Integrative approaches as an opportunity for the conservation of forest biodiversity. International Journal of Environmental Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207233.2014.889472>
- Kresin, V. S., Eremenko, E. V., Zakharchenko, M. A., Yurchenko, A. I., [Кресин В.С., Еременко Е.В., & Захарченко М.А. Юрченко А.И.]. (2008). Динамика поступления соединений фосфора в украинские прибрежные воды Черного моря и комплекс водоохраных мероприятий [Dynamics of phosphorus compounds arrivals in the Ukrainian coastal Black Sea water and complex of water conservation measures]. *Экология Окружающей Среды И Безопасность [Ecology Environment and Safety]*, (5), 28–33.
- Kristiansen, T., Stock, C., Drinkwater, K. F., & Curchitser, E. N. (2014). Mechanistic insights into the effects of climate change on larval cod. *Global Change Biology*, 20(5), 1559–1584. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12489>
- Kristinsson, H., Zhurbenko, M., & Steen Hansen, E. (2010). Panarctic checklist of lichens and lichenicolous. *CAFF Technical Report No. 20, CAFF International Secretariat, Akureyri, Iceland*, (October 2010), 19–20.
- Kuemmerle, T., Levers, C., Erb, K., Estel, S., Jepsen, M. R., Müller, D., ... Reenberg, A. (2016). Hotspots

- of land use change in Europe. *Environmental Research Letters*, 11(6), 64020.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/6/064020>
- Kuijper, D. P. J., Jedrzejewska, B., Brzeziecki, B., Churski, M., Jedrzejewski, W., & Zybura, H. (2010). Fluctuating ungulate density shapes tree recruitment in natural stands of the Białowieża Primeval Forest, Poland. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 21(6), 1082–1098.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2010.01217.x>
- Kuksa, V. I., & [Кукса В.И.]. (1994). Южные моря (Аральское, Каспийское, Азовское и Черное) в условиях антропогенного стресса [Southern Seas (Aral, Caspian, Azov and Black) in anthropogenic stress conditions]. St. Peterburg: Hydrometeoizdat.
- Kulagin V.M. [Кулагин В.М.], Markov P.A. [Марков П.А.], & Tishkov A.A. [Тишков А.А.]. (1990). Иссык-Кульский заповедник [Issyk-Kul strict natural reserve]. In *Заповедники Средней Азии и Казахстана. Заповедники СССР [Strict natural reserves of Central Asia and Kazakhstan. Strict natural reserves of the USSR]* (p. 399). Moscow: Мысль [Mysl].
- Kumpula, T., Forbes, B. C., Stammer, F., & Meschtyb, N. (2012). Dynamics of a coupled system: Multi-resolution remote sensing in assessing social-ecological responses during 25 years of gas field development in Arctic Russia. *Remote Sensing*, 4(4), 1046–1068.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs40401046>
- Kumpula, T., Pajunen, A., Kaarlejärvi, E., Forbes, B. C., & Stammer, F. (2011). Land use and land cover change in Arctic Russia: Ecological and social implications of industrial development. *Global Environmental Change*, 21(2), 550–562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.12.010>
- Künzi, Y., Prati, D., Fischer, M., & Boch, S. (2015). Reduction of Native Diversity by Invasive Plants Depends on Habitat Conditions. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*, (October), 2718–2733.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/ajps.2015.617273>
- Kupianskaya, A. N., Proshchalykin, M. Y., & Lelej, A. S. (2014). Contribution to the fauna of bumble bees (Hymenoptera, Apidae: *Bombus* Latreille, 1802) of the Republic of Tyva, Eastern Siberia. *Euroasian Entomological Journal*, 13(3), 290–294.
- Kuzemko, A. A., Steinbauer, M. J., Becker, T., Didukh, Y. P., Dolnik, C., Jeschke, M., ... Dengler, J. (2016). Patterns and drivers of phytodiversity in steppe grasslands of Central Podolia (Ukraine). *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(12), 2233–2250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1060-7>
- Laidre, K. L., Stern, H., Kovacs, K. M., Lowry, L., Moore, S. E., Regehr, E. V., ... Ugarte, F. (2015). Arctic marine mammal population status, sea ice habitat loss, and conservation recommendations for the 21st century. *Conservation Biology*, 29(3), 724–737. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12474>
- Lambin, E. F., & Meyfroidt, P. (2011). Global land use change, economic globalization, and the looming land scarcity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 108(9), 3465–3472. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1100480108>
- Landolt, J., Gross, A., Holdenrieder, O., & Pautasso, M. (2016). Ash dieback due to *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*: what can be learnt from evolutionary ecology? *Plant Pathology*, 65(7), 1056–1070.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12539>
- Landsat-8. (2016). Lake Chany. Retrieved from <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>
- Lang, S. I., Cornelissen, J. H. C., Shaver, G. R., Ahrens, M., Callaghan, T. V., Molau, U., ... Aerts, R. (2012). Arctic warming on two continents has consistent negative effects on lichen diversity and mixed effects on bryophyte diversity. *Global Change Biology*, 18(3), 1096–1107.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02570.x>

- Larsen, J.N., O.A. Anisimov, A. Constable, A.B. Hollowed, N. Maynard, P. Prestrud, T.D. Prowse, and J. M. R. S. (2014). Polar regions. In C. B. Field, D. Barros, Vicente R., M. Mastrandrea, K. Mach, T. Bilir, M. Chatterjee, ... L. White (Eds.), *Climate change 2014 : impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability : Working Group II contribution to the fifth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (pp. 1567–1612). Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from <http://www.citeulike.org/group/15400/article/13497155>
- Latvian Academy of Science, L. A. of. (1997). *Red Data Book of Latvia - Vascular Plants and Mosses*.
- Le Roux, X., Barbault, R., Baudry, J., Burel, F., Doussan, I., Garnier, E., ... Trommetter, M. (2010). *Agriculture and biodiversity: Benefiting from synergies*.
- Le Viol, I., Jiguet, F., Brotons, L., Herrando, S., Lindström, A., Pearce-Higgins, J. W., ... Devictor, V. (2012). More and more generalists: two decades of changes in the European avifauna. *Biology Letters*, 8(5), 780–2. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2012.0496>
- Leeuwen, C. V., Emeljanenko, T., & Popova, L. (1994). *Nomads in Central Asia: animal husbandry and culture in transition (19th-20th century)*. Amsterdam: Koninklijk Instituut voor de Tropen (KIT)(Royal Tropical Institute, RTI). Retrieved from <https://www.cabdirect.org/cabdirect/abstract/19951800186>
- Lehsten, V., Sykes, M. T., Scott, A. V., Tzanopoulos, J., Kallimanis, A., Mazaris, A., ... Vogiatzakis, I. (2015). Disentangling the effects of land-use change, climate and CO₂ on projected future European habitat types. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 24(6), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12291>
- Lelej, A. S., & Storozhenko, S. Y. (2010). Insect taxonomic diversity in the Russian Far East. *Entomological Review*, 90(2), 372–386. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S001387381003005X>
- Lenoir, J., Gégout, J. C., Marquet, P. A., de Ruffray, P., & Brisse, H. (2008). A significant upward shift in plant species optimum elevation during the 20th century. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 320(5884), 1768–71. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1156831>
- Leppäkoski, E., Gollasch, S., Gruszka, P., Ojaveer, H., Olenin, S., & Panov, V. (2002). The Baltic - —a sea of invaders. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 59(7), 1175–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1139/f02-089>
- Leppik, E., Jüriado, I., Suija, A., & Liira, J. (2013). The conservation of ground layer lichen communities in alvar grasslands and the relevance of substitution habitats. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 22(3), 591–614. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-012-0430-z>
- Lester, S.E., Halpern, B.S., Grorud-Colvert, K., Lubchenco, J. Ruttenberg, B.I., Gaines, S.D., Airamé, S., and Warner, R. R. (2009). Biological effects within no-take marine reserves: a global synthesis. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 348, 33–46.
- Levers, C., Müller, D., Erb, K., Haberl, H., Jepsen, M. R., Metzger, M. J., ... Kuemmerle, T. (2015). Archetypical patterns and trajectories of land systems in Europe. *Regional Environmental Change*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0907-x>
- Levin, L. A., Mengerink, K., Gjerde, K. M., Rowden, A. A., Van Dover, C. L., Clark, M. R., ... Bridler, J. (2016). Defining “serious harm” to the marine environment in the context of deep-seabed mining. *Marine Policy*, 74(October), 245–259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2016.09.032>
- Lilleleht, V. (1998). *Eesti Puname Raama. Ohustatud seemed, taimed ja loomad Red data book of Estonia. Threatened Fungi, Plants and Animals*. Tartu: Eesti Teaduste Akadeemia, Looduskaitse Komisjon.

- Lindal Jørgensen, L., Archambault, P., Armstrong, C., Dolgov, A., Edinger, E., Gaston, T., ... Hannah, C. (2016). Chapter 36G. Arctic Ocean. In *The First Global Integrated Marine Assessment - World Ocean Assessment I* (pp. 1–47). New York. Retrieved from http://www.un.org/depts/los/global_reporting/WOA_RPROC/Chapter_36G.pdf
- Lindner, M. M., Maroschek, S., Netherer, A., Kremer, A., Barbati, J., Garcia-Gonzalo, R., ... Marchetti, M. (2010). Climate change impacts, adaptive capacity, and vulnerability of European forest ecosystems. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 259(4), 698–709.
- Lindsey, R. (2016). Shrinking Aral Sea. Retrieved from http://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/Features/WorldOfChange/arak_sea.php
- Liška, J., Zdeněk, P., & Slavíková, Š. (2012). Lichen flora of the Czech Republic. *Preslia*, 84(3), 851–862. Retrieved from <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-84865453402&partnerID=tZOtx3y1>
- Lisowska, M. (2011). Lichen recolonisation in an urban-industrial area of southern Poland as a result of air quality improvement. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 179(1–4), 177–190. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-010-1727-6>
- Liu, Y., Webber, S., Bowgen, K., Schmaltz, L., Bradley, K., Halvarsson, P., ... Griesser, M. (2013). Environmental factors influence both abundance and genetic diversity in a widespread bird species. *Ecology and Evolution*, 3(14), 4683–4695. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.856>
- Lõhmus, A., Nellis, R., Pullerits, M., & Leivits, M. (2016). The Potential for Long-Term Sustainability in Seminatural Forestry: A Broad Perspective Based on Woodpecker Populations. *Environmental Management*, 57(3), 558–571. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-015-0638-2>
- Lõhmus, A., & Runnel, K. (2014). Ash dieback can rapidly eradicate isolated epiphyte populations in production forests: A case study. *Biological Conservation*, 169, 185–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.11.031>
- Lomský, B., Šrámek, V., & Novotný, R. (2012). Changes in the air pollution load in the Jizera Mts.: Effects on the health status and mineral nutrition of the young Norway spruce stands. *European Journal of Forest Research*, 131(3), 757–771. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10342-011-0549-6>
- LPI. (2016). Living Planet Index. 2016. Retrieved from <http://www.livingplanetindex.org/>
- Ludwig, G., & Schnittler, M. (1996). *Rote Liste gefährdeter Pflanzen Deutschlands*. BfN.
- Lukić-Bilela, L., Ozimec, R., Miculinić, K., & Basara, D. (2013). A comprehensive valorisation of Megara cave with a view to preservation and protection. *Natura Montenegrina*, 12(3), 1–17.
- Lynam, C. P., & Rossberg, A. G. (2017). New univariate characterization of fish community size structure improves precision beyond the Large Fish Indicator. Retrieved from <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.06569>
- MacDonald, D., Crabtree, J. ., Wiesinger, G., Dax, T., Stamou, N., Fleury, P., ... Gibon, a. (2000). Agricultural abandonment in mountain areas of Europe: Environmental consequences and policy response. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 59(1), 47–69. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jema.1999.0335>
- Madre, F., Vergnes, A., Machon, N., & Clergeau, P. (2013). A comparison of 3 types of green roof as habitats for arthropods. *Ecological Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2013.04.029>
- Madžule, L., Brumelis, G., & Tjarve, D. (2012). Structures determining bryophyte species richness in a managed forest landscape in boreo-nemoral Europe. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 21(2), 437–

450. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-0192-z>
- Magurran, A. E., Dornelas, M., Moyes, F., Gotelli, N. J., & McGill, B. (2015). Rapid biotic homogenization of marine fish assemblages. *Nature Communications*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms9405>
- Mair, L., Harrison, P. J., Rätty, M., Bärning, L., Strandberg, G., & Snäll, T. (2017). Forest management could counteract distribution retractions forced by climate change: *Ecological Applications*, 27(5), 1485–1497. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1541>
- Mäkeläinen, S., De Knegt, H. J., Ovaskainen, O., & Hanski, I. K. (2016). Home-range use patterns and movements of the Siberian flying squirrel in urban forests: Effects of habitat composition and connectivity. *Movement Ecology*, 4(5). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40462-016-0071-z>
- Макоедов, А. Н., Козхемиако, О. Н., [Макоедов А.Н., & Кожемяко О.Н.]. (2007). *Основы рыбохозяйственной политики России [The Principles of fishery policy in Russian Federation]*. Moscow: Нац. рыб. ресурсы [National fish resources].
- Malaj, E., von der Ohe, P. C., Grote, M., Kühne, R., Mondy, C. P., Usseglio-Polatera, P., ... Schäfer, R. B. (2014). Organic chemicals jeopardize the health of freshwater ecosystems on the continental scale. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(26), 9549–54. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1321082111>
- Máliš, F., Kopecký, M., Petřík, P., Vladovič, J., Merganič, J., & Vida, T. (2016). Life stage, not climate change, explains observed tree range shifts. *Global Change Biology*, 22(5), 1904–1914. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13210>
- Mamaev, V. (2002). The Caspian Sea - enclosed and with many endemic species. In *Europe's biodiversity - biogeographical regions and seas. Seas around Europe. EEA Report No 1/2002* (pp. 1–26). EEA.
- Manca, M., & DeMott, W. R. (2009). Response of the invertebrate predator *Bythotrephes* to a climate-linked increase in the duration of a refuge from fish predation. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 54(part2), 2506–2512. https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2009.54.6_part_2.2506
- Mannerla, M., Andersson, M., Birzaks, J., Debowski, P., Degerman, E., Huhmarniemi, A., ... Yrjänä, T. (2011). Salmon and Sea Trout Populations and Rivers in the Baltic Sea.
- Mansuroglu, S., Ortacesme, V., & Karaguzel, O. (2006). Biotope mapping in an urban environment and its implications for urban management in Turkey. *Journal of Environmental Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2005.10.008>
- Manu, M., Szekely, L., Oromulu, L. V., Bărbuceanu, D., Honciuc, V., Maican, S., ... Ion, M. (2015). Bucharest. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 379–451). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>
- Marhold K. and al. (1999). *Zoznam nízších a vyšších rastlín Slovenska Check List of Non-vascular and Vascular Plants of Slovakia (Contains also red lists of Fungi, Lichens, Bryophytes, Ferns and Flowering plants)*. Bratislava: Veda.
- Marian, S. (1903). *Insectele în limba: credințele, si obiceiurile Românilor*. Studiu folkloristic Inst. de Arte Grafice“ Carol Göbl.”
- Markovic, D., Carrizo, S., Freyhof, J., Cid, N., Lengyel, S., Scholz, M., ... Darwall, W. (2014). Europe's freshwater biodiversity under climate change: Distribution shifts and conservation needs. *Diversity and Distributions*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12232>

- Marmor, L., Randle, T., Jürriado, I., & Saag, A. (2017). Host tree preferences of red-listed epiphytic lichens in Estonia. *Baltic Forestry*, 23(2), 364–373.
- Martin-Mehers, G. (2016). *Western Gray Whale Advisory Panel: Stories of influence*. IUCN, WWF, IFAW.
- Martin, A. (2009). The Loch Ness monster and La Palma giant lizard *Gallotia auaritae*: are they really extant? *Oryx*, 43, 17.
- Masterman, E. W. G. (1921). Crocodiles in Palestine. *Palestine Exploration Fund: Quarterly Statement*, 1920, 19–21.
- Mateo Miras Martínez-Solano, I., J. A. (2009). *Gallotia auaritae*. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2009*, e.T61501A12492629. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2009.RLTS.T61501A12492629.en>
- Mathar, W., Kleinebecker, T., & Hölzel, N. (2015). Environmental variation as a key process of co-existence in flood-meadows. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 26(3), 480–491. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvs.12254>
- Mathar, W. P., Kämpf, I., Kleinebecker, T., Kuzmin, I., Tolstikov, A., Tupitsin, S., & Hölzel, N. (2015). Floristic diversity of meadow steppes in the Western Siberian Plain: effects of abiotic site conditions, management and landscape structure. *Biodiversity and Conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-1023-4>
- Maykop. (2012). *The Red Data Book of the Republic of Adygheya. Rare and threatened representatives of the regional fauna and flora. Part 1. Introduction. Vegetabilia and Mycota. Second edition. Maykop, 183 p. [In Russian]. (Урбанавичюс Г. П., Урбанавичене И. Н., Отте Ф. . (MAYKOP, Ed.) (Second Edi)*.
- McCauley, B. D. J., Woods, P., Sullivan, B., Bergman, B., Jablonicky, C., Roan, A., ... Boerder, K. (2016). Ending hide and seek at sea. *Science*, 351(6278), 1148–1150. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad5686>
- McCauley, D. J., Pinsky, M. L., Palumbi, S. R., Estes, J. a., Joyce, F. H., & Warner, R. R. (2015). Marine defaunation: Animal loss in the global ocean. *Science*, 347(6219), 247–254. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1255641>
- McKinney, M. L. (2006). Urbanization as a major cause of biotic homogenization. *Biological Conservation*, 127(3), 247–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.09.005>
- McNeill, D. C. (2010). *Translocation of a population of great crested newts (Triturus cristatus): a Scottish case study*. University of Glasgow. Retrieved from <http://theses.gla.ac.uk/2184/>
- McQuatters-Gollop, A., Raitsos, D. E., Edwards, M., & Attrill, M. J. (2007). Spatial patterns of diatom and dinoflagellate seasonal cycles in the NE Atlantic Ocean. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 339, 301–306.
- Mcrae, L., Deinet, S., Gill, M., & Collen, B. (2011). *Tracking trends in Arctic marine populations*. Akureyri, Iceland: Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/11374/219>
- MedPAN and RAC/SPA. (2016). The 2016 status of Marine Protected Areas in the Mediterranean. Main findings.
- Meerhoff, M., Teixeira-de Mello, F., Kruk, C., Alonso, C., González-Bergonzoni, I., Pacheco, J. P., ... Jeppesen, E. (2012). *Environmental Warming in Shallow Lakes. A Review of Potential Changes in*

Community Structure as Evidenced from Space-for-Time Substitution Approaches. Advances in Ecological Research (Vol. 46). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-396992-7.00004-6>

- Meiri Bauer, A., Castro-Herrera, F., Chirio, L., Colli, G., Das, I., Doan, T., Glaw, F., Grismer, L., Hoogmoed, M., Kraus, F., LeBreton, M., Meirte, D., Nagy, Z., Nogueira, C., Oliver, P., Pincheira-Donoso, D., Shea, G., Sindaco, R., Tallwin, O., Torres, S. (2017). Extinct, obscure or imaginary: the lizard species with the smallest ranges. *Diversity & Distributions*, *in press*.
- Meliadou, A., & Troumbis, A. Y. (1997). Aspects of heterogeneity in the distribution of diversity of the European herpetofauna, *18*(4), 393–412.
- Meltofte, H., Barry, T., Berteaux, D., Bültmann, H., Christiansen, J. S., Cook, J. A., ... Wrona, F. J. (2013). *Arctic Biodiversity Assessment. Synthesis*. Akureyri, Iceland: Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF).
- Mengerink, K. J., Dover, C. L. Van, Ardron, J., Baker, M., Escobar-briones, E., Gjerde, K., ... Levin, L. A. (2014). A Call for Deep-Ocean Stewardship. *Science*, *344*, 8–10. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1251458>
- Merunková, K., Preislerová, Z., & Chytrý, M. (2014). Environmental drivers of species composition and richness in dry grasslands of northern and central Bohemia, Czech Republic. *Tuexenia*, *34*(1), 447–466. <https://doi.org/10.14471/2014.34.017>
- Messenger, M. L., Lehner, B., Grill, G., Nedeva, I., & S. (2016). Estimating the volume and age of water stored in global lakes using a geo-statistical approach. *Nature Communications*, (7).
- Messenger, M. L., Lehner, B., Grill, G., Nedeva, I., & Schmitt, O. (2016). Estimating the volume and age of water stored in global lakes using a geo-statistical approach. *Nature Communications*, *7*, 13603. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13603>
- Meyer, S., Wesche, K., Krause, B., & Leuschner, C. (2013). Dramatic losses of specialist arable plants in Central Germany since the 1950s/60s - a cross-regional analysis. *Diversity and Distributions*, *19*(9), 1175–1187. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12102>
- Micheli, F., Halpern, B. S., Walbridge, S., Ciriaco, S., Ferretti, F., Fraschetti, S., ... Rosenberg, A. A. (2013). Cumulative Human Impacts on Mediterranean and Black Sea Marine Ecosystems: Assessing Current Pressures and Opportunities. *Plos One*, *8*(12), e79889. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0079889>
- Micklin, P. (2007). The Aral Sea Disaster. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, *35*(1), 47–72. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.earth.35.031306.140120>
- Mieszowska, N., Kendall, M. A., Hawkins, S. J., Leaper, R., & Williamson, P. (2006). Changes in the range of some common rocky shore species in Britania response to climate change. *Hydrobiologia*, *555*, 241.
- Mieszowska, N., Sugden, H., Firth, L. B., Hawkins, S. J., Southward, A., Frost, M., ... Stenford, G. (2014). The role of sustained observations in tracking impacts of environmental change on marine biodiversity and ecosystems. *Philosophical Transactions. Series A, Mathematical, Physical, and Engineering Sciences*, *372*(2025), 1–105. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2013.0339>
- Millaku, F., Rexhepi, F., Krasniqi, E., Pajazitaj, Q., Mala, X., & Berisha, N. (2013). *Libri i Kuq i Florës Vaskulare të Republikës së Kosovës*.
- Millenium Ecosystem Assessment. (2005). *Ecosystems and human well-being: synthesis*. Washington, DC. Retrieved from <http://www.unep.org/maweb/documents/document.354.aspx.pdf>

- Milner-Gulland, E. J., Kreuzberg-Mukhina, E., Grebot, B., Ling, S., Bykova, E., Abdusalamov, I., ... Stogova, L. (n.d.). Application of IUCN red listing criteria at the regional and national levels: a case study from Central Asia. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-005-4304-5>
- Milner-Gulland, E. J., & Singh, N. J. (2016). Two Decades of Saiga Antelope Research. In *Antelope Conservation* (pp. 297–314). Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118409572.ch15>
- Minayeva, T., & Sirin, A. (2009). Wetlands – Threatened Arctic Ecosystems: Vulnerability to Climate Change and Adaptation Options. In *Climate Change and Arctic Sustainable Development* (pp. 76–83). UNESCO.
- Minayeva, T., & Sirin, A. (2010). Arctic peatlands. In *Arctic Biodiversity Trends 2010 – Selected indicators of change* (pp. 71–74). Akureyri, Iceland: CAFF International Secretariat.
- Minayeva, T., Sirin, A., Kershaw, P., & Bragg, O. (2017). Arctic peatlands. In *The Wetland Book II: Distribution, Description and Conservation* (pp. 1–15). Springer Science+Business Media B.V. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6173-5_109-2
- Minayeva, T., Sirin, A., & Stracher, G. (2013). The peat fires of Russia. In G. Stracher (Ed.), *Coal and peat fires: A global perspective* (pp. 376–394). Amsterdam: Elsevier B.V.
- Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Russian Federation. (2015). *5th National Report Conservation of Biodiversity in the Russian Federation*.
- Mirzoyan, Z. A., Volovik, S. P., Martyniuk, M. L., [Мирзоян З.А., Воловик С.П., & Мартынюк М.Л.]. (2002). Развитие популяции *Beroe ovata* в Азово-Черноморском бассейне [Development of *Beroe ovata* populations in the Azov-Black Sea basin]. In *Основные проблемы рыбного хозяйства и охраны рыбохозяйственных водоемов Азово-Черноморского бассейна (2000-2001 гг.) [Main problems of fisheries and protection of fishery water bodies of the Azov-Black Sea basin]* (pp. 180–192). Rostov-on-Don: АзНИИРХ [AzNIIRKh].
- Mitrofanov, I. V., & Mamilov, N. S. (2015). Fish diversity and fisheries in the Caspian Sea and Aral–Syr Darya basin in the Republic of Kazakhstan at the beginning of the 21st Century. *Aquatic Ecosystem Health & Management*, 18(2), 160–170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14634988.2015.1028870>
- Moerland, W., De Baerdemaeker, A., Boesveld, A., Grutters, M. A. J., & Van de Poel, J. L. (2015). Rotterdam. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 453–494). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>
- Möllmann, C., Müller-Karulis, B., Diekmann, R., Flinkman, J., & Gårdmark, A. (2007). Ecosystem regime state in the Baltic Proper, Gulf of Riga, Gulf of Finland, and the Bothnian Sea. *HELCOM Indica-Tor Fact Sheet*.
- Molnár, Z., Biró, M., Bartha, S., & Fekete, G. (2012). Past Trends, Present State and Future Prospects of Hungarian Forest-Steppes. In *Eurasian steppes. Ecological problems and livelihoods in a changing world* (pp. 209–252). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-3886-7_7
- Möls, T., Vellak, K., Vellak, A., & Ingerpuu, N. (2013). Global gradients in moss and vascular plant diversity. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 22(6–7), 1537–1551. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-013-0492-6>
- Moning, C., & Müller, J. (2009). Critical forest age thresholds for the diversity of lichens, molluscs and birds in beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) dominated forests. *Ecological Indicators*, 9(5), 922–932.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2008.11.002>

- Montero-Serra, I., Edwards, M., & Genner, M. J. (2015). Warming shelf seas drive the subtropicalization of European pelagic fish communities. *Global Change Biology*, 21(1), 144–153. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12747>
- Montes, C., & Martino, P. (1987). Las lagunas salinas españolas. In *Bases Científicas para la protección de los humedales en España* (pp. 95–145). Madrid: Real Academia de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales de Madrid.
- Mooij, W. M., Janse, J. H., De Senerpont Domis, L. N., Hülsmann, S., & Ibelings, B. W. (2007). Predicting the effect of climate change on temperate shallow lakes with the ecosystem model PCLake. *Hydrobiologia*, 584(1), 443–454. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-007-0600-2>
- Moon, D. (2013). *The Plough that Broke the Steppes: Agriculture and Environment on Russias Grasslands, 1700-1914*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Retrieved from <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/the-plough-that-broke-the-steppes-9780199556434?cc=cz&lang=en&>
- Moore, S. E., & Huntington, H. P. (2008). ARCTIC MARINE MAMMALS AND CLIMATE CHANGE: IMPACTS AND RESILIENCE. *Ecological Applications*, 18(sp2), S157–S165. <https://doi.org/10.1890/06-0571.1>
- Morato, T., Watson, R., Pitcher, T. J., & Pauly, D. (2006). Fishing down the deep. *Fish and Fisheries*, 7(1), 24–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2006.00205.x>
- Moss, B. (2015). Biodiversity climate change impacts report card technical paper: Freshwaters, climate change and UK conservation. *Freshwater Ecology, Biodiversity Report Card Paper 17*, 1–63.
- Mouillot, D., Albouy, C., Guilhaumon, F., Ben Rais Lasram, F., Coll, M., Devictor, V., ... Mouquet, N. (2011). Protected and threatened components of fish biodiversity in the mediterranean sea. *Current Biology*, 21(12), 1044–1050. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2011.05.005>
- Mulec, J., & Kosi, G. (2009). Lampenflora algae and methods of growth control. *Journal of Cave and Karst Studies*, 71(2), 109–115.
- Müller, J., Klaus, V. H., Kleinebecker, T., Prati, D., Hölzel, N., & Fischer, M. (2012). Impact of land-use intensity and productivity on bryophyte diversity in agricultural grasslands. *PloS One*, 7(12), e51520. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0051520>
- Mullon, C., Steinmetz, F., Merino, G., Fernandes, J. A., Cheung, W. W. L., Butenschön, M., & Barange, M. (2016). Quantitative pathways for Northeast Atlantic fisheries based on climate, ecological–economic and governance modelling scenarios. *Ecological Modelling*, 320, 273–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2015.09.027>
- Muñoz-Fuentes, V., Vilà, C., Green, A. J., Negro, J. J., & Sorenson, M. D. (2007). Hybridization between white-headed ducks and introduced ruddy ducks in Spain. *Molecular Ecology*, 16(3), 629–638. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2006.03170.x>
- Murray, J. W., Top, Z., & Ozsoy, E. (1989). Hydrographic properties and ventilation of the Black Sea. *Deep Sea Resources*, 38(Suppl.1.2A.), S663–S691.
- Mustonen, T., & Helander, E. (2004). *Snowscapes, Dreamscapes - A Snowchange Community Book of Change*. Tampere Polytechnic.
- Namsaraev B.B. [Намсараев Б.Б.], Abidueva E.Y. [Абидуева Е.Ю.], & Lavrent'eva E.V. [Лаврентьева

- E.B.]. (2008). *Экология микроорганизмов экстремальных водных систем [Ecology of microorganisms in extreme aquatic systems]*. Ulan-Ude: Издательство Бурятского Государственного Университета [Publishing house of Buryat state University].
- NASA. (n.d.). Caspian Sea. Retrieved from <https://eoimages.gsfc.nasa.gov/images/imagerecords/66000/66761/CaspianSea.A2003162.0710.1km.jpg>
- NASA Earth Observatory. (2014). Revelation of Aral Sea disaster. Retrieved from <http://www.capitalwired.com/nasas-images-revelation-of-aral-sea-disaster/23259/>
- Nascimbene, J., Lazzaro, L., & Benesperi, R. (2015). Patterns of β -diversity and similarity reveal biotic homogenization of epiphytic lichen communities associated with the spread of black locust forests. *Fungal Ecology*, 14, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2014.10.006>
- Nascimbene, J., Nimis, P. L., & Ravera, S. (2013a). Evaluating the conservation status of epiphytic lichens of Italy: A red list. *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with All Aspects of Plant Biology*, 147(4), 898–904. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2012.748101>
- Nascimbene, J., Nimis, P. L., & Ravera, S. (2013b). Evaluating the conservation status of epiphytic lichens of Italy: A red list. *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with All Aspects of Plant Biology*, 147(4), 898–904. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2012.748101>
- Nascimbene, J., Thor, G., & Nimis, P. L. (2013). Effects of forest management on epiphytic lichens in temperate deciduous forests of Europe - A review. *Forest Ecology and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2013.03.008>
- Nash, T. H. (2008a). *Lichen Biology*. (T. H. Nash, Ed.) (Second). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Great Britain, New York, NY, USA and Melbourne, Australia 410 pp.
- Nash, T. H. (2008b). Lichen sensitivity to air pollution. In T. Nash (Ed.), *Lichen Biology* (2nd ed., pp. 301–316). Cambridge : Univ. Press. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511790478.016>
- Natcheva, R., Ganeva, A., & Spiridonov, G. (2006). Red List of the bryophytes in Bulgaria. *Phytologia Balcanica*, 12(1), 55–62.
- National Atlas of Russia. Chapter 2. (2000). Retrieved from <http://национальныйатлас.рф/cd2/index.html>
- Nesterova, D. A., Terenko, L. M., [Нестерова Д.А., & М.], Т. Л. (2009). Фитопланктон Каркинитского залива в сентябре 2008 г. [The Karkinit Bay phytoplankton in September 2008]. *Экологическая Безопасность Прибрежной И Шельфовой Зон Моря [Ecological Safety of Sea Coastal and Shelf Zones]*, (20), 293–300.
- Neumann, T. (2010). Climate change effects on the Baltic Sea ecosystem: a model study, (2006), 1–16.
- Newbold, T., Hudson, L. N., Hill, S. L. L., Contu, S., Lysenko, I., Senior, R. A., ... Purvis, A. (2015). Global effects of land use on local terrestrial biodiversity. *Nature*, 520(7545), 45–50. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14324>
- Nicastro, K. R., Zardi, G. I., Teixeira, S., Neiva, J., Serrao, E. A., & Pearson, G. A. (2013). Shift happens: trailing edge contraction associated with recent warming trends threatens a distinct genetic lineage in the marine macroalga *Fucus vesiculosus*. *BMC Biology*, 11, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7007-11-6>

- Nicolaev S., Alexandrov L., Boicenco L., Coatu V., Diaconeasa D., Dumitrache C., Dumitrescu O., Golumbeanu, L. Lazar, V. Malciu, R. Mateescu, V. Maximov, D. Micu, E. Mihailov, M. Nenciu M., Nita V., Oros A., Spinu A., Stoica E., Tabarcea C., Timofte F., T, Z. T. (2013). Report on the state of marine and coastal environment in 2013. *Recherches Marines*, 43, 5–138.
- Niemelä, J., & Kotze, D. J. (2009). Carabid beetle assemblages along urban to rural gradients: A review. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 92(2), 65–71.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2009.05.016>
- Nieto, A., & Alexander, K. N. a. (2010). *European Red List of Saproxyllic Beetles. IUCN Species Programme*. <https://doi.org/10.2779/84561>
- Nieto, A., Ralph, G. M., Comeros-Raynal, M. T., Kemp, J., García Criado, M., Allen, D. J., ... Williams, J. T. (2015). *European Red List of marine fishes*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/082723>
- Niklfeld, H. (1999). *Rote Listen gefährdeter Pflanzen Österreichs*.
- Nikolsky, G. V. (1938). *Fishes of Tajikistan*. Moscow-Leningrad: Academy of Science of the USSR.
- Nikolsky, G. V. (1971). *Special Ichthyology*. Moscow: Vysshaya Shkola.
- Nissenbaum, A. (1975). The Microbiology and Biogeochemistry of the Dead Sea. *Microbial Ecology*, 2(2), 139–161.
- Nogués-Bravo, D., Araújo, M. B., Errea, M. P., & Martínez-Rica, J. P. (2007). Exposure of global mountain systems to climate warming during the 21st Century. *Global Environmental Change*, 17(3–4), 420–428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2006.11.007>
- Nordén, B., Dahlberg, A., Brandrud, T. E., Fritz, Ö., Ejrnaes, R., & Ovaskainen, O. (2014). Effects of ecological continuity on species richness and composition in forests and woodlands: A review. *Écoscience*, 21(1), 34–45. <https://doi.org/10.2980/21-1-3667>
- Norkko, A., Laakkonen, T., & Laine, A. (2007). *Trends in soft-sediment macrozoobenthic communities in the open sea areas of the Baltic Sea*.
- Norse, E. A., Brooke, S., Cheung, W. W. L., Clark, M. R., Ekeland, I., Froese, R., ... Watson, R. (2012). Sustainability of deep-sea fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 36(2), 307–320.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2011.06.008>
- Nowak, A., & Nowak, S. (2015). Distribution patterns of segetal weeds of cereal crops in tajikistan. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 47(4), 1415–1422.
- Nowak, A., Nowak, S., & Nobis, M. (2011). Distribution patterns, ecological characteristic and conservation status of endemic plants of Tadzhikistan - A global hotspot of diversity. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 19(5), 296–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2011.05.003>
- Nowak, A., Nowak, S., Nobis, M., & Nobis, A. (2014). A report on the conservation status of segetal weeds in Tajikistan. *Weed Research*, 54(6), 635–648. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wre.12103>
- Ogus, T. (Ed.). (2008). The state of marine living resources. In *State of the Environment of the Black Sea (2001-2006/7)* (pp. 321–364). Istanbul, Turkey: Commission on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (BSC).
- Ojaveer, H., Jaanus, A., Mackenzie, B. R., Martin, G., Olenin, S., Radziejewska, T., ... Zaiko, A. (2010). Status of biodiversity in the Baltic sea. *PLoS ONE*, 5(9), 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012467>

- Ojaveer, H., Olenin, S., Narščius, A., Florin, A.-B., Ezhova, E., Gollasch, S., ... Stråke, S. (2016). Dynamics of biological invasions and pathways over time : a case study of a temperate coastal sea. *Biological Invasions*, 19(3), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1316-x>
- Olivier L. and al. (1995). *Livre rouge de la flore menacée de France I espèces prioritaires*. Paris: MNHN.
- Oltean M. and al. (1994). *Lista rosie a plantelor superioare din România Red List of Higher Plants of Romania*. Bucurest: Academia Romana Institutul de Biologie.
- Oren, A. (2006). Life at high salt concentrations. In *The Prokaryotes* (pp. 263–282). New York: Springer New York.
- Orgiazzi, A., Bardgett, R.D., Barrios, E., Behan-Pelletier, V., Briones, M. J. I., Chotte, J-L., De Deyn, G.B., Eggleton, P., Fierer, N., Fraser, T., H., K., Jeffery, S., Johnson, N.C., Jones, A., Kandeler, E., Kaneko, N., L., P., Lemanceau, P., Miko, L., Montanarella, L., Moreira, F.M.S., R., K.S., Scheu, S., Singh, B.K., Six, J., van der Putten, W.H., Wall, D. H., & (Eds.). (2016). *Global Soil biodiversity atlas*. <https://doi.org/doi:10.2788/799182>
- Orlandi, S., Probo, M., Sitzia, T., Trentanovi, G., Garbarino, M., Lombardi, G., & Lonati, M. (2016). Environmental and land use determinants of grassland patch diversity in the western and eastern Alps under agro-pastoral abandonment. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(2), 275–293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1046-5>
- Orlova, T. Y., Konovalova, G. V, Stonik, I. V, Selina, M. S., Tatyana, V., & Shevchenko, O. G. (2002). Harmful algal blooms on the eastern coast of Russia. In *Harmful algal blooms in the PICES region of the North Pacific. PICES Report 23 (August 2002)*. PICES. Retrieved from https://www.pices.int/publications/scientific_reports/Report23/default.aspx
- Orlov A.A. [Орлов А.А.], Chechevishnikov A.L. [Чечевичников А.Л.], Alekseenkova E.S. [Алексеенкова Е.С.], Vorishpolets K.P. [Боришполец К.П.], Krylov A.V. [Крылов А.В.], Kudeneeva Yu.S. [Куденеева Ю. С.], ... Chernyavskii S.I. [Чернявский С.И.]. (2011). *Проблема пресной воды. Глобальный контекст политики России [Problem of fresh water. Global context of Russian politics]*. Moscow: МГИМО-Университет [MGIMO-University].
- Örmeci, C., & Ekercin, S. (2005). Water quality monitoring using satellite image data: a case study around the Salt Lake in Turkey. In *Proc. SPIE 5977, Remote Sensing of the Ocean, Sea Ice, and Large Water Regions 2005, 59770K (October 20, 2005)*. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.628558>
- OSPAR. (2008). *Case Reports for the OSPAR List of threatened and/or declining species and habitats. Biodiversity Series*. OSPAR Commission.
- OSPAR. (2010). *Quality Status Report 2010*. London: OSPAR Commission.
- OSPAR. (2017a). Intermediate Assessment 2017. Retrieved October 7, 2017, from <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/intermediate-assessment-2017>
- OSPAR. (2017b). Intermediate Assessment 2017. Retrieved July 6, 2017, from <https://oap.ospar.org/en/ospar-assessments/intermediate-assessment-2017>
- Österblom, H., Hansson, S., Larsson, U., Hjerne, O., Wulff, F., Elmgren, R., & Folke, C. (2007). Human-induced trophic cascades and ecological regime shifts in the baltic sea. *Ecosystems*, 10(6), 877–889. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-007-9069-0>
- Otero, M.M., Numa, C., Bo, M., Orejas, C., Garrabou, J., Cerrano, C., KružičÁL, P., Antoniadou, C., Aguilar, R., Kipson, S., Linares, C., Terr.n-Sigler, A., Brossard, J., Kersting, D., Casado-Amez.a, P., Garc.a, S., Goffredo, S., Oca.a, O., Caroselli, E., B. (2017). *Overview of the conservation status of Mediterranean anthozoans*. Malaga, Spain.

- Oug, E., Cochrane, S. K. J., Sundet, J. H., Norling, K., & Nilsson, H. C. (2011). Effects of the invasive red king crab (*Paralithodes camtschaticus*) on soft-bottom fauna in Varangerfjorden, northern Norway. *Marine Biodiversity*, 41(3), 467–479. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-010-0068-6>
- Overland, J. E., & Stabeno, P. J. (2004). Is the climate of the Bering Sea warming and affecting the ecosystem? *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union*, 85(33), 309. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004EO330001>
- Pabi, S., van Dijken, G. L., & Arrigo, K. R. (2008). Primary production in the Arctic Ocean, 1998–2006. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 113(8), C08005. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JC004578>
- Pacifici, M., Foden, W. B., Visconti, P., Watson, J. E. M., Butchart, S. H. M., Kovacs, K. M., ... Rondinini, C. (2015). Assessing species vulnerability to climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(February), 215–225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2448>
- Paillet, Y., Bergès, L., Hjältén, J., Ódor, P., Avon, C., Bernhardt-Römermann, M., ... Virtanen, R. (2010). Biodiversity differences between managed and unmanaged forests: Meta-analysis of species richness in Europe. *Conservation Biology*, 24(1), 101–112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2009.01399.x>
- Pajunen, A. M., Oksanen, J., & Virtanen, R. (2011). Impact of shrub canopies on understorey vegetation in western Eurasian tundra. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 22(5), 837–846. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01285.x>
- Palmer, A. N. (1991). Origin and morphology of limestone caves. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*. [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1991\)103<0001:OAMOLC>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1991)103<0001:OAMOLC>2.3.CO;2)
- Pape, T., Bickel, D., & Meier, R. (2009). *Diptera Diversity: Status, Challenges and Tools*. Leiden, Boston: Brill.
- Parfenov V.I. and al. (1987). *Rare and Threatened Plant Species of Byelorussia and Lithuania*. Minsk: Nauka i Tekhnica.
- Parmesan, C. (2006). Ecological and Evolutionary Responses to Recent Climate Change. *Annual of Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, 37(1), 637–669. <https://doi.org/10.2307/annurev.ecolsys.37.091305.30000024>
- Parnikoza, I., & Vasiluk, A. (2011). Ukrainian steppes: current state and perspectives for protection. *Annales Universitatis Mariae Curie-Skłodowska. Sectio C. Biologia*, 9(1), 23–37. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10067-011-0018-0>
- Pärtel, M., Bruun, H. H., & Sammuli, M. (2005). Biodiversity in temperate European grasslands: origin and conservation. In *Grassland Science in Europe* (Vol. 10, pp. 1–14). Retrieved from <http://lup.lub.lu.se/record/532202/file/625284.pdf>
- Pauchard, A., Kueffer, C., Dietz, H., Daehler, C. C., Alexander, J., Edwards, P. J., ... Seipel, T. (2009). Ain't no mountain high enough: Plant invasions reaching new elevations. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 7(9), 479–486. <https://doi.org/10.1890/080072>
- Pauli, H., Gottfried, M., Dullinger, S., Abdaladze, O., Akhalkatsi, M., Alonso, J. L. B., ... Grabherr, G. (2012). Recent Plant Diversity Changes on Europe's Mountain Summits. *Science*, 336(6079), 353–355. [https://doi.org/DOI 10.1126/science.1219033](https://doi.org/DOI%2010.1126/science.1219033)
- Pavlov V. A., S. J. H. (2011). Snow crab. In T. Jakobsen & V. K. Ozhigin (Eds.), *The Barents Sea : ecosystem, resources, management : half a century of Russian-Norwegian cooperation* (pp. 168–172). Trondheim: Tapir Academic Press. Retrieved from

<https://brage.bibsys.no/xmlui/handle/11250/109444>

- Pavlovskaya, L. P. (1995). Fishery in the lower Amu-Darya under the impact of irrigated agriculture. Retrieved September 20, 2017, from <http://www.fao.org/docrep/V9529E/v9529E04.htm>
- PBL. (2014). *How sectors can contribute to sustainable use and conservation of biodiversity*. Montreal: Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. Montreal. Technical Series 79.
- PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency. (n.d.). Roads from Rio + 20.
- Pe'er, G., Arlettaz, R., Báldi, A., Benton, T. G., Collins, S., Dieterich, M., ... Scott, a V. (2014). EU agricultural reform fails on biodiversity. *Science*, *344*(6188), 1090–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1253425>
- Peay, K. G., Kennedy, P. G., & Talbot, J. M. (2016). Dimensions of biodiversity in the Earth mycobiome. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, *14*(7), 434–447. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro.2016.59>
- Peeler, E. J., Oidtmann, B. C., Midtlyng, P. J., Miossec, L., & Gozlan, R. E. (2011). Non-native aquatic animals introductions have driven disease emergence in Europe. *Biological Invasions*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-010-9890-9>
- Pekel, J.-F., Cottam, A., Gorelick, N., & Belward, A. S. (2016). High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes. *Nature*, (540), 418–422. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20584>
- Pekel, J.-F., Cottam, A., Gorelick, N., & Belward, A. S. (2016). High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20584>
- Pellissier, L., Anzini, M., Maiorano, L., Dubuis, A., Pottier, J., Vittoz, P., & Guisan, A. (2013). Spatial predictions of land-use transitions and associated threats to biodiversity: The case of forest regrowth in mountain grasslands. *Applied Vegetation Science*, *16*(2), 227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-109X.2012.01215.x>
- Pereira, H. M., Leadley, P. W., Proença, V., Alkemade, R., Scharlemann, J. P. W., Fernandez-Manjarrés, J. F., ... Walpole, M. (2010). Scenarios for global biodiversity in the 21st century. *Science*, *330*(6010), 1496–501. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1196624>
- Pérez-Ruzafa, A., García-Charton, J. A., & Marcos, C. (2017). North East Atlantic vs . Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas as Fisheries Management Tool, *4*(August), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00245>
- Pérez-Ruzafa, Á., González-Wangüemert, M., Lenfant, P., Marcos, C., & García-Charton, J. A. (2006). Effects of fishing protection on the genetic structure of fish populations. *Biological Conservation*, *129*(2), 244–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.10.040>
- Pérez-Ruzafa, A., & Marcos, C. (2012). Fisheries in coastal lagoons: An assumed but poorly researched aspect of the ecology and functioning of coastal lagoons. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, *110*, 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2012.05.025>
- Pérez-Ruzafa, A., Marcos, C., & Pérez-Ruzafa, I. M. (2011). Mediterranean coastal lagoons in an ecosystem and aquatic resources management context. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth*, *36*(5–6). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2010.04.013>
- Peringer, A., Siehoff, S., Chételat, J., Spiegelberger, T., Buttler, A., & Gillet, F. (2013). Past and future landscape dynamics in pasture-woodlands of the Swiss Jura Mountains under climate change. *Ecology and Society*, *18*(3), 11. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05600-180311>

- Perry, A. L., Low, P. J., Ellis, J. R., & Reynolds, J. D. (2005). Climate change and distribution shifts in marine fishes. *Science*, *308*(5730), 1912–5. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1111322>
- Peskova, T. J. (2000). Polovaja struktura populjatsij zemnoovodnikh pri obitanii v chistikh i zagrjaznennikh pestitsidami vodoemakh (Sex-ratio structure of the amphibians inhabiting pure and pesticide-polluted reservoirs). *Modern Herpetology (Collected Proceedings)*, *1*, 26–35.
- Petersen, S., Krätschell, A., Augustin, N., Jamieson, J., Hein, J. R., & Hannington, M. D. (2016). News from the seabed – Geological characteristics and resource potential of deep-sea mineral resources. *Marine Policy*, *70*, 175–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2016.03.012>
- Petitpierre, B., MacDougall, K., Seipel, T., Broennimann, O., Guisan, A., & Kueffer, C. (2015). Will climate change increase the risk of plant invasions into mountains? *Ecological Applications*, *26*(2), 150709023716008. <https://doi.org/10.1890/14-1871.1>
- Petr, T., Ismukhanov, K., Kamilov, B., Pulakhton, D., & Umarov, P. D. (2004). Irrigation systems and their fisheries in the Aral Sea Basin, central Asia. In T. Welcomme, R., Petr (Ed.) (RAP Public). Bangkok: FAO Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/docrep/007/ad526e/ad526e00.htm>
- Pettersson, R. B., Ball, J. P., Renhorn, K. E., Esseen, P. A., & Sjöberg, K. (1995). Invertebrate communities in boreal forest canopies as influenced by forestry and lichens with implications for passerine birds. *Biological Conservation*, *74*(1), 57–63. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(95\)00015-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(95)00015-V)
- Pham, C. K., Diogo, H., Menezes, G., Porteiro, F., Braga-Henriques, A., Vandepierre, F., & Morato, T. (n.d.). Deep-water longline fishing has reduced impact on Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems, *4*, 4837. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/srep04837>
- Pham, C. K., Ramirez-Llodra, E., Alt, C. H. S., Amaro, T., Bergmann, M., Canals, M., ... Tyler, P. A. (2014). Marine Litter Distribution and Density in European Seas, from the Shelves to Deep Basins. *PLoS ONE*, *9*(4), e95839. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0095839>
- Phitos D. and al. (1995). *The Red Data Book of Rare and Threatened Plants of Greece*. Athens.
- PHOENIX, G. K., EMMETT, B. A., BRITTON, A. J., CAPORN, S. J. M., DISE, N. B., HELLIWELL, R., ... POWER, S. A. (2012). Impacts of atmospheric nitrogen deposition: responses of multiple plant and soil parameters across contrasting ecosystems in long-term field experiments. *Global Change Biology*, *18*(4), 1197–1215.
- Piano, E., De Wolf, K., Bona, F., Bonte, D., Bowler, D. E., Isaia, M., ... Hendrickx, F. (2017). Urbanization drives community shifts towards thermophilic and dispersive species at local and landscape scales. *Global Change Biology*, *23*(7), 2554–2564. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13606>
- Plotnikov I.S. [Плотников И.С.]. (2016). *Многолетние изменения фауны свободноживущих водных беспозвоночных Аральского моря [Multiyear changes of fauna of aquatic invertebrates of the Aral Sea]*. Saint-Petersburg: ЗИИ РАН [ZIN RAN].
- Poloczanska, E. S., Brown, C. J., Sydeman, W. J., Kiessling, W., Schoeman, D. S., Moore, P. J., ... Richardson, A. J. (2013). Global imprint of climate change on marine life. *Nature Climate Change*, *3*(August), 919–925. <https://doi.org/10.1038/Nclimate1958>
- Poloczanska, E. S., Burrows, M. T., Brown, C. J., Molinos, J. G., Halpern, B. S., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., ... Sydeman, W. J. (2016). Responses of marine organisms to climate change across oceans. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, *3*(MAY). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00062>
- Prather, C. M., Pelini, S. L., Laws, A., Rivest, E., Woltz, M., Bloch, C. P., ... Joern, A. (2013).

- Invertebrates, ecosystem services and climate change. *Biological Reviews*, 88(2), 327–348.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12002>
- Prishchepov, A. A., Müller, D., Dubinin, M., Baumann, M., & Radeloff, V. C. (2013). Determinants of agricultural land abandonment in post-Soviet European Russia. *Land Use Policy*, 30(1), 873–884.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.06.011>
- Procházka F. and al. (2000). *Cerný a červený seznam cévnatých rostlin České republiky Black and Red lists of Vascular Plants of the Czech Republic*. Praha: Příroda.
- Prop, J., Aars, J., Bårdsen, B.-J., Hanssen, S. A., Bech, C., Bourgeon, S., ... Moe, B. (2015). Climate change and the increasing impact of polar bears on bird populations. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 3, 33. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2015.00033>
- Puig, P., Canals, M., Company, J. B., Martín, J., Amblas, D., Lastras, G., ... Calafat, A. M. (2012). Ploughing the deep sea floor. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11410>
- Purvis, O. W. (2015). Lichens on *Betula* in the Ural Mountains; relationships with bark acidity and element concentrations as indicators of geology and anthropogenic influences. *British Lichen Society Bulletin*, 117, 15–28.
- Purvis, O. W., Tittley, I., Chimonides, P. D. J., Bamber, R., Hayes, P. A., James, P. W., ... Read, H. (2010). Long-term biomonitoring of lichen and bryophyte biodiversity at Burnham Beeches SAC and global environmental change. *Systematics and Biodiversity*, 8(2), 193–208.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14772001003782088>
- Pyšek, P., Křivánek, M., & Jarošík, V. (2009). Planting intensity, residence time, and species traits determine invasion success of alien woody species. *Ecology*, 90(10), 2734–2744.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/08-0857.1>
- Quaas, M. F., Reusch, T. B. H., Schmidt, J. O., Tahvonen, O., & Voss, R. (2016). It is the economy, stupid! Projecting the fate of fish populations using ecological-economic modeling. *Global Change Biology*, 22(1), 264–270. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13060>
- Rabalais, N. N., Díaz, R. J., Levin, L. A., Turner, R. E., Gilbert, D., & Zhang, J. (2010). Dynamics and distribution of natural and human-caused hypoxia. *Biogeosciences*, 7, 585–619. Retrieved from www.biogeosciences.net/7/585/2010/
- Rachkovskaya, E. I., & Bragina, T. M. (2012). Steppes of Kazakhstan: Diversity and Present State. In M. A. van S. Marinus J.A. Werger (Ed.), *Eurasian Steppes. Ecological Problems and Livelihoods in a Changing World* (pp. 103–148). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-3886-7_3
- Radu, G., & Anton, E. (2014). Impact of turbot fishery on cetaceans in the Romanian Black Sea area. *Scientia Marina*, 78(S1), 103–109. <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04029.27A>
- Rakonczay, Z. (1989). *Red Data Book on Mosses, Vascular Plants and Animals (Invertebrates and Vertebrates)*. Budapest: Vörös Könyv. Akadémiai Kiado.
- Ram, D., Axelsson, A.-L., Green, M., Smith, H. G., & Lindström, Å. (2017). What drives current population trends in forest birds – forest quantity, quality or climate? A large-scale analysis from northern Europe. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 385, 177–188.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2016.11.013>
- Ramirez-Llodra, E., Tyler, P. A., Baker, M. C., Bergstad, O. A., Clark, M. R., Escobar, E., ... Van Dover, C. L. (2011). Man and the Last Great Wilderness: Human Impact on the Deep Sea. *PLoS ONE*, 6(8), e22588. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0022588>

- Ramos-Espla AA, Bitar G., Khalaf G, El Shaer H, Forcada A, Limam A, Ocaña O, Sghaier YR, V. C. (2014). *Ecological characterization of sites of interest for conservation in Lebanon: Enfeh Peninsula, Ras Chekaa cliffs, Raoucheh, Saida, Tyre And Nakoura*. Tunis.
- Ramsar. (n.d.). Ramsar Sites Information Service. Retrieved from <https://rsis.ramsar.org/>
- Randi, E. (2008). Detecting hybridization between wild species and their domesticated relatives. *Molecular Ecology*, 17(1), 285–293. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2007.03417.x>
- Randin, C. F., Engler, R., Normand, S., Zappa, M., Zimmermann, N. E., Pearman, P. B., ... Guisan, A. (2009). Climate change and plant distribution: Local models predict high-elevation persistence. *Global Change Biology*, 15(6), 1557–1569. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2008.01766.x>
- Randlane, T., Juriado, I., Suija, A., Lohmus, P., & Leppik, E. (2008). Lichens in the new Red List of Estonia. *Folia Cryptog. Estonica, Fasc*, 44(January), 113–120.
- Rangwala, I., Sinsky, E., & Miller, J. R. (2013). Amplified warming projections for high altitude regions of the northern hemisphere mid-latitudes from CMIP5 models. *Environmental Research Letters*, 8(2), 24040. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/8/2/024040>
- Rassi, P., Hyvärinen, E., Juslén, A., & Mannerkoski, I. (2010). *The 2010 Red List of Finnish Species*. Ympäristöministeriö & Suomen ympäristökeskus. Helsinki, Finland.
- Raybaud, V., Beaugrand, G., Dewarumez, J. M., & Luczak, C. (2014). Climate-induced range shifts of the American jackknife clam *Ensis directus* in Europe. *Biological Invasions*, 17(2), 725–741. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-014-0764-4>
- Reading Luiselli, L.M., Akani, G.C., Bonnet, X., Amori, G., Ballouard, J.M., Filippi, E., Naulleau, G., Pearson, D., Rugiero, L., C. J. (2010). Are snake populations in widespread decline? *Biology Letters*, 6, 777–780.
- Reif, J., Voříšek, P., Štátný, K., Bejček, V., & Petr, J. (2008). Agricultural intensification and farmland birds: New insights from a central European country. *Ibis*, 150(3), 596–605. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2008.00829.x>
- Reinecke, J., Klemm, G., & Heinken, T. (2014). Vegetation change and homogenization of species composition in temperate nutrient deficient Scots pine forests after 45 yr. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 25(1), 113–121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvs.12069>
- Renaud, P. E., Sejr, M. K., Bluhm, B. A., Sirenko, B., & Ellingsen, I. H. (2015). The future of Arctic benthos: Expansion, invasion, and biodiversity. *Progress in Oceanography*, 139, 244–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2015.07.007>
- Republic of Turkey. (2014). *Republic of Turkey. Ministry of Forestry And Water Affairs. UN Convention on Biological Diversity. Fifth National Report. August 2014*.
- Rhymer, J. M., & Simberloff, D. (1996). Extinction By Hybridization and Introgression. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 27(1), 83–109. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.27.1.83>
- Rice, J., Arvanitidis, C., Boicenco, L., Kasapidis, P., Mahon, R., Malone, T., ... Van Gaever, S. (2016). North Atlantic Ocean, Chapter 36A. In *World Ocean Assessment*.
- Richardson, D. M., & Pysek, P. (2006). Plant invasions: merging the concepts of species invasiveness and community invasibility. *Progress in Physical Geography*, 30(3), 409–431. <https://doi.org/10.1191/0309133306pp490pr>
- Richner, N., Holderegger, R., Linder, H. P., & Walter, T. (2015). Reviewing change in the arable flora of Europe: A meta-analysis. *Weed Research*, 55(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wre.12123>

- Rigling, D., Hilfiker, S., Schöbel, C., Meier, F., Engesser, R., Scheidegger, C., ... Queloz, V. (2016). Das Eschentriebsterben Biologie, Krankheitssymptome und Handlungsempfehlungen. *Merkblatt Für Die Praxis*, 57, 1–8. Retrieved from www.wsl.ch/publikationen
- Rintelen, T., & Van Damme, D. (2011). *Dreissena caspia*. Retrieved from <http://www.iucnredlist.org/details/full/188971/0>
- Roberge, J. M., Lämås, T., Lundmark, T., Ranius, T., Felton, A., & Nordin, A. (2015). Relative contributions of set-asides and tree retention to the long-term availability of key forest biodiversity structures at the landscape scale. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 154, 284–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.02.040>
- Robinson, R., & Sutherland, W. (2002). Post-war changes in arable farming and biodiversity in Great Britain . J Appl Ecol Post-war changes in arable farming and biodiversity in Great Britain. *Journal of Applied E*, 39(May), 157–176. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2664.2002.00695.x>
- Rogers, A. D., Tyler, P. A., Connelly, D. P., Copley, J. T., James, R., Larter, R. D., ... Zwirgmaier, K. (2012). The Discovery of New Deep-Sea Hydrothermal Vent Communities in the Southern Ocean and Implications for Biogeography. *PLoS Biology*, 10(1), e1001234. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001234>
- Roll Feldman, A., Novosolov, M., Allison, A., Bauer, A.M., Bernard, R., Böhm, M., Castro-Herrera, F., Chirio, L., Collen, B., Colli, G.R., Dabool, L., Das, I., Doan, T.M., Grismer, L.L., Hoogmoed, M., Itescu, Y., Kraus, F., LeBreton, M., Lewin, A., Marti, U. (2017). The global distribution of tetrapods reveals a need for targeted reptile conservation. . *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, in press.
- Rondinini, C., & Visconti, P. (2015). Scenarios of large mammal loss in Europe for the 21st century. *Conservation Biology*, 29(4), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12532>
- Rönkkönen, S., Ojaveer, E., Raid, T., & Viitasalo, M. (2004). Long-term changes in Baltic herring (*Clupea harengus membras*) growth in the Gulf of Finland. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 61(2), 219–229. <https://doi.org/10.1139/f03-167>
- Roques, A., Rabitsch, W., Rasplus, J., Lopez-Vaamonde, C., Nentwig, W., & Kenis, M. (2009). Alien terrestrial invertebrates of Europe. In P. Hulme, W. Nentwig, P. Pyšek, & M. Vilà (Eds.), *DAISIE, The Handbook of Alien Species in Europe* (pp. 63–79). Heidelberg: Springer.
- Rose, F. (1992). Temperate forest management: its effect on bryophyte and lichen floras and habitats. In A. Bates, J.W., Farmer (Ed.), *Bryophytes and lichens in a changing environment* (pp. 211–233). Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Roshydromet. (2014). *Second Assessment Report on climate change and their impact on the territory of the Russian Federation (in Russian)*. Moscow. Retrieved from <http://voeikovmgo.ru/download/2014/od/od2.pdf>
- Roué, M., & Molnár, Z. (2016). Indigenous and Local Knowledge of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Europe and Central Asia. *Knowledges of Nature. UNESCO: Paris.*, (9), 156.
- Ruas, S., Bergamini, A., Carvalho, P., Fontinha, S., & Sim-sim, M. (2015). The community structure of bryophytes and macrolichens in Madeira’s natural forest: the effects of environmental variables and relations to old-growth forests. *Nova Hedwigia*, 100(3), 439–460. <https://doi.org/10.1127/nova>
- Ruiz-Labourdette, D., Nogués-Bravo, D., Ollero, H. S., Schmitz, M. F., & Pineda, F. D. (2012). Forest composition in Mediterranean mountains is projected to shift along the entire elevational gradient under climate change. *Journal of Biogeography*, 39(1), 162–176.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2011.02592.x>

- Russell, D. J. F., Wanless, S., Collingham, Y. C., Huntley, B., & Hamer, K. C. (2015). Predicting future European breeding distributions of British seabird species under climate change and unlimited/no dispersal scenarios. *Diversity*, 7(4), 342–359. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d7040342>
- Russian Forest Protection Centre [Российского центра защиты леса]. (n.d.). Огнёвка самшитовая - 3 года на Российском Кавказе [The box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*) - 3 years in the Russian Caucasus]. Retrieved December 8, 2016, from http://rcfh.ru/23_09_2014_de743.html
- Russian Government. (2013). Стратегия развития Арктической зоны Российской Федерации и обеспечения национальной безопасности на период до 2020 года [Strategy of the Arctic zone of the Russian Federation development and national security for the period up to 2020]. Russian Government. Retrieved from <http://government.ru/info/18360/>
- Russian Steppe Conservation Strategy: NGOs position*. (2006). Moscow (in Russian).
- Sabovljevit, M., Ganeva, A., Tsakiri, E., & Stefanut, S. (2001). Bryology and bryophyte protection in south-eastern Europe. *Biological Conservation*, 101(1), 73–84. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(01\)00043-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(01)00043-X)
- Sadikov, K., Abdurahmanov, A., Bekmirzaeva, I., Yunusov, N., Grigoryants, A., Goncharov, G., ... Tsaruk, O. (2015). *Fifth national report of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Conservation of Biodiversity*. UNDP. Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/uz/uz-nr-05-en.pdf>
- Sahlén, G., Bernard, R., A., C. R., Ketelaar, R., & Suhling, F. (2004). Critical species of Odonata in Europe. *International Journal of Odonatology*, 7, 385–398.
- Sala, E., Kizilkaya, Z., Yildirim, D., & Ballesteros, E. (2011). Alien marine fishes deplete algal biomass in the Eastern Mediterranean. *PLoS ONE*, 6(2), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0017356>
- Saltankin, V. P. (2012). *Russian Water Reservoirs* (pp. 691–697). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4410-6_250
- Saltré, F., Duputié, A., Gaucherel, C., & Chuine, I. (2015). How climate, migration ability and habitat fragmentation affect the projected future distribution of European beech. *Global Change Biology*, 21(2), 897–910. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12771>
- Sandrea, R., & Sandrea, I. (2010). Deepwater crude oil output: How large will the uptick be? *Oil and Gas Journal*, 108(41), 48–53. Retrieved from http://uq.summon.serialssolutions.com/2.0.0/link/0/eLvHCXMwnV1Lj9MwEB4hTiCk8m54SD7AMRA_mjRcKISo-gNAiJMV25PVaqMmbRN1f_7OpE0pZVdacbYPccb-_M145hsArT4l8RkmFKbwmcGco_y0axSiD9rjJCUmdaqvGTsNfwyqEAdrDyDZI3eoPQfNP0-J2k8ycsNnzTrmLL82npoqcGQPM35nGa_fv8BZpPuJTR1wtJ7
- Sandström, P., Cory, N., Svensson, J., Hedenås, H., Jougda, L., & Borchert, N. (2016). On the decline of ground lichen forests in the Swedish boreal landscape: Implications for reindeer husbandry and sustainable forest management. *Ambio*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-015-0759-0>
- Santini, A., Ghelardini, L., De Pace, C., Desprez-Loustau, M. L., Capretti, P., Chandelier, A., ... Stenlid, J. (2013). Biogeographical patterns and determinants of invasion by forest pathogens in Europe. *New Phytologist*, 197(1), 238–250. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2012.04364.x>
- Sauer, J., Sami, @bullet, @bullet, D., Nowak, C., Haase, P., Sauer, J., ... Haase, Á. P. (2011). Low mountain ranges: summit traps for montane freshwater species under climate change. *Biodivers Conserv*, 20, 3133–3146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-0140-y>

- Savvaitova, K. A., & Petr, T. (1999). Fish and fisheries in Lake Issyk-Kul (Tien Shan), River Chu and Pamir Lakes. In *Fish and Fisheries at Higher Altitudes: Asia* (pp. 168–187). FAO.
- Scheidegger, C., Bilovitz, P. O., Werth, S., Widmer, I., & Mayrhofer, H. (2012). Hitchhiking with forests: Population genetics of the epiphytic lichen *Lobaria pulmonaria* in primeval and managed forests in southeastern Europe. *Ecology and Evolution*, *2*(9), 2223–2240. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.341>
- Scheidegger, C., & Clerc, P. (2002). *Rote Liste der gefährdeten Arten der Schweiz: Baum- und erdbewohnende Flechten*. Bern: Bundesamt für Umwelt, Wald und Landschaft BUWAL, Bern, und Eidgenössische Forschungsanstalt WSL, Birmensdorf, und Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de la Ville de Genève CJBG.
- Scheidegger, C., & Werth, S. (2009). Conservation strategies for lichens: insights from population biology. *Fungal Biology Reviews*, *23*(3), 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbr.2009.10.003>
- Scheidegger, C., Wolseley, P. A., & Thor, G. (1995). Conservation Biology of Lichenised Fungi. *MITTEILUNGEN Der Eidgenössischen Forschungsanstalt Für Wald, Schnee Und Landschaft*, *70*(1).
- Scherrer, D., & Körner, C. (2011). Topographically controlled thermal-habitat differentiation buffers alpine plant diversity against climate warming. *Journal of Biogeography*, *38*(2), 406–416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2010.02407.x>
- Schmidt, N. M., Ims, R. A., Høye, T. T., Gilg, O., Hansen, L. H., Hansen, J., ... Sittler, B. (2012). Response of arctic predator guilds to collapsing lemming cycles. *Proceedings of the Royal Society*, *279*, 4417–4422.
- Schneider-Binder, E. (2007). Xerophilous and xero-mesophilous grasslands on slumping hills around the Saxon villages Apold and Saschiz (Transylvania, Romania). *Transylvanian Review of Systematical and Ecological Research*, *4*, 55–64. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/00559c262e577f36a9987e28a286449e/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=54813>
- Scholefield, P., Firbank, L., Butler, S., Norris, K., Jones, L. M., & Petit, S. (2011). Modelling the European Farmland Bird Indicator in response to forecast land-use change in Europe. *Ecological Indicators*, *11*(1), 46–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.09.008>
- Schustov, M. (2015). ЛИШАЙНИКИ В КРАСНЫХ КНИГАХ УЛЬЯНОВСКОЙ И САМАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТЕЙ (Red List of lichens in the Uliyanovsk and the Samara region).
- Schwarz, U. (2012). Hydropower Projects in Protected Areas on the Balkans, 1–34.
- Schwörer, C., Henne, P. D., & Tinner, W. (2014). A model-data comparison of Holocene timberline changes in the Swiss Alps reveals past and future drivers of mountain forest dynamics. *Global Change Biology*, *20*(5), 1512–1526. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12456>
- Sciberras, M., Jenkins, S. R., Mant, R., Kaiser, M. J., Hawkins, S. J., & Pullin, A. S. (2015). Evaluating the relative conservation value of fully and partially protected marine areas. *Fish and Fisheries*, *16*(1), 58–77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12044>
- Seaward, M. (2008). Environmental role of lichens. In Nash TH III (Ed.), *Lichen Biology* (2nd ed., pp. 274–298). Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press.
- Šebesta, J., Šamonil, P., Lacina, J., Oulehle, F., Houška, J., & Buček, A. (2011). Acidification of primeval forests in the Ukraine Carpathians: Vegetation and soil changes over six decades. *Forest Ecology and Management*, *262*(7), 1265–1279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2011.06.024>

- Sedelnikova, N. V. (1988). Lichens. In *Red Book of Novosibirsk Oblast: Plants* (pp. 123–129). Novosibirsk: Nauka.
- Seebens, H., Blackburn, T. M., Dyer, E. E., Genovesi, P., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., ... Essl, F. (2017). No saturation in the accumulation of alien species worldwide. *Nature Communications*, 8, 14435.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14435><http://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms14435#supplementary-information>
- ŠeffEROVÁ StanOVÁ, V., ŠeffER, J., & Janák, M. (2008). *Management of Natura 2000 habitats 7230 Alkaline fens*.
- Segerstråle, S. G. (1957). Baltic sea. *Geological Society of America Memoirs*, 67, 751–800.
- Şekerçiođlu, Ç. H., Anderson, S., Akçay, E., Bilgin, R., Can, Ö. E., Semiz, G., ... Nüzhet Dalfes, H. (2011). Turkey's globally important biodiversity in crisis. *Biological Conservation*, 144(12), 2752–2769.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2011.06.025>
- Senn-irlet, B., Heilmann-Clausen, J., Genney, D., & Dahlberg, A. (2007). Guidance for Conservation of Macrofungi in Europe. *Document Prepared for the European Council for Conservation of Fungi (ECCF) within the European Mycological Association (EMA) and the Directorate of Culture and Cultural and Natural Heritage, Council of Europe, Strasbourg*, (October).
- Serussiaux, E. (1989). *Liste rouge des Macrilichens dans la communaute Europeenne*. Liège, Belgium. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/2268/138066>
- Sheldon, R. D., Kamp, J., Koshkin, M., Urazaliev, R., Iskakov, T., Field, R., ... Donald, P. F. (2013). Breeding ecology of the globally threatened Sociable Lapwing *Vanellus gregarius* and the demographic drivers of recent declines. *Journal of Ornithology*, 154, 501–516.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-012-0921-4>
- Shelyak-Sosonka, Y. R. (1996). *Chervona Kniga Ukrainy - Roslinnyy Svit Red Data Book of Ukraine - Plant Kingdom*. Kiev: Ukrainskaya Enciklopedia.
- Shevchenko, V. V., & Datsky, A. V. (2014). *Биоэкономика использования промысловых ресурсов минтая Северной Пацифики [Bioeconomics of Alaska Pollack fishery resources using in North Pacific]*. Moscow: Изд-во ВНИРО [Publishing House VNIRO].
- Shiganova, T. A., & [Шиганова Т.А.]. (2000). Некоторые итоги изучения биологии вселенца *M. leidyi* (A. Agassiz) в Черном море [Some results of studying the biology of the invader *M. leidyi* (A. Agassiz) in the Black Sea]. In S. P. Volovik (Ed.), *Гребневик Mnemiopsis leidyi* (A. Agassiz) в Азовском и Черном морях и последствия его вселения [Ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* (A. Agassiz) in the Azov and Black seas and the consequences of its invasion] (pp. 33–75). Rostov-on-Don.
- Shiganova, T. A., Bulgakova, Y. V., Sorokin, P. Y., & Lukashev, Y. F. (2000). Investigation of a new settler *Beroe ovata* in the Black Sea. *Biology Bulletin*, 27(2), 202–209.
- Shuman, J. K., & Shugart, H. H. (2009). Evaluating the sensitivity of Eurasian forest biomass to climate change using a dynamic vegetation model. *Environmental Research Letters*, 4(4), 45024.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/4/4/045024>
- Shuntov, V. P., & Temnykh, O. S. (2013). Иллюзии и реалии экосистемного подхода к изучению и управлению морскими и океаническими биологическими ресурсами [Illusions and realities of the ecosystem approach to the study and management of marine and oceanic biological resources]. *Известия ТИНРО [Izvestiya TINRO]*, 173, 3–29.

- Shurin, J. B., Winder, M., Adrian, R., Keller, W. B., Matthews, B., Paterson, A. M., ... Yan, N. D. (2010). Environmental stability and lake zooplankton diversity - contrasting effects of chemical and thermal variability. *Ecology Letters*, 13(4), 453–463. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01438.x>
- Shustov, M. (Main B. G. named after N. V. T. R. (2015). The lichens in the Red Books of Ulyanovsk and Samara Oblasts (ЛИШАЙНИКИ В КРАСНЫХ КНИГАХ УЛЬЯНОВСКОЙ И САМАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТЕЙ). *Proceedings of the Samara Scientific Center, Russian Academy of Sciences (Известия Самарского Научного Центра Российской Академии Наук)*, 17(6), 322–325.
- Siedentop, S., & Fina, S. (2012). Who Sprawls Most? Exploring the Patterns of Urban Growth across 26 European Countries. *Environment and Planning A*, 44(11), 2765–2784. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a4580>
- Silic, C. (1996). *Spisak biljnih vrsta (Pteridophyta i Spermatophyta) za crvenu knjigu Bosne i Hercegovine*.
- Sillero Campos, J., Bonardi, A., Corti, C., Creemers, R., Crochet, P.-A., Crnobrnja-Isailovic, J., Denoël, M., Ficetola, G.F., Gonçalves, J., Kuzmin, S., Lymerakis, P., de Pous, P., Rodríguez, A., Sindaco, R., Speybroeck, J., Toxopeus, B., Vieites, D.R., N. (2014). Updated distribution and biogeography of amphibians and reptiles of Europe. *Amphibia-Reptilia*, 35, 1–31.
- Silva, J., Toland, J., Jones, W., Elridge, J., Thorpe, E., Campbell, M., & O’Hara, E. (2008). *LIFE and endangered plants. Conserving Europe’s threatened flora. European Union*. <https://doi.org/10.2779/99297>
- Simpson, M., & Prots, B. (2013). Predicting the distribution of invasive plants in the Ukrainian Carpathians under climatic change and intensification of anthropogenic disturbances: implications for biodiversity conservation. *Environmental Conservation*, 40(2), 167–181. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s037689291200032x>
- Singh, G., Dal Grande, F., Werth, S., & Scheidegger, C. (2015). Long-term consequences of disturbances on reproductive strategies of the rare epiphytic lichen *Lobaria pulmonaria*: Clonality a gift and a curse. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiu009>
- Sirenko, B. I., & Gagaev, S. Y. (2007). Unusual abundance of macrobenthos and biological invasions in the Chukchi Sea. *Russian Journal of Marine Biology*, 33(6), 355–364. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063074007060016>
- Sirenko B.I. (2009). The present state of investigations of the Chukchi Sea fauna. In Sirenko B.I. (Ed.), *Ecosystems and biological resources of the Chukchi Sea and adjacent areas. Explorations of the Fauna of the Sea* (in Russian, pp. 5–27). Zoological Institute of RAS. Retrieved from <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/2010GL045059>
- Sirkkä, S., Lindén, A., Helle, P., Nikula, A., Knape, J., & Lindén, H. (2010). Are the declining trends in forest grouse populations due to changes in the forest age structure? A case study of Capercaillie in Finland. *Biological Conservation*, 143(6), 1540–1548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.03.038>
- Sket, B. (1999). The nature of biodiversity in hypogean waters and how it is endangered. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 8(10), 1319–1338. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1023/A:1008916601121>
- Sket, B. (2005). Dinaric karst, diversity in. In D. C. White, W. B. & Culver (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Caves* ((2nd Editi, pp. 158–165). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Sket, B. (2012). Diversity patterns in Dinaric karst. In William B. White David C. Culver (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Caves* (2 nd, pp. 228–238). Academic Press.

- Sket, B., Paragamian, K., & Trontelj, P. (2004). A census of obligate subterranean fauna of the Balkan Peninsula. In Ian Griffiths; Boris Kryštufek; Jane M Reed (Ed.), *Balkan biodiversity : pattern and process in the European hotspot* (pp. 309–323). Dordrecht ; Boston ; London : Kluwer Academic.
- Skorka, P., Lenda, M., & Tryjanowski, P. (2010). Invasive alien goldenrods negatively affect grassland bird communities in Eastern Europe. *Biological Conservation*, *143*(4), 856–861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2009.12.030>
- Slingenberg, A., Braat, L., Windt, H. Van Der, Rademaekers, K., Eichler, L., & Turner, K. (2009). Study on understanding the causes of biodiversity loss and the policy assessment framework, (October), 1–206.
- Smale, D. A., Burrows, M. T., Moore, P., O'Connor, N., & Hawkins, S. J. (2013). Threats and knowledge gaps for ecosystem services provided by kelp forests: A northeast Atlantic perspective. *Ecology and Evolution*, *3*(11), 4016–4038. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.774>
- Smaliychuk, A., Müller, D., Prishchepov, A. V., Levers, C., Kruhlov, I., & Kuemmerle, T. (2016). Recultivation of abandoned agricultural lands in Ukraine: Patterns and drivers. *Global Environmental Change*, *38*, 70–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.02.009>
- Smelansky, I. E. (2003). *Biodiversity of agricultural lands in Russia: current state and trends*. Moscow.
- Smelansky, I. E., & Tishkov, A. A. (2012). The Steppe Biome in Russia: Ecosystem Services, Conservation Status, and Actual Challenges. In *Eurasian steppes: ecological problems and livelihoods in a changing world* (Vol. 6, pp. 45–101). Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-3886-7>
- Smelansky, I., & Simonov, E. (2008). Temperate grassland region: Russian steppes. In B. Peart (Ed.), *Compendium of Regional Templates on the Status of Temperate Grasslands Conservation and Protection* (pp. 87–99). Vancouver, Canada: IUCN World Commission on Protected Areas.
- Smith, G. F., Gittings, T., Wilson, M., French, L., Oxbrough, A., O'Donoghue, S., ... Giller, P. (2008). Identifying practical indicators of biodiversity for stand-level management of plantation forests. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, *17*(5), 991–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-007-9274-3>
- Snickars, M., Weigel, B., & Bonsdorff, E. (2015). Impact of eutrophication and climate change on fish and zoobenthos in coastal waters of the Baltic Sea. *Marine Biology*, *162*(1), 141–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-014-2579-3>
- Socher, S. A., Prati, D., Boch, S., Müller, J., Klaus, V. H., Hölzel, N., & Fischer, M. (2012). Direct and productivity-mediated indirect effects of fertilization, mowing and grazing on grassland species richness. *Journal of Ecology*, *100*(6), 1391–1399. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2012.02020.x>
- Sokolov, V. E., & [Соколов В.Е.]. (1986). *Редкие и исчезающие животные. Млекопитающие [Rare and endangered animals. Mammals]*. Moscow: Высшая школа [High School].
- Sokos, C. K., Birtsas, P. K., Connelly, J. W., & Pappaspyropoulos, K. G. (2013). Hunting of migratory birds: disturbance intolerant or harvest tolerant? *Wildlife Biology*, *19*(2), 113–125. <https://doi.org/10.2981/12-032>
- Soliveres, S., Manning, P., Prati, D., Gossner, M. M., Alt, F., Arndt, H., ... Allan, E. (2016). Locally rare species influence grassland ecosystem multifunctionality. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *371*(1694). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0269>
- Soliveres, S., van der Plas, F., Manning, P., Prati, D., Gossner, M. M., Renner, S. C., ... Allan, E. (2016). Biodiversity at multiple trophic levels is needed for ecosystem multifunctionality. *Nature*,

536(7617), 456–459. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature19092>

Soós, Á., Papp, L., & Oosterbroek, P. (1992). *Catalogue of palaearctic diptera vol 1*. Budapest: Hungarian Natural History Museum.

Sorokin, Y. I. (2002). *Black Sea Ecology and Oceanography*. Leiden: Backhuys Publishers.

Sorokovikova, L. M., Popovskaya, G. I., Tomberg, I. V., Sinyukovich, V. N., Kravchenko, O. S., Marinaite, I. I., ... Khodzher, T. V. (2013). The Selenga River water quality on the border with Mongolia at the beginning of the 21st century. *Russian Meteorology and Hydrology*, 38(2), 126–133. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1068373913020106>

Soto, C. G. (2001). The potential impacts of global climate change on marine protected areas. *Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries*, 11(3), 181–195. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1020364409616>

Spalding, M. D., Fox, H. E., Allen, G. R., Davidson, N., Ferdaña, Z. A., Finlayson, M., ... Robertson, J. (2007). Marine Ecoregions of the World: A Bioregionalization of Coastal and Shelf Areas. *BioScience*, 57(7), 573. <https://doi.org/10.1641/B570707>

Sparrius, L. B., & Kooijman, A. M. (2011). Invasiveness of *Campylopus introflexus* in drift sands depends on nitrogen deposition and soil organic matter. *Applied Vegetation Science*, 14(2), 221–229. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-109X.2010.01120.x>

Št'astný, K., Červený, J., Řezáč, M., Kurka, A., Veselý, P., Kadlec, T., ... Marhoul, P. (2015). Prague. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 379–451). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>

Št'astný, K., Červený, J., Rom, J., Solský, M., Hanel, L., Andreska, J., ... Kerouš, K. (2015). Prague. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 119–153). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>

Stelmakh, L. V., Mansurova, I. M., [Стельмах Л.В., & Мансурова И.М.]. (2012). Эколого-физиологические основы биоразнообразия фитопланктона Черного моря [Ecological and physiological basis of phytoplankton biodiversity in the Black Sea]. *Экосистемы [Ecosystems]*, (7), 149–158.

Stendera, S., Adrian, R., Bonada, N., Cañedo-Argüelles, M., Hugueny, B., Januschke, K., ... Hering, D. (2012). Drivers and stressors of freshwater biodiversity patterns across different ecosystems and scales: A review. *Hydrobiologia*, 696(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-012-1183-0>

Stenger-Kovács, C., Lengyel, E., Buczkó, K., Tóth, F., Crossetti, L., Pellingner, A., ... Padisák, J. (2014). Vanishing world: alkaline, saline lakes in Central Europe and their diatom assemblages. *Inland Waters*, (4(4)), 383–396.

Steppe fires and fire management in steppe protected areas: environmental and conservation aspects. Analytical survey. (2015). Moscow: BCC Press.

STOA. (2013). *Technology options for feeding 10 billion people - Interactions between climate change & agriculture and between biodiversity & agriculture* (Vol. 1). <https://doi.org/10.2861/43440>

Stoate, C., Baldi, A., Beja, P., Boatman, N. D., Herzon, I., van Doorn, A., ... Ramwell, C. (2009). Ecological impacts of early 21st century agricultural change in Europe - A review. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 91(1), 22–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.07.005>

- Stoate, C., Boatman, N. D., Borralho, R. J., Carvalho, C. R., de Snoo, G. R., & Eden, P. (2001). Ecological impacts of arable intensification in Europe. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 63(4), 337–365. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jema.2001.0473>
- Stöcklin, J., Bosshard, A., Klaus, G., Rudmann-Maurer, K., & Fischer, M. (2007). *Landnutzung und biologische Vielfalt in den Alpen – Fakten, Perspektiven, Empfehlungen*. vdf Verlag, Zürich.
- Stofer, S., Bergamini, A., Aragón, G., Carvalho, P., Coppins, B. J., Davey, S., ... Scheidegger, C. (2006). Species richness of lichen functional groups in relation to land use intensity. *The Lichenologist*, 38(4), 331. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0024282906006207>
- Stokland, J. N., Siitonen, J., & Jonsson, B. G. (2012). *Biodiversity in deadwood*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139025843>
- Stone, R. (2008). A New Great Lake or Dead Sea? *Science*, 320(5879), 1002–1005.
- Strayer, D. L., & Dudgeon, D. (2010). Freshwater biodiversity conservation: recent progress and future challenges. *Journal of the North American Benthological Society*, 29(1), 344–358. <https://doi.org/10.1899/08-171.1>
- Stuart-Smith, S. J., & Jepson, P. D. (2017). Persistent threats need persistent counteraction: Responding to PCB pollution in marine mammals. *Marine Policy*, 84(December 2016), 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.06.033>
- Sugar, I. (1994). *Crvena knjiga biljnih vrstva Republike Hrvatske Red List of Plant Species of Croatia*. Zagreb: Ministarstvo graditeljstva i zaštite okoliša, Zavod za zaštitu prirode.
- Svendsen, L. M., Pyhälä, M., Gustafsson, B., Sonesten, L., & Knuuttila, S. (2015). *Inputs of nitrogen and phosphorus to the Baltic Sea. HELCOM core indicator report*.
- Svetasheva, T. (2017). Fungal conservation in Russia: an update. In *Fungal Conservation in a Changing Europe*. Ohrid, Republic of Macedonia.
- Svetasheva, T. 2015. (2015). *Armillaria ectypa*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2015: e.T75097245A75098379, 8235. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2015-%0A4.RLTS.T75097245A75098379.en%0A%0A>
- Symon, C., Arris, L., & Heal, B. (2005). *The Arctic: geography, climate, ecology and people*. Arctic Climate Impact Assessment. Cambridge. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.ru/scholar?q=Symon+C.%2C+Arris+L.+%26+Heal+B.+%282005%29.+&btnG=&hl=ru&as_sdt=0%2C5
- Synnes, M. (2007). Bioprospecting of organisms from the deep sea: scientific and environmental aspects. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 9(1), 53–59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-006-0062-7>
- Szabó, P. (2013). The end of common uses and traditional management in a Central European wood. In *Cultural Severance and the Environment: The Ending of Traditional and Customary Practice on Commons and Landscapes Managed in Common* (pp. 205–213). Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6159-9>
- Takala, T., Kouki, J., & Tahvanainen, T. (2014). Bryophytes and their microhabitats in coniferous forest pastures: should they be considered in the pasture management? *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 23(12), 3127–3142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-014-0769-4>
- Takala, T., Tahvanainen, T., & Kouki, J. (2012). Can re-establishment of cattle grazing restore bryophyte diversity in abandoned mesic semi-natural grasslands? *Biodiversity and Conservation*,

21(4), 981–992. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-012-0234-1>

- Taskavak Atatür, M.K., Ghaffari, H., Meylan, P.A., E. (2016). *Rafetus euphraticus* (Daudin 1801) – Euphrates Softshell Turtle. . (A. G. J. Rhodin Iverson, J.B., van Dijk, P.P., Saumure, R.A., Buhlmann, K.A., Pritchard, P.C.H. Mittermeier, R.A., Ed.), *Conservation Biology of Freshwater Turtles and Tortoises: A Compilation Project of the IUCN/SSC Tortoise and Freshwater Turtle Specialist Group. Chelonian Research Monographs* 5.
- Taylor, M. L., & Roterman, C. N. (2017). Invertebrate population genetics across Earth’s largest habitat: The deep-sea floor. *Molecular Ecology*, (March), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.14237>
- Temple, H. J., & Cox, N. A. (2009). *European red list of amphibians*. (Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, Ed.).
- Terlizzi, A., Fellingine, S., Lionetto, M. G., Caricato, R., Perfetti, V., Cutignano, A., & Mollo, E. (2011). Detrimental physiological effects of the invasive alga *Caulerpa racemosa* on the mediterranean white seabream *Diplodus sargus*. *Aquatic Biology*, 12(2), 109–117. <https://doi.org/10.3354/ab00330>
- Thackeray, S. J., Sparks, T. H., Frederiksen, M., Burthe, S., Bacon, P. J., Bell, J. R., ... Wanless, S. (2010). Trophic level asynchrony in rates of phenological change for marine, freshwater and terrestrial environments. *Global Change Biology*, 16(12), 3304–3313. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02165.x>
- The Russian Academy of Sciences. (2014). The second international conference "Lichenology in Russia: Problems and perspectives". (M. P. Andreev, D. E. Himelbrant, E. S. Kuznetsova, & I. S. Stepanchikova, Eds.). ST. PETERSBURG.
- Theurillat, J. P., & Guisan, A. (2001). Potential impact of climate change on vegetation in the European alps: A review. *Climatic Change*, 50(1–2), 77–109. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010632015572>
- Thomas, J. A., Simcox, D. J., & Clarke, R. T. (2008). Successful Conservation of a Threatened *Maculinea* Butterfly, 877(1992).
- Thomas, Y., Pouvreau, S., Alunno-Bruscia, M., Barillé, L., Gohin, F., Bryère, P., & Gernez, P. (2016). Global change and climate-driven invasion of the Pacific oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*) along European coasts: A bioenergetics modelling approach. *Journal of Biogeography*, 43(3), 568–579. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12665>
- Thorpe, A., Whitmarsh, D., Drakeford, B., Reid, C., Karimov, B., Timirkhanov, S., ... Van Anrooy, R. (2011a). *Feasibility of stocking and culture-based fisheries in Central Asia. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture*.
- Thorpe, A., Whitmarsh, D., Drakeford, B., Reid, C., Karimov, B., Timirkhanov, S., ... Van Anrooy, R. (2011b). *Feasibility of stocking and culture-based fisheries in Central Asia. FAO fisheries and aquaculture technical paper. No. 565*.
- Thuiller, W., Guéguen, M., Georges, D., Bonet, R., Chalmandrier, L., Garraud, L., ... Lavergne, S. (2014). Are different facets of plant diversity well protected against climate and land cover changes? A test study in the French Alps. *Ecography*, 37(12), 1254–1266. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.00670>
- Thuiller, W., Lavergne, S., Roquet, C., Boulangeat, I., Lafourcade, B., & Araujo, M. (2011). Consequences of climate change on the tree of life in Europe. *Nature*, 470(7335), 531–534. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1038/nature09705>

- Thuiller, W., Lavorel, S., Araujo, M. B., Sykes, M. T., & Prentice, I. C. (2005). Climate change threats to plant diversity in Europe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102(23), 8245–8250. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0409902102>
- Thurber, A. R., Sweetman, A. K., Narayanaswamy, B. E., Jones, D. O. B., Ingels, J., & Hansman, R. L. (n.d.). Ecosystem function and services provided by the deep sea, 11(14), 3941–3963. Retrieved from http://www.biogeosciences.net/11/3941/2014/bg-11-3941-2014.html?utm_source=Daily+Carbon+Briefing&utm_campaign=cc97676163-DAILY_BRIEFING&utm_medium=email&utm_term=0_876aab4fd7-cc97676163-303435821
- Timdal, E. (2015). Lav ('Lichenes'). Norsk rødliste for arter 2015. Retrieved January 17, 2017, from <http://www.artsdatabanken.no/Rodliste/Artsgruppene/Lav>
- Tingstad, L., Gjerde, I., Dahlberg, A., & Grytnes, J. A. (2017). The influence of spatial scales on Red List composition: Forest species in Fennoscandia. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 11, 247–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2017.07.005>
- Tishkov, A. A. (2005). Managing conservation of the biota and ecosystems in the steppe zone. *Issues of Steppe Science*, (6), 47–58.
- Tishkov A.A. [Тишков А.А.]. (2009). *Fourth National Report "Biodiversity Conservation in the Russian Federation ["Четвертый национальный доклад «Сохранение биоразнообразия в Российской Федерации»]*. Moscow: Ministry of Natural Resources of Russian Federation, UNDP.
- Tockner, K., Robinson, C. & Uehlinger, U. (2008). *Rivers of Europe*. Elsevier Ltd, London.
- Tockner, K., Pusch, M., Gessner, J., & Wolter, C. (2011). Domesticated ecosystems and novel communities: challenges for the management of large rivers. *Ecohydrology & Hydrobiology*, 11(3–4), 167–174. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10104-011-0045-0>
- Tokarev, Y., & Shulman, G. (2007). Biodiversity in the Black Sea: effects of climate and anthropogenic factors. *Hydrobiologia*, 580(1), 23–33.
- Török, P., Ambarlı, D., Kamp, J., Wesche, K., & Dengler, J. (2016). Step(pe) up! Raising the profile of the Palearctic natural grasslands. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(12), 2187–2195.
- Tosun, M. S. (2011). Demographic Divide and Labor Migration in the Euro-Mediterranean Region. *Population (English Edition)*, (6188).
- Tóth-Ronkay, M., Bajor, Z., Bárány, A., Földvári, G., Görföl, T., Halpern, B., ... Vörös, J. (2015). Budapest. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 27–73). New York: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>
- Trewick, S. (2017). Plate Tectonics in Biogeography. *International Encyclopedia of Geography: People, the Earth, Environment and Technology*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118786352.wbieg0638>
- Trivedi, M. R., Berry, P. M., Morecroft, M. D., & Dawson, T. P. (2008). Spatial scale affects bioclimate model projections of climate change impacts on mountain plants. *Global Change Biology*, 14(5), 1089–1103. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2008.01553.x>
- Trontelj, P., Douady, C. J., Fišer, C., Gibert, J., Gorički, Š., Lefébure, T., ... Zakšek, V. (2009). A molecular test for cryptic diversity in ground water: How large are the ranges of macrostygobionts? *Freshwater Biology*, 54(4), 727–744. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2007.01877.x>

- Trontelj, P., & Zakšek, V. (2016). Genetic monitoring of iProteus/i populations. *Natura Sloveniae*, 18(1), 53–54.
- Tsikliras, A. C., Dinouli, A., Tsiros, V.-Z., & Tsalkou, E. (2015). The Mediterranean and Black Sea fisheries at risk from overexploitation. *PLoS One*, 10(3), e0121188. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0121188>
- Tuniyev, B. S. (1990). On the Independence of the Colchis Center of Amphibian and Reptile Speciation. *Asiatic Herpetological Research*, 3, 67–84.
- Tuniyev, B. S. (1995). On the Mediterranean influence on the formation of herpetofauna of the Caucasian Isthmus and its main xerophylous refugia. *Russian Journal of Herpetology*, 2, 95–119.
- Tuniyev, B. S. (1997). About exact borders of the Colchis biogeographical Province. *Russian Journal of Herpetology*, 4, 182–185.
- Tuniyev, B. S. (2012). First consequences of climate variation and use of Natural Resources in the Biota of the West Caucasus [In Russian]. *Global Environmental Processes. Moscow*, 438–443.
- Tuniyev, B. S. (2016). Rare species of shield-head vipers in the Caucasus. *Nature Conservation Research*, 1, 11–25.
- Tuniyev, Ananjeva, N.B., Agasyan, A., Orlov, N.L., Tuniyev, S., B. (2009). *Eremias pleskei*. (errata version published in 2017) . *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 2009*, e.T164583A114550294. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2009.RLTS.T164583A5910262.en>
- Turdakov, F. A. (1963). *Fishes of Kirghizia*. Frunze: Izdat: AN KirgizSSR.
- Türk, R., & Hafellner, J. (1999). Flechten. Rote Liste gefährdeter Flechten (Lichenes) Österreichs. In H. NIKLFELD (Ed.), *Rote Listen gefährdeter Pflanzen Österreichs* (pp. 187–228). Grüne Reihe des Bundesministeriums für Umwelt, Jugend und Familie.
- Turkmenistan Fifth National Report to CBD*. (2015). Ashgabat.
- Uetz, P. (2017). The Reptile Database. Retrieved from <http://www.reptile-database.org>
- Ulicsni, V., Svanberg, I., & Molnár, Z. (2016). Folk knowledge of invertebrates in Central Europe - folk taxonomy, nomenclature, medicinal and other uses, folklore, and nature conservation. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 12(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13002-016-0118-7>
- UNESCO. (2009). Global Open Oceans and Deep Seabed (GOODS) - biogeographic classification. *IOC Technical Series*, 84(April), 84. Retrieved from <http://www.citeulike.org/user/LNCScatalogo/article/10352567?updated=1336273165&rejected=>
- United Nations. (2016). *World Ocean Assessment*. New York NY, USA.
- Väinölä, R., Witt, J. D. S., Grabowski, M., Bradbury, J. H., Jazdzewski, K., & Sket, B. (2008). Global diversity of amphipods (Amphipoda; Crustacea) in freshwater. *Hydrobiologia*, 595(1), 241–255. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-007-9020-6>
- Valkó, O., Deák, B., Török, P., Kelemen, A., Migléc, T., Tóth, K., & Tóthmérész, B. (2016). Abandonment of croplands: problem or chance for grassland restoration? Case studies from Hungary. *Ecosystem Health and Sustainability*, 2(2), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ehs2.1208>
- Van Cauwenberghe, L., Vanreusel, A., Mees, J., & Janssen, C. R. (2013). Microplastic pollution in deep-sea sediments. *Environmental Pollution*, 182, 495–499.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2013.08.013>

- Van de Poel, J. L., De Baerdmaeker, A., Bakker, G., Moerland, W., & De Zwarte, N. (2015). Rotterdam. In J. Kelcey (Ed.), *Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna* (pp. 155–178). New York: Springer Science+Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6>
- van de Wouw, M., van Hintum, T., Kik, C., van Treuren, R., & Visser, B. (2010). Genetic diversity trends in twentieth century crop cultivars: A meta analysis. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*, *120*(6), 1241–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-009-1252-6>
- van der Plas, F., Manning, P., Soliveres, S., Allan, E., Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Verheyen, K., ... Fischer, M. (2016a). Biotic homogenization can decrease landscape-scale forest multifunctionality. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *113*(13), 201517903. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517903113>
- van der Plas, F., Manning, P., Soliveres, S., Allan, E., Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Verheyen, K., ... Fischer, M. (2016b). Biotic homogenization can decrease landscape-scale forest multifunctionality. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *113*(13), 3557–62. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517903113>
- Van Der Wal, R., Pearce, I. S. K., & Brooker, R. W. (2005). Mosses and the struggle for light in a nitrogen-polluted world. *Oecologia*, *142*(2), 159–168. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-004-1706-0>
- Van Dover, C. L., Ardron, J. A., Escobar, E., Gianni, M., Gjerde, K. M., Jaeckel, A., ... Weaver, P. P. E. (2017). Biodiversity loss from deep-sea mining. *Nature Geoscience*, *10*(7), 464–465. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2983>
- van Herk, C. M. (2001). Bark pH and susceptibility to toxic air pollutants as independent causes of changes in epiphytic lichen composition in space and time. *Lichenologist*, *33*(5), 419–441. <https://doi.org/10.1006/lich.2001.0337>
- Van Swaay, C., Cuttelod, A., Collins, S., Maes, D., Munguira, M. L., Šašić, M., ... Wynhoff, I. (2010). *European Red List of Butterflies*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/doi:10.2779/83897>
- van Swaay, C., & et al. (2015). *The European Butterfly Indicator for Grassland species: 1990-2013. October*.
- Van Swaay, C., Van Strien, a, & Harpke, a. (2013). *The European Grassland Butterfly Indicator: 1990–2011. EEA Technical* European Environment Agency. <https://doi.org/10.2800/89760>
- Vanderpoorten, A., Engels, P., & Sotiaux, A. (2004). Trends in diversity and abundance of obligate epiphytic bryophytes in a highly managed landscape. *Ecography*, *27*(5), 567–576. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0906-7590.2004.03890.x>
- Vangjeli, J., Ruci, B., & Mullaj, A. (1995). *Libri i Kuq*.
- Vangjeli, J., Ruci, P., & Hoda, P. (1997). *Shoqerimet bimore, in Libri i Kuq (Bime, Shoqerime bimore dhe kafshe te Rrezikuara)*.
- Vanhatalo, J., Vetemaa, M., Herrero, A., Aho, T., & Tiilikainen, R. (2014). By-catch of grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) in Baltic fisheries - a Bayesian analysis of interview survey. *PloS One*, *9*(11), e113836. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0113836>
- Vanreusel, A., Hilario, A., Ribeiro, P. A., Menot, L., & Arbizu, P. M. (2016). Threatened by mining,

- polymetallic nodules are required to preserve abyssal epifauna. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 26808. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep26808>
- Vasilakopoulos, P., Maravelias, C. D., & Tserpes, G. (2014). The alarming decline of mediterranean fish stocks. *Current Biology*, 24(14), 1643–1648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2014.05.070>
- Vasiluk, A. V., Parnikoza, I. Y., & Shevchenko, M. S. (2010). Biodiversity of steppes under protection of Red Book and Green Book of Ukraine. *Steppe Bulletin*, 29, 33–36 (in Russian).
- Velchev V. and al. (1984). *Red Data Book of the People's Republic of Bulgaria. Volume 1. Plants*. Sofia: Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.
- Venn, S., Schulman, H., TÖrrÖnen, S., Salla, A., Pajunen, T., Kerppola, S., ... Karjalainen, S. (2015). *Helsinki. Vertebrates and Invertebrates of European Cities: Selected Non-Avian Fauna*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1698-6_10
- Ventosa, A., & Arahall, D. R. (2009). Physico-chemical characteristics of hypersaline environments and their biodiversity. In *Extremophiles* (pp. 247–262). Oxford: EOLSS.
- Verboom, J., Alkemade, R., Klijn, J., Metzger, M. J., & Reijnen, R. (2007). Combining biodiversity modeling with political and economic development scenarios for 25 EU countries. *Ecological Economics*. Retrieved from [wos:000246655500008](https://www.wos.com/wos/000246655500008)
- Vergés, A., Tomas, F., Cebrian, E., Ballesteros, E., Kizilkaya, Z., Dendrinis, P., ... Sala, E. (2014). Tropical rabbitfish and the deforestation of a warming temperate sea. *Journal of Ecology*, 102(6), 1518–1527. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12324>
- Verheyen, K., Baeten, L., De Frenne, P., Bernhardt-Römermann, M., Brunet, J., Cornelis, J., ... Verstraeten, G. (2012). Driving factors behind the eutrophication signal in understory plant communities of deciduous temperate forests. *Journal of Ecology*, 100(2), 352–365. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2011.01928.x>
- Vershinin, A., & [Вершинин А.]. (2003). *Жизнь Черного Моря [The Life of the Black Sea]*. Moscow: MacCentr.
- Vershinin, A., & [Вершинин А.]. (2016). *Живое Черное Море [The Living Black Sea]*. Moscow: Ковчег [Kovcheg].
- Vershinin, V. L., Vershinina, S. D., Berzin, D. L., & Zmeeva, D. V. (2015). Long-term observation of amphibian populations inhabiting urban and forested areas in Yekatarinburg, Russia. *Scientific Data*, 2, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.18>
- Vetrov, A. A., & Romankevich, E. A. (2011). Primary production and fluxes of organic carbon to the seabed in the Russian Arctic seas as a response to the recent warming. *Oceanology*, 51(2), 255–266. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0001437011020196>
- Vězda, A. (1983). Foliicole Flechten aus der Kolchis (West-Transkaukasien, UdSSR). *Folia Geobotanica & Phytotaxonomica*, 18(1), 45–70.
- Vickery, J. A., Ewing, S. R., Smith, K. W., Pain, D. J., Bairlein, F., Škorpilová, J., & Gregory, R. D. (2014). The decline of Afro-Palaeartic migrants and an assessment of potential causes. *Ibis*, 156(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.12118>
- Vilà, M., & Hulme, P. E. (2017). *Impact of Biological Invasions on Ecosystem Services*.
- Vilkov, E. V. (2013). Population Trends in Regular Migrants As the Basis for a Prediction Model for Conservation of the Birds of Eurasia. *Russian Journal of Ecology*, 44(2), 142–157. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S106741361301013X>

- Villéger, S., Grenouillet, G., & Brosse, S. (2014). Functional homogenization exceeds taxonomic homogenization among European fish assemblages, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12226>
- Villnäs, A., Norkko, J., Lukkari, K., Hewitt, J., & Norkko, A. (2012). Consequences of increasing hypoxic disturbance on benthic communities and ecosystem functioning. *PLoS ONE*, *7*(10), e44920. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0044920>
- Vinogradov, K. A., & [Виноградов К. А.]. (1958). *Очерки по истории отечественных гидробиологических исследований на Черном море [Essays on the history of the National hydrobiological studies in the Black Sea]*. Kiev: Издательство Академии Наук Украинской ССР [Publishing house of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR].
- Vinogradov, M. E., Shiganova, T. A., & Khoroshilov, V. S. (1995). The status of the main components of the zooplankton community in the Black Sea in 1993. *Oceanology*, *35*(3), 418–421.
- Virkkala, R., Heikkinen, R. K., Leikola, N., & Luoto, M. (2008). Projected large-scale range reductions of northern-boreal land bird species due to climate change. *Biological Conservation*, *141*(5), 1343–1353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.03.007>
- Virtanen, R., Grytnes, J. A., Lenoir, J., Luoto, M., Oksanen, J., Oksanen, L., & Svenning, J. C. (2013). Productivity-diversity patterns in arctic tundra vegetation. *Ecography*, *36*(3), 331–341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2012.07903.x>
- Virtanen, R., Johnston, A. E., Crawley, M. J., & Edwards, G. R. (2000). Bryophyte biomass and species richness on the park grass experiment, Rothamsted, UK. *Plant Ecology*, *151*(2), 129–141. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026533418357>
- Virtanen, T., Mikkola, K., Patova, E., & Nikula, A. (2002). Satellite image analysis of human caused changes in the tundra vegetation around the city of Vorkuta, north-European Russia. *Environmental Pollution*, *120*(3), 647–658. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491\(02\)00186-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491(02)00186-0)
- Visconti, P., Bakkenes, M., Baisero, D., Brooks, T., Butchart, S. H. M., Joppa, L., ... Rondinini, C. (2016). Projecting global biodiversity indicators under future development scenarios. *Conservation Letters*, *9*(1), 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12159>
- Vitasse, Y., Hoch, G., Randin, C. F., Lenz, A., Kollas, C., & Körner, C. (2012). Tree recruitment of European tree species at their current upper elevational limits in the Swiss Alps. *Journal of Biogeography*, *39*(8), 1439–1449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2012.02697.x>
- Voigt, C. C., Popa-Lisseanu, A. G., Niermann, I., & Kramer-Schadt, S. (2012). The catchment area of wind farms for European bats: A plea for international regulations. *Biological Conservation*, *153*, 80–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.04.027>
- Volvenko, I. V. (2014). The New Large Database of the Russian Bottom Trawl Surveys in the Far Eastern Seas and the North Pacific Ocean in 1977-2010. *International Journal of Environmental Monitoring and Analysis*, *2*(6), 302–312. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijema.20140206.12>
- Vörösmarty, C. J., McIntyre, P. B., Gessner, M. O., Dudgeon, D., Prusevich, a, Green, P., ... Davies, P. M. (2010). Global threats to human water security and river biodiversity. *Nature*, *467*(7315), 555–561. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09549>
- Vrahnakis, M., Janiřová, M., Růřina, S., Török, P., Venn, S., & Dengler, J. (2013). The European Dry Grassland Group (EDGG): stewarding Europe’s most diverse habitat type. In *Steppenlebensräume Europas—Gefährdung, Erhaltungsmaßnahmen und Schutz* (pp. 417–434).
- Vyaznikova, K. S., & [Вязникова К.С.]. (2014). Влияние хозяйств марикультуры приморского гребешка на химико-экологическое состояние прибрежных акваторий [The impact of

- mariculture scallop farming on the chemical and ecological status of coastal waters]. In *Актуальные проблемы освоения биологических ресурсов Мирового океана [Actual problems of the World Ocean biological resource using]* (pp. 65–67). Moscow.
- Wagner, C., & Adrian, R. (2011). Consequences of changes in thermal regime for plankton diversity and trait composition in a polymictic lake: A matter of temporal scale. *Freshwater Biology*, 56(10), 1949–1961. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2011.02623.x>
- Wagner Mingo, V., Schulte, U., Lötters, S., N. (2015). Risk evaluation of pesticide use to protected European reptile species. *Biological Conservation*, 191, 667–673.
- Walker, M. D., Wahren, H. C., Hollister, R. D., Henry, G. H. R., Ahlquist, L. E., Alatalo, J. M., ... Wookey, P. A. (2006). Plant community responses to experimental warming across the tundra biome. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 103(5), 1342–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0503198103>
- Wasmund, N., Göbel, J., & Bodungen, B. v. (2008). 100-years-changes in the phytoplankton community of Kiel Bight (Baltic Sea). *Journal of Marine Systems*, 73(3–4), 300–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2006.09.009>
- Wassmann, P., Duarte, C. M., Agustí, S., & Sejr, M. K. (2011). Footprints of climate change in the Arctic marine ecosystem. *Global Change Biology*, 17(2), 1235–1249. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02311.x>
- Wassmann, P., Kosobokova, K. N., Slagstad, D., Drinkwater, K. F., Hopcroft, R. R., Moore, S. E., ... Berge, J. (2015). The contiguous domains of Arctic Ocean advection: Trails of life and death. *Progress in Oceanography*, 139, 42–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2015.06.011>
- Watson, M., Wilson, J. M., Koshkin, M., Sherbakov, B., Karpov, F., & Gavrillov, A. (2006). Nest survival and productivity of the critically endangered Sociable Lapwing *Vanellus gregarius*, 489–502.
- Watson, R. A., & Morato, T. (2013). Fishing down the deep: Accounting for within-species changes in depth of fishing. *Fisheries Research*, 140, 63–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2012.12.004>
- Wedding, L. M., Reiter, S. M., Smith, C. R., Gjerde, K. M., Kittinger, J. N., Friedlander, a. M., ... Crowder, L. B. (2015). Managing mining of the deep seabed. *Science*, 349(6244), 144–145. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac6647>
- Weeda E.J. and al. (1990). *Floron Red Data List 1990. Red Data List of Extinct, Endangered and Vulnerable Plants in Netherlands in the period 1980 -1990.*
- Wegner, P., Kleinstäuber, G., Baum, F., & Schilling, F. (2005). Long-term investigation of the degree of exposure of German peregrine falcons (*Falco peregrinus*) to damaging chemicals from the environment. *Journal of Ornithology*, 146(1), 34–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-004-0053-6>
- Wehn, S., Lundemo, S., & Holten, J. I. (2014). Alpine vegetation along multiple environmental gradients and possible consequences of climate change. *Alpine Botany*, 124(2), 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00035-014-0136-9>
- Weinert, M., Mathis, M., Kröncke, I., Neumann, H., Pohlmann, T., & Reiss, H. (2016). Modelling climate change effects on benthos: Distributional shifts in the North Sea from 2001 to 2099. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 175, 157–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2016.03.024>
- Werger, M. J. A., & van Staaldouin, M. A. (2012). *Eurasian Steppes. Ecological Problems and Livelihoods in a Changing World.* (M. A. Werger, M.J.A. and van Staaldouin, Ed.). Dordrecht: Springer.

- Werner Disi, M., Mousa Disi, A.M., Y. (2006). *Acanthodactylus beershebensis*. . *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, 2006*, e.T61454A12488658.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2006.RLTS.T61454A12488658.en>
- Werth, S., Gugerli, F., Holderegger, R., Wagner, H. H., Csencsics, D., & Scheidegger, C. (2007). Landscape-level gene flow in *Lobaria pulmonaria*, an epiphytic lichen. *Molecular Ecology*, *16*(13), 2807–2815. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2007.03344.x>
- Werth, S., Wagner, H. H., Holderegger, R., Kalwij, J. M., & Scheidegger, C. (2006). Effect of disturbances on the genetic diversity of an old-forest associated lichen. *Molecular Ecology*, *15*(4), 911–921. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2006.02838.x>
- Wesche, K., Ambarlı, D., Kamp, J., Török, P., Treiber, J., & Dengler, J. (2016). The Palaearctic steppe biome: a new synthesis. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, *25*(12), 2197–2231.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1214-7>
- Wesche, K., Krause, B., Culmsee, H., & Leuschner, C. (2012). Fifty years of change in Central European grassland vegetation: Large losses in species richness and animal-pollinated plants. *Biological Conservation*, *150*(1), 76–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.02.015>
- Westerbom, M., Kilpi, M., & Mustonen, O. (2002). Blue mussels, *Mytilus edulis* at the edge of the range: population structure, growth and biomass along a salinity gradient in the north-eastern Baltic Sea. *Marine Biology*, *140*(5), 991–999. [https://doi.org/DOI 10.1007/s00227-001-0765-6](https://doi.org/DOI%2010.1007/s00227-001-0765-6)
- Westling, A. (2015). *Rödlistade arter i Sverige 2015*.
- Wiedmann, M., Aschan, M., Certain, G., Dolgov, A., Greenacre, M., Johannesen, E., ... Primicerio, R. (2014). Functional diversity of the Barents Sea fish community. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, *495*, 205–218. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10558>
- Wiens, J. J. (2016). Climate-Related Local Extinctions Are Already Widespread among Plant and Animal Species. *PLoS Biol*, *14*(12), e2001104. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001104>
- Wilkens, H., Culver, D.C., Humphreys, W. F. (2002). Grand Tour of the World's Underground. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, *11*, 261–263.
- Williams, W. (1981). Inland salt lakes: An introduction. *Hydrobiologia*, (81–82(1)), 1–14.
[https://doi.org/DOI: 10.1007/BF00048701](https://doi.org/DOI:10.1007/BF00048701)
- Wilson, J. B., Peet, R. K., Dengler, J., & Pärtel, M. (2012). Plant species richness: The world records. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, *23*(4), 796–802. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2012.01400.x>
- Wind, P., & Pihl, S. (2004). Den danske rødliste. - Danmarks Miljøundersøgelser, Aarhus Universitet, [2004]-. redlist.dmu.dk (opdateret i april 2010).
- Wirth, V., Hauck M, S. M. (2013). *Die Flechten Deutschlands* (Vol. 1 and 2). Stuttgart: Eugen Ulmer.
- Wirth, V., Hauck, M., Von Brackel, W., Cezanne, R., De Bruyn, U., Dürhammer, O., ... Heinrich, D. (2011). *Rote Liste und Artenverzeichnis der Flechten und flechtenbewohnenden Pilze Deutschlands* (Vol. 70). Naturschutz und Biologische Vielfalt.
- Wolf, A., Lazzarotto, P., & Bugmann, H. (2012). The relative importance of land use and climatic change in Alpine catchments. *Climatic Change*, *111*(2), 279–300.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0209-3>
- Wolseley, P. A. (1995). A global perspective on the status of lichens and their conservation. *Mitteilungen Der Eidgenössischen Forschungsanstalt Für Wald, Schnee Und Landschaft*, *70*, 11–

27.

- Woods, R. G., & Coppins, B. J. (2012). A Conservation Evaluation of British Lichens and Lichenicolous Fungi. Species status 13. *Species Status*, (13).
- Worm, B., Barbier, E. B., Beaumont, N., Duffy, J. E., Folke, C., Halpern, B. S., ... Watson, R. (2006). Impacts of biodiversity loss on ocean ecosystem services. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 314(November), 787–90. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1132294>
- Wraber T. and al. (1989). *Rdeci seznam ogrozenih praprotnic in semenk SR Slovenije The Red Data List of Threatened Vascular Plants in Socialist Republic of Slovenia*. Ljubljana.
- Wright, H. L., Lake, I. R., & Dolman, P. M. (2012). Agriculture—a key element for conservation in the developing world. *Conservation Letters*, 5(1), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00208.x>
- Yablokov, A. V., Belkovich, V. M., Borisov, V. I., [Яблоков А.В., Белькович В.М., & Борисов В.И.]. (1972). *Киты и дельфины [Whales and dolphins]*. Moscow: Наука [Science].
- Yablokov, A. V., Koltsov, N. K., Levchenko, V. F., Sechenov, I. M., & Kerzhentsev, A. S. (2014). The Transition to a Managed Evolution of Biosphere - the Way Out of the Global Environmental Crisis. *Астраханский Вестник Экологического Образования [Astrakhan Herald of Ecological Education]*, (3(29)), 28–37.
- Yakubov Kh.E. [Якубов Х.Э.], Yakubov M.A. [Якубов М.А.], & Yakubov S.Kh. [Якубов С.Х.]. (2011). *Коллекторно-дренажный сток Центральной Азии и оценка его использования на орошение [Collector-drainage waters in Central Asia and estimation of their use for irrigation]*. Tashkent: IWP AS Uzbekistan, SIC ICWC.
- Yakushev, E. V. (1999). An approach to modelling anoxic conditions in the Black Sea. In *Environmental degradation of the Black Sea: Challenges and Remedies* (pp. 93–108). Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Yankova, M., Pavlov, D., Ivanova, P., Karpova, E., Boltachev, A., Öztürk, B., ... Mgeladze, M. (2014). Marine fishes in the Black Sea: Recent conservation status. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 15(2), 366–379. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.700>
- Yoccoz, N. G., Delestrade, A., & Loison, A. (2010). Impact of climatic change on alpine ecosystems: inference and prediction. *Revue de Géographie Alpine*, 98(4), 1–10.
- Yokes, A., & Baki, M. (2012). Alien opisthobranchs from Turkish coasts : first record of *Plocamopherus tilesii* Bergh , 1877 from the Mediterranean, (April 2015).
- Yom-Tov, Y. (2003). Poaching of Israeli wildlife by guest workers. *Biological Conservation*, 110, 11–20.
- Zacharias, I., Dimitriou, E., Dekker, A., & Dorsman, E. (2007). Overview of temporary ponds in the Mediterranean region : Threats , management and conservation issues, 28(January), 1–9.
- Zagmajster, M., Culver, D. C., & Sket, B. (2008). Species richness patterns of obligate subterranean beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) in a global biodiversity hotspot - Effect of scale and sampling intensity. *Diversity and Distributions*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2007.00423.x>
- Zaharia, T., Maximov, V., Radu, G., Anton, E., Spinu, A., & Nenciu, M. (2014). Reconciling fisheries and habitat protection in Romanian coastal marine protected areas. *Scientia Marina*, 78(S1), 95–101. <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04028.25B>
- Zaitsev, Y. ., & Mamaev, V. (1997). *Marine biological diversity in the Black Sea : a study of change and decline*. New York: GEF BSEP United Nations Publications.

- Zalota, A. K., & Spiridonov, V. A. (2015). Understanding and forecasting invasive marine decapods distribution in the waters of Northern Eurasia. In *Abstracts of the 50th European Marine Biological Symposium 21-25 September* (p. 23). Helgoland .
- Zamin, T. J., Baillie, J. E. M., Miller, R. M., Rodríguez, J. P., Ardid, A., & Collen, B. (2010). National red listing beyond the 2010 target. *Conservation Biology*, 24(4), 1012–1020.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2010.01492.x>
- Zarfl, C., Lumsdon, A. E., & Tockner, K. (2015). A global boom in hydropower dam construction. *Aquatic Sciences*, 77, 161–170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-014-0377-0>
- Zarzycky K. and al. (2001). *Polska Czerwona księga roślin ed. 2 - Polish Red Data Book of Plants - Pteridophyta and Flowering Plants*. Crakow: Institute of Botany, Institute of Nature.
- Zavialov, P. O. (2005). *Physical Oceanography of the Dying Aral Sea*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer.
https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-27234-8_1
- Zechmeister, H. G., & Moser, D. (2001). The influence of agricultural land-use intensity on bryophyte species richness. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 10(10), 1609–1625.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1012008828522>
- Zektser, I. S. (2000). *Groundwater and the Environment: Applications for the Global Community*. (L. G. Everett, Ed.). CRC Press. Retrieved from
https://books.google.ru/books?hl=ru&lr=&id=V1g5SWyevXUC&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Zektser+I.S.,+Everett+L.G.+Groundwater+and+the+Environment:+Applications+for+the+Global+Community&ots=ZIsiUrsneX&sig=SzFGIJ7AdjO-NzpTZsPeTaumuM&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Zektser+I.S.%25
- ZEN. (2009). Climate Change in Central Asia by zoi environment - issuu. Retrieved September 20, 2017, from https://issuu.com/zoienvironment/docs/climate_change
- Zhakova L.V. [Жакова Л.В.]. (2013). О влиянии многолетних изменений солености Аральского моря на динамику сообществ макрофитов [Effect of long-term changes of the salinity on the water flora composition and distribution of macrophytes in Aral]. *Труды Зоологического Института РАН [Proceedings of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences]*, (Annex 3), 113–119. Retrieved from
https://www.zin.ru/journals/trudyzin/doc/vol_317_s2/TZ_317_2_Supplement_Zhakova.pdf
- Zimina, O. L., Lyubin, P. A., Jørgensen, L. L., Zakharov, D. V., & Lyubina, O. S. (2015). Decapod Crustaceans of the Barents Sea and adjacent waters: species composition and peculiarities of distribution. *Arthropoda Selecta*, 24(3), 417–428.
- Zoi. (2012). *Vital Caspian Graphics 2 - Opportunities, Aspirations and Challenges*. Zoï Environment Network. Retrieved from <http://www.grida.no/publications/vg/caspian2/>
- Zonn, I. S., Glantz, M. H., Kostianoy, A. G., & Kosarev, A. N. (2009). *The Aral Sea Encyclopedia*. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-85088-5_10
- Zotz, G., & Bader, M. Y. (2009a). Epiphytic Plants in a Changing World-Global: Change Effects on Vascular and Non-Vascular Epiphytes. In *Progress in Botany 70* (Vol. 70, pp. 147–170). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-68421-3>
- Zotz, G., & Bader, M. Y. (2009b). Epiphytic Plants in a Changing World-Global: Change Effects on Vascular and Non-Vascular Epiphytes. *Progress in Botany 70*, 70, 147–170.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-68421-3>
- Zvereva, E. L., & Kozlov, M. V. (2011). Impacts of industrial pollutants on bryophytes: A meta-analysis

of observational studies. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution*, 218(1–4), 573–586.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-010-0669-5>

Zwick, P. (2004). Key to the West Palearctic genera of stoneflies (Plecoptera) in the larval stage. *Limnologica - Ecology and Management of Inland Waters*, 34, 315–348.

Доклад о состоянии природопользования и об охране окружающей среды Краснодарского края в 2012 году [Report about the state of natural resources and environmental protection of the Krasnodar region in 2012]. (2013). Krasnodar: Administration and Ministry of Natural Resources of Krasnodar Region. Retrieved from <http://www.mprkk.ru/media/main/attachment/attach/df4e573261d9d541c06e3036616b6f5c.pdf>

Красная книга Российской Федерации (животные) [Red Data Book of Russian Federation (animals)]. (2001). Moscow: АСТ-Астрель [AST-Astrel]. Retrieved from <http://biodat.ru/db/rb/>

Красная книга Российской Федерации (растения и грибы) [Red Data Book of Russian Federation (plants and fungus)]. (2008). Moscow: КМК.

Физико-географический атлас мира [Physico-Geographical Atlas of the World]. (1964). Moscow: Академия наук СССР и главное управление геодезии и картографии ГК СССР [Academy of Science of the USSR and the Main Agency of Geodesia and Carthography of the USSR]. Retrieved from <http://geochemland.ru/uchebnye-materialy/fgam>